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Global least squares alignment with Kalman Filter fitted tracks

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ABSTRACT

The Kalman Filter approach to fitting charged particle trajectories is widespread in modern complex tracking systems. At the same time, the global fit of the detector geometry using Newton-Raphson fitted tracks remains the baseline method to achieve efficient and reliable track-based alignment which is free from weak-mode biases affecting physics measurements. A brief reminder of the global least squares formalism for track-based alignment and how Kalman Filter fitted tracks can be equivalently used for the global fit as well as potential computational benefits and use of additional constraints are reviewed.

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1 Introduction

Contemporary high energy physics experiments are equipped with high precision semiconductor tracking systems of high complexity. In order to exploit their full potential an accurate determination of their geometry is indispensable. This is usually achieved using so-called track-based alignment, whereby reconstructed tracks are used as survey (gauge) tools for the detector elements.

The Global χ^2 fit of the detector geometry using *least squares*-fitted (LS) tracks remains the baseline method to achieve efficient and reliable track-based alignment which is free from weak-mode biases affecting physics measurements. However, the *Kalman Filter* (KF) approach to fitting charged particle trajectories is widespread in modern complex tracking systems. The natural question arises: Can KF-fitted tracks be used for the the Global χ^2 alignment, and at what cost? In the following we recall the basic formalism and illustrate it with some very simplistic examples in order to gain better insight into the mechanism, in hope of adding a pedagogical value.

2 Track models

There is a number of different fitting methods and corresponding track models. They generally split into global, usually iterative, fit approaches and sequential update ones. From physics point of view, the only relevant information returned by the fit are track parameters and their covariance at its origin, usually the point of closest approach to the production vertex. In case of tracks used for alignment, however, these are rather track parameters at subsequent measurement planes together with their full covariance, notably the off-diagonal elements representing correlations between measurements in different tracking elements. An alignment fit additionally uses derivatives of track residuals* w.r.t. the track parameters which may take very different form depending on the track model.

2.1 The Least Squares track model

In the LS global approach track fit is based on the minimization of the χ^2 defined as:

$$\chi^2 = \boldsymbol{\rho}^T \mathbf{V}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\rho}, \quad \text{with} \quad \boldsymbol{\rho} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{r} \\ \boldsymbol{\theta} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{V} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \Omega & 0 \\ 0 & \Theta \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{r} represents a vector of residuals of measurements associated along the trajectory and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is a vector of trajectory deflection angles due to multiple Coulomb scattering (MCS) on the subsequent measurement planes. \mathbf{V} is an explicitly diagonal matrix representing measurement uncertainties and MCS standard deviations, hence is of size $n_r + 2n$, with n being the number of measurement planes and n_r the number of measurements[†] Tracks are parameterized by a single set of global parameters and two deflection angles per material surface (\approx measurement plane):

$$\boldsymbol{\pi} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\tau} \\ \boldsymbol{\theta} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\tau} = (d_0, z_0, \phi, \theta, Q/p) \quad (2)$$

corresponding to a vector of $5 + 2n$ parameters.

Track parameter covariance matrix is given by:

$$\mathbf{C} = \text{Cov}(\boldsymbol{\pi}) = (\mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{V}^{-1} \mathbf{H}) \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbf{H} \equiv \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\rho}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}}. \quad (3)$$

The crucial matrix \mathbf{H} of size $(n_r + 2n) \times (5 + 2n)$ is dense and generally highly nontrivial.

*A residual is defined as a distance between the position of the signal cluster and the track intersection with the sensitive detector element, usually measured in its local reference frame.

[†]It may, in general, be larger than n if a single plane provides more than one measurement, e.g. pixel detectors.

2.2 The Kalman Filter track model

The Kalman Filter track fitting is based on sequential update of the state vector during the forward *filtering* and backward *smoothing* processes [1]. A track is represented by n state vectors and their corresponding covariance matrices:

$$\mathbf{x}_k \equiv (l_1, l_2, \phi, \theta, Q/p)_k, \quad C_k \quad (4)$$

resulting in $5n$ track parameters:

$$\boldsymbol{\pi} \equiv (\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n). \quad (5)$$

Residuals and their covariance are reduced to the measurement ones only:

$$\boldsymbol{\rho} \equiv \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{m} - \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}), \quad \mathbf{V} \equiv \Omega, \quad (6)$$

while the scattering Θ contributes as the process random noise \mathbf{w} in the update of the state vector:

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = F_k \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{w}_k, \quad C_{k+1}^k = F_k C_k^k F_k^T + Q_k, \quad (7)$$

where F_k is the state propagator and $Q_k = \text{Cov}(\mathbf{w}_k)$. The derivatives $H \equiv \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\rho}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}}$, although given by a large $(n_r + 2n) \times 5n$ matrix are usually trivial and sparse. The full covariance matrix of the track parameters appears large ($5n \times 5n$):

$$C = \text{Cov}(\boldsymbol{\pi}) = \begin{pmatrix} C_1 & C_{1,2} & \dots & C_{1,n} \\ C_{2,1} & C_2 & \dots & C_{2,n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ C_{n,1} & C_{n,2} & \dots & C_n \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

and is never fully constructed in the normal KF process. Only the diagonal sub-matrices C_k (5×5) are obtained in:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{filtering :} \quad & C_k^k = (\mathbf{1} - K_k H_k) C_k^{k-1}, & K_k &= C_k^{k-1} H_k^T (V_k + H_k C_k^{k-1} H_k^T)^{-1} \\ \text{smoothing :} \quad & C_k^k = C_k^k + S_k (C_{k+1}^k - C_{k+1}^k) S_k^T, & S_k &= (F_k)^{-1} (C_{k+1}^k - Q_k) (C_{k+1}^k)^{-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where, K_k is the Kalman *gain matrix* while S_k is the commonly called the *smoother gain matrix*. The smoothing step is necessary to propagate the full information about all measurements on the track back to its origin.

3 The Global χ^2 alignment

The track-based alignment of the tracking system relies on the minimization of the χ^2 summed over all considered tracks [2]:

$$\chi_{\text{global}}^2 = \sum_i \chi_i^2, \quad \frac{d\chi_{\text{global}}^2}{d\boldsymbol{\alpha}} = 0, \quad \boldsymbol{\rho} \equiv \boldsymbol{\rho}(\boldsymbol{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), \boldsymbol{\alpha}), \quad (10)$$

where both the the fitted tracks and the position detector measurements explicitly depend on alignment parameters $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$. The full derivative with respect to the alignment parameters is then given by:

$$\frac{d}{d\boldsymbol{\alpha}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \boldsymbol{\alpha}} + \frac{d\boldsymbol{\pi}}{d\boldsymbol{\alpha}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \boldsymbol{\alpha}} - A^T V^{-1} H C \frac{\partial}{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}}, \quad \text{where } A \equiv \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\rho}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\alpha}}. \quad (11)$$

In the limit of small corrections, the χ_{global}^2 minimization problem can be solved using a linear expansion[‡]:

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\alpha} = - \underbrace{(\mathcal{M}^{-1})}_{\text{Cov}(\boldsymbol{\alpha})} \mathcal{R} \quad (12)$$

[‡]In practice this condition is sufficiently well satisfied. Nonetheless, alignment usually allows for a few iterations in order to mitigate residual nonlinearities.

with

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{R} &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{d\chi^2}{d\boldsymbol{\alpha}} = \sum_{\text{tracks}} A^T V^{-1} R V^{-1} \boldsymbol{\rho}, \\ \mathcal{M} &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2\chi^2}{d\boldsymbol{\alpha}^2} = \sum_{\text{tracks}} A^T V^{-1} R V^{-1} A.\end{aligned}\tag{13}$$

$R = V - HCH^T$ is the full covariance of the residuals of the track fit, the cornerstone of the alignment principle. Any track model that is capable of returning this information is suitable to provide input for alignment.

4 The Kalman Filter tracks for alignment

In order to use KF-fitted tracks for alignment one needs to recover the off-diagonal elements of the C matrix. It has been shown that these can be obtained recursively using the already known smoother gain matrix [3]:

$$C_{k,l} = S_k C_{k+1,l}.\tag{14}$$

The procedure requires $125n(n-1)$ multiplications, provided S_k are known from the track fit. Calculation of $R = V - HCH^T$ appears faster for the KF than LS tracks thanks to the sparse nature of H .

Constraints on KF track parameters can be introduced just as in the LS fit [2] by adding pseudo-measurements in the filtering. It can be thought of as providing a meaningful prior.

If several tracks have been fitted to a common vertex, the covariance of each track at the vertex position $C_0^{(i)}$ gets modified by the additional measurement [4]. This can be propagated forward to the states at subsequent measurement planes to yield their full covariance:

$$\tilde{C}_{k,l}^{(i)} = C_{k,l}^{(i)} + C_{k,0}^{(i)} \left(C_0^{(i)} \right)^{-1} \left(\tilde{C}_0^{(i)} - C_0^{(i)} \right) \left(C_0^{(i)} \right)^{-1} C_{0,l}^{(i)}\tag{15}$$

Even more importantly, the vertex introduces precious correlations between any two states in any two tracks:

$$\tilde{C}_{k,l}^{(i,j)} = \mathbf{0} + C_{k,0}^{(i)} \left(C_0^{(i)} \right)^{-1} \left(\tilde{C}_0^{(i,j)} - \mathbf{0} \right) \left(C_0^{(j)} \right)^{-1} C_{0,l}^{(j)}\tag{16}$$

All above additional constraints allow to mitigate weak modes of alignment which lead to systematic deformations and can bias reconstructed track parameters.

5 Super-simple examples

In the following we illustrate solutions to alignment problem using the simplest possible setups and ignoring process noise (MCS) which in real case always has to be included.

5.1 LS track fit

Let us consider a LS fit of a straight line through three equidistant vertical planes providing measurements with a common uncertainty σ , as schematically illustrated in Fig.1a. The measurement covariance, derivative matrix and the resulting covariance matrix of the fitted parameters $\boldsymbol{\pi} = (a_0, b_0)$ are given by:

$$V = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma^2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad H = \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\rho}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\pi}} = \begin{pmatrix} d & 1 \\ 2d & 1 \\ 3d & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad C = (H^T V^{-1} H)^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\sigma^2}{2d^2} & \frac{-\sigma^2}{d} \\ \frac{-\sigma^2}{d} & \frac{7\sigma^2}{3} \end{pmatrix}$$

Hence, we get the full covariance of the fitted residuals:

$$R = V - HCH^T = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\sigma^2}{6} & \frac{-2\sigma^2}{6} & \frac{\sigma^2}{6} \\ \frac{-2\sigma^2}{6} & \frac{4/\sigma^2}{6} & \frac{-2\sigma^2}{6} \\ \frac{\sigma^2}{6} & \frac{-2\sigma^2}{6} & \frac{\sigma^2}{6} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Figure 1: A fit of a straight line through three equidistant measurements (in the vertical direction) with common uncertainties. (a) the LS fit, (b) the KF fit.

5.2 KF track fit

Now, let us perform a KF fit through the same three equidistant measurements with a common uncertainty σ , as illustrated in Fig.1b. The derivative matrix takes a particularly simple, sparse form as track parameters are defined in the local reference frame of the measurement plane. The track parameter[§] covariance matrix is obtained by the filtering and smoothing to get the block-diagonal elements, as shown black in Eq. 9. The remaining off-diagonal ones (in blue) are recovered recursively using Eq. 14:

$$H = \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \pi} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad C = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\sigma^2}{2d^2} & \frac{-\sigma^2}{2d} & \frac{\sigma^2}{2d^2} & \frac{-\sigma^2}{2d} & \frac{\sigma^2}{2d^2} & \frac{-\sigma^2}{2d} \\ \frac{-\sigma^2}{2d} & \frac{5\sigma^2}{6} & 0 & \frac{\sigma^2}{3} & \frac{\sigma^2}{2d} & \frac{\sigma^2}{6} \\ \frac{\sigma^2}{2d^2} & 0 & \frac{\sigma^2}{2d^2} & 0 & \frac{\sigma^2}{2d^2} & 0 \\ \frac{-\sigma^2}{2d} & \frac{\sigma^2}{3} & 0 & \frac{\sigma^2}{3} & \frac{\sigma^2}{2d} & \frac{\sigma^2}{3} \\ \frac{\sigma^2}{2d^2} & \frac{\sigma^2}{2d} & \frac{\sigma^2}{2d^2} & \frac{\sigma^2}{2d} & \frac{\sigma^2}{2d^2} & \frac{\sigma^2}{2d} \\ \frac{-\sigma^2}{2d} & \frac{\sigma^2}{6} & 0 & \frac{\sigma^2}{3} & \frac{\sigma^2}{2d} & \frac{5\sigma^2}{6} \end{pmatrix}$$

Despite very different form of the derivatives and track covariance, the resulting full covariance of the fitted residuals is exactly identical to the one obtained with the LS fit:

$$R = V - HCH^T = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\sigma^2}{6} & \frac{-2\sigma^2}{6} & \frac{\sigma^2}{6} \\ \frac{-2\sigma^2}{6} & \frac{4\sigma^2}{6} & \frac{-2\sigma^2}{6} \\ \frac{\sigma^2}{6} & \frac{-2\sigma^2}{6} & \frac{\sigma^2}{6} \end{pmatrix},$$

which is the sought after result.

5.3 The Global χ^2 alignment solution

As a next step we find solution to the alignment, or rather the alignment parameter weight matrix \mathcal{M} , which after inversion gives the covariance of the alignment parameters. For sake of simplicity, let us assume that each measurement belongs to a vertical measurement plane with just a single degree of freedom (DoF), i.e. can move in the measurement direction, as shown in Fig. 2.

The derivatives of the residuals w.r.t. alignment parameters are trivially obtained and give us the system of linear equations for the alignment problem:

$$A \equiv \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \alpha} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{M} = A^T V^{-1} R V^{-1} A = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{6\sigma^2} & \frac{-2}{6\sigma^2} & \frac{1}{6\sigma^2} \\ \frac{-2}{6\sigma^2} & \frac{4}{6\sigma^2} & \frac{-2}{6\sigma^2} \\ \frac{1}{6\sigma^2} & \frac{-2}{6\sigma^2} & \frac{1}{6\sigma^2} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{R} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{r_1 - 2r_2 + r_3}{6\sigma^2} \\ \frac{-2r_1 + 4r_2 - 2r_3}{6\sigma^2} \\ \frac{r_1 - 2r_2 + r_3}{6\sigma^2} \end{pmatrix}.$$

[§]Recall, that in the KF model tracks are parameterized at each measurement plane, in our case by three pairs of local track parameter (a_i, b_i) ; $\pi = (a_1, b_1, a_2, b_2, a_3, b_3)$.

Figure 2: Alignment of three measurement planes with one DoF (vertical translation) each. X_1, X_2, X_3 show the three eigenmodes of the solution. The modes marked in red are singular in the unconstrained solution.

The matrix \mathcal{M} is singular leading to two *weak modes*[¶] of the alignment solution:

$$\lambda_1 = 0, \quad X_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_2 = 0, \quad X_2 = \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_3 = \frac{1}{\sigma^2}, \quad X_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -2 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

5.4 Adding constraints on the Global χ^2 alignment solution

The free-flying solution obtained in the previous section does not represent a meaningful solution in practical terms. In order for it to be so, one needs to impose additional, well motivated constraints in order to mitigate the weak (singular) modes. In alignment problems there are three types of such constraints: on alignment parameters (or their linear combinations), on individual track parameters and on common vertices of several tracks^{||}. The first one is straightforward and not discussed here. The latter two enter the alignment solution via the covariance of the fitted track parameters.

In our simple example let us assume a perfect knowledge of the a_0 parameter. In the KF process this is equivalent to using a prior for a_0 with an infinitesimally small uncertainty. The constraint results in removing one of the two weak modes, the skew:

$$\lambda_1 = 0, \quad X_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_2 = \frac{1}{\sigma^2}, \quad X_2 = \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_3 = \frac{1}{\sigma^2}, \quad X_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -2 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The resulting \mathcal{M} matrix is still singular due to the remaining global translation, though. This one could be removed by either introducing an arbitrary constraint on the motion of any of the measurement planes or imposing a constraint on the b_0 track parameter.

Another and very powerful constraint comes with the requirement of a common vertex of two or more tracks. In order to illustrate this, let us consider the setup shown in Fig. 3. Two tracks (A and B) are fitted through three detector elements. For the sake of maximal simplicity only the two elements at position d are free to move in the vertical direction, while the measurement plane at $2d$ remains frozen. The two eigenmodes of the solution, X_1 and X_2 would both be singular without any further constraints.

Imposing a requirement of the common vertex ($y^A(0) = y^B(0) = b_0$) correlates parameters of the two tracks. At the vertex position ($x = 0$) the joint covariance matrix of the two track parameters ($a_0^A, b_0^A, a_0^B, b_0^B$)

[¶]In alignment problems, it is customary to use the term *weak mode* for both strictly singular eigenmodes of the solution as well as the eigenmodes with unacceptably large uncertainties. Here, we are dealing with explicitly singular solutions, of course.

^{||}Other methods of mitigating weak modes are known, e.g. using tracks with different topology, notably cosmic muons. However, this does not require any special treatment from the formal point of view and as such is not discussed here.

Figure 3: Alignment of two measurement planes with one DoF (vertical translation) each and using two tracks. X_1, X_2 show the eigenmodes of the solution. The mode marked in blue loses its singularity after imposing the common vertex constraint.

reads:

$$C_0^{AB} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{11\sigma^2}{10d^2} & \frac{-15\sigma^2}{10d} & \frac{9\sigma^2}{10d^2} & \frac{-15\sigma^2}{10d} \\ \frac{-15\sigma^2}{10d} & \frac{25\sigma^2}{10} & \frac{-15\sigma^2}{10d} & \frac{25\sigma^2}{10} \\ \frac{9\sigma^2}{10d^2} & \frac{-15\sigma^2}{10d} & \frac{11\sigma^2}{10d^2} & \frac{-15\sigma^2}{10d} \\ \frac{-15\sigma^2}{10d} & \frac{25\sigma^2}{10} & \frac{-15\sigma^2}{10d} & \frac{25\sigma^2}{10} \end{pmatrix}$$

The matrix \mathcal{M} is singular due to the unconstrained vertex position. However, the other singularity is removed via correlation between A and B :

$$\lambda_1 = 0, \quad X_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_2 = \frac{4}{5\sigma^2}, \quad X_2 = \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

As a result, such geometry is free from deformation which would otherwise compromise vertexing capability of the detector.

5.5 Conclusions

In track-based alignment problems tracks are merely tools providing correlations between measurements recorded by detector elements. Kalman Filter provides a track fit which is equivalent to the least squares one but represented in a different model. The off-diagonal elements of the covariance matrix of the track parameters, i.e. correlations between different track Kalman states, can be recovered recursively using the smoother gain matrix. The full calculation does not appear computationally more intense than in the LS case. It may, however, be more numerically stable thanks to very simple structure of the H matrix, hence democratic treatment of all measurements. In turn, H matrix of the LS track fit is dense and highly nontrivial. Constraints on track parameters can be introduced as in the LS by adding pseudo-measurements in the filtering process. Other constraints, such as common vertex or invariant mass of several tracks, etc. can be equally introduced with full propagation to Kalman states which does not involve large matrix inversions.

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ACTS Vertexing and Deep Learning Vertex Finding

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ABSTRACT

The reconstruction of particle trajectories and their associated vertices is an essential task in the event reconstruction of most high energy physics experiments. In order to maintain or even improve upon the current performance of tracking and vertexing algorithms under the upcoming challenges of increasing energies and ever increasing luminosities in the future, major software upgrades are required. Based on the well-tested ATLAS tracking and vertexing software, *ACTS (A Common Tracking Software)* aims to provide a modern, experiment-independent set of track- and vertex reconstruction software, specifically designed for parallel execution. Exploiting modern software concepts, thread-safe implementations of iterative and multi-adaptive primary vertex finding algorithms, as well as a full Billoir vertex fitter, Z-Scan- and Gaussian track density seed finder, are available in ACTS and being deployed in the multi-threaded version of the ATLAS software framework AthenaMT. In addition to these computationally optimized reimplementations of classical primary vertexing algorithms, all of which have been validated against the original ATLAS implementations, ACTS provides a solid code base for evaluating new approaches to primary vertex finding, such as applications of sophisticated deep learning methods. Associating tracks to the correct vertex candidate is a crucial step in vertexing and will become even more important in the high-pileup environments expected for HL-LHC or FCC-hh in order not to merge close-by vertices. Learning a track representation in an embedding space in such a way that tracks emerging from a common vertex are close together while tracks from neighboring vertices are further separated from one another allows for the determination of a similarity score between a pair of tracks. Constructing undirected, edge-weighted graphs from these results allows the subsequent usage of classical graph algorithms or graph neural networks for clustering tracks to vertex candidates. The current status of the ACTS vertexing as well as new results on deep learning approaches to vertex finding will be presented in this talk.

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1 Introduction

Future upgrades and improvements of particle accelerators, like the high-luminosity upgrade of the LHC (HL-LHC, [1]), will impose new and never before seen challenges to the respective experiments and their event processing software.

High pile-up scenarios with expected $\langle\mu\rangle \simeq 200$ for the HL-LHC or even higher values for future particle accelerators like the FCC-hh [2] will lead to extremely high track multiplicities and thus extreme conditions, especially for track- and vertex reconstruction software tools. Major software upgrades will therefore be required in order to maintain or even improve upon the current physics performance while being able to fully exploit the available computational resources. A fully functional, multi-threading capable vertexing suite and novel approaches to vertex (seed) finding within the detector-independent track- and vertex-reconstruction software ACTS will be presented in the following.

2 ACTS Vertexing

2.1 The ACTS Project

ACTS (*A Common Tracking Software*) is a detector-independent track- and vertex reconstruction toolkit, aiming to provide a modern, highly-performant and open source tracking software for particle physics experiments. It is designed for parallel code execution and is based on the ATLAS track reconstruction software [5], which has been rigorously tested over the last 15 years and always served to highest satisfaction. In order to ensure high code quality, the ACTS coding guidelines demand in addition to modern C++ and thread-safe code with const-correctness and stateless engines also the minimization of virtual inheritance and externals dependencies.

Apart from computationally optimized re-implementations of ATLAS tracking- and vertexing code, ACTS offers a solid code base for evaluating novel approaches to track- and vertex reconstruction.

2.2 The ACTS Vertexing Suite

Several ATLAS primary vertexing algorithms have been re-implemented in ACTS and numerically validated with respect to the original ATLAS implementations. Two major vertexing approaches are available in ACTS: A so-called *fitting-after-finding* approach, manifested through the `IterativeVertexFinder` (IVF) with a *Billoir* vertex fitter [3] and a *finding-through-fitting* approach, manifested through an adaptive multi-vertex fitter deployed by the `AdaptiveMultiVertexFinder` (AMVF) [4].

The modular design of the vertexing software allows for easy exchange of various components, such as the easy usage of different vertex seed finders. Currently, the ACTS vertexing suite comprises three different vertex seed finder, the `ZScanVertexFinder`, the `GaussianTrackDensityVertexFinder` and a newly developed vertex seed finder (see Section 2.3.2), the `GaussianGridTrackDensityVertexFinder`. In addition, also tools for linearizing tracks, estimating impact parameters and deterministic annealing are available in the ACTS vertexing suite.

A relative comparison between the ACTS and ATLAS implementation in terms of number of reconstructed vertices and number of tracks associated to a vertex for the `AdaptiveMultiVertexFinder` together with the `GaussianTrackDensityVertexFinder` as an example is shown in Fig. 1. A perfect agreement on reconstructed objects on all tested events can be seen.

Fig. 2a shows the AMVF vertex z-position resolution with respect to the original ATLAS implementation where a very good agreement within micrometers is observable. Small deviations between the two algorithms are expected here as the ACTS vertexing deploys the *ACTS Propagator* with the *ACTS EigenStepper* which varies in its internal implementation from its ATLAS counterpart.

Although no algorithmic changes have been made (yet) to the ACTS vertexing algorithms, a significant speedup with respect to the ATLAS version of $t_{\text{AMVF}}^{\text{ATLAS}}/t_{\text{AMVF}}^{\text{ACTS}} \approx 1.4$ can be seen in Fig. 2b for the AMVF implementation, exclusively arising from various code improvements in the ACTS AMVF implementation.

Figure 1: Relative comparisons of the ACTS Adaptive Multi Vertex Finder with respect to the original ATLAS implementation on $\langle \mu \rangle = 60$ $t\bar{t}$ -data in terms of number of reconstructed vertices (a) and number of tracks associated to a vertex (b) with perfect agreement.

Figure 2: Vertex z-position resolution where almost perfect agreement is met (a) and CPU performance speedup (b) of the ACTS Adaptive Multi Vertex Finder with respect to the original ATLAS AMVF implementation on $\langle \mu \rangle = 60$ $t\bar{t}$ -data.

2.3 ACTS Vertexing Developments

As ACTS provides a solid test bed for developing and testing novel tracking- and vertexing methods, several studies on new vertexing techniques are currently being conducted and will be presented in the following.

2.3.1 Track Linearization using the ACTS Propagator

The track linearization tool that is currently available in ACTS as the `HelicalTrackLinearizer` is based on the ATLAS `LinearizedTrackFactory` [5] which assumes an underlying helical track model for linearizing tracks. The linearized track parameters

$$\vec{q} = \vec{q}(\vec{r}, \vec{p}) = A\vec{r} + B\vec{p} + \vec{c}_0 \quad (1)$$

are a function of the global position \vec{r} , momentum \vec{p} , a constant term \vec{c}_0 and the Jacobians A and B which represent the transformations from the \vec{r} and \vec{p} space to the track parameters space \vec{q} , respectively. Assuming helical tracks, A and B can be analytically derived and computed. Since this assumption is only a special case for detectors with an ideal solenoid magnetic field and thus not robust in all detector regions, a generalization of linearizing tracks using Eq.(1) is currently being investigated in ACTS, potentially harmonizing primary and secondary vertexing with common math kernels. This process will involve the generalization of the

Jacobians A and B which can be computed in all detector regions and made available to the vertex finders by the *ACTS Propagator*. Since time propagation is fully integrated in the *ACTS Propagator* and the time component t is thus available also in the Jacobians A and B , the global position \vec{r} in Eq.(1) will be expanded to $\vec{r} \rightarrow \mathbf{x} = (\vec{r}, t)$ and Eq.(1) becomes

$$\vec{q} = \vec{q}(\mathbf{x}, \vec{p}) = A(t)\mathbf{x} + B(t)\vec{p} + \vec{c}_0. \quad (2)$$

Besides being able to harmonize primary and secondary vertexing, the generalized track linearization equation Eq.(2) will allow time-dependent vertex fitting which can help to resolve spatially superimposed but temporally distinct vertices.

2.3.2 Gaussian Grid Track Density Vertex Finder

The *Gaussian Track Density Seed Finder* presented in [6] models tracks as two-dimensional Gaussian distributions in the $(d_0 - z_0)$ plane in the form of

$$P(r, z) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{|\Sigma|}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}((r-d_0), (z-z_0))^T \Sigma^{-1} ((r-d_0), (z-z_0))}. \quad (3)$$

The track density distributions, which are centered around the respective impact parameter points (d_0, z_0) with their shapes determined by the track covariance submatrices

$$\Sigma = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma^2(d_0) & \sigma(d_0, z_0) \\ \sigma(d_0, z_0) & \sigma^2(z_0) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

are superimposed and the maximum along the beam axis is considered the vertex seed position. Based on the assumption that the seed position is located in the vicinity of a track, the summed track density values and their first and second derivatives are evaluated along the beam axis for every single track, allowing for subsequent Δz -steps in the direction of the density maximum if the second derivative is negative (and hence the track position close to a density maximum).

This approach has proven to give excellent physics performances [6], however, since it relies on the calculation of continuous track density values which are algorithmically hard to cache, it can become computationally very expensive, especially for high track multiplicity environments.

In order to maintain the excellent physics performance while mitigating the CPU performance issues for high pile-up events, the *ACTS Gaussian Grid Track Density Vertex Finder* models tracks as two-dimensional Gaussian density distributions on a grid, similarly centered around (d_0, z_0) with their shapes defined by Σ . Fig. 3 shows an example of three single track density distributions in the $(d_0 - z_0)$ plane grid. Since primary vertices are expected along the beam axis, and hence only the density distribution along this axis is of interest, only the respective one-dimensional track contribution vectors (red) need to be calculated. The superposition of all track density vectors along the beam axis results in the overall density beam axis vector from which the maximum bin can easily be determined and its center z -position considered the vertex position.

During the iterative processes in vertex finding, the track density contribution vectors need to be calculated and summed only once in the very first iteration and can be easily cached. In subsequent iterations, where single seed tracks have possibly been removed, the former contributions of the removed tracks can just be deducted from the overall beam axis density vector and a new maximum can be found.

This approach avoids the (possibly massive amount of) recalculation of track densities during vertex finding and thus results in a significant speedup with respect to the original continuous version [6] of this algorithm, as can be seen in Fig. 4b. Fig. 4a shows the vertex z -position resolution of this approach where very good agreement on micrometer level is observable. The resulting position resolutions and speedups are subject to density grid bin width optimization, where coarser bin sizes yield even higher speedups with lower vertex position accuracy.

In addition to the seed vertex z -position, also the seed width σ_z can be estimated exploiting the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the track density peak according to the relation

$$\sigma_z = \frac{\text{FWHM}}{\sqrt{8 \ln(2)}}. \quad (5)$$

Figure 3: Example of three single Gaussian track density distributions in the $d_0 - z_0$ -impact parameter grid. The two horizontal black lines indicate the beam axis vector at which the track density contributions (red) are calculated.

Figure 4: Vertex z -position resolution (a) and CPU performance speedup (b) of the Gaussian Grid Track Density Vertex Finder with respect to the original continuous implementation of this algorithm [6].

2.3.3 Siamese Neural Network Vertex Finder

Vertex finding is the process of grouping reconstructed particle tracks into disjoint sets of tracks, believed to have originated from a common interaction vertex, and will become more and more challenging for high pile-up environments at future particle accelerators. A novel approach to vertex finding, based on a so-called Siamese Neural Network (SNN) [7], is currently being investigated in ACTS.

As shown in Fig. 5, the SNN utilizes a single instance of a simple feed-forward *Track embedding network* N twice with shared weights. N takes a 20-dimensional track vector (5 perigee parameters + 15 flattened covariance matrix entries) x_i for track i as input and returns an embedding representation vector h_i of this track which is consecutively fed, together with the embedding vector h_j of track j , into a distance function $d(h_i, h_j)$. d can now be used to determine the SNN output, a similarity score s that equals 1 if the tracks are *similar* (i.e. they stem from the same vertex) or 0 if they do not originate from the same vertex.

Iterating through an event of z_0 -sorted tracks, the similarity scores of all combinations of track pairs within a certain z_0 -window can be determined using the SNN and an adjacency matrix M can be constructed, where M_{ij} represents the score that track i and j originated from a common vertex (see Fig.6a). The resulting block structure in M can be exploited to identify each block with a set of tracks stemming from the same vertex and hence find vertices. Fig. 6b shows the resulting number of reconstructed vertices for different numbers of true vertices on truth smeared track events by making use of this simple approach of counting non-zero blocks in the adjacency matrix. Non-zero interconnections between single blocks can lead to vertex merging and thus a more elaborated strategy for reconstructing vertices from the adjacency matrix, utilizing *graphs*, will be pursued. Graphs, where nodes are identified as tracks and edges as similarity scores can easily be constructed from adjacency matrices and clustered into subgraphs (i.e. vertices) using classical as well as machine learning-based graph clustering algorithms such as Graph Neural Network.

Figure 5: Siamese neural network for vertex finding which takes a pair of track vectors (x_i, x_j) as input, finds an embedding representation (h_i, h_j) that minimizes a metric d in such a way that it outputs a score s indicating if the tracks originated from the same vertex ($s = 1$) or not ($s = 0$).

Figure 6: (a) Adjacency matrix constructed using a SNN with two visible vertex candidates with four (blue) and three (red) tracks, respectively. (b) Number of found vertices from counting non-zero blocks in the adjacency matrix on ACTS truth smeared track events.

3 Conclusions

ACTS offers a modern, MT-capable vertexing suite with various highly performant primary vertexing tools, validated against their original ATLAS implementations. Ongoing vertex reconstruction developments include both, classical developments such as a generalized track linearization and a novel extremely fast grid density vertex finder, as well as very promising machine learning approaches to vertex finding that will be extended to even more powerful graph methods in the future.

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Fast tracking for the HL-LHC ATLAS detector

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ABSTRACT

During the High-Luminosity LHC, up to 200 simultaneous inelastic proton-proton collisions per bunch crossing are expected. This poses a significant challenge for the track reconstruction and its associated computing requirements due to the unprecedented number of particle hits in the tracker system. In order to tackle this challenge, dedicated algorithms have been developed to speed up the track reconstruction and further optimise the default algorithms of the ATLAS detector. The performance of this Fast Track Reconstruction is presented and compared to the one of the default Phase-II track reconstruction.

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1 Introduction

During the Run-2 the ATLAS experiment recorded data from up to $\langle\mu\rangle \approx 70$ proton-proton collisions per bunch-crossing (pile-up) as shown in Figure 1(a). For the HL-LHC era a pile-up regime between 140 and 200 is expected. In order to estimate the corresponding reconstruction time, a high- μ run was performed in 2017 using the Run-2 detector and software. As shown in Figure 1(b), the reconstruction time is increasing exponentially as a function of pile-up. This illustrates that the HL-LHC will become a challenge for tracking. However, it should be noted that the ATLAS detector was designed for a pile-up of $\langle\mu\rangle \lesssim 23$ and the software

Figure 1: Recorded Run-2 pile-up [1] (a) and CPU requirements for track reconstruction vs. η including high- μ run [2] (b).

was used unchanged for that high- μ run. This clearly shows that for the HL-LHC scenario work and R&D has to be performed in several areas: a new detector design that targets this challenging environment, but also an optimised reconstruction software that is based on the current track reconstruction software augmented or enhanced by new components as an outcome of dedicated R&D initiatives. These areas are presented in the following.

2 ATLAS Phase-II tracking

The current Inner Detector (ID) of the ATLAS experiment will due to radiation damage come to the end of its lifetime by the end of Run-3. Additionally, the ID operates at the current pile-up scenario at its bandwidth limit and the Transition Radiation Tracker (TRT) has up to 50% occupancy at $\langle\mu\rangle = 70$. In order to provide high tracking performance in the HL-LHC era, the ID will be replaced by an all-Silicon Inner Tracker (ITk)[3]. This new tracking detector was designed to provide a high tracking performance at up to $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$. As shown in Figure 2(a), it consists of five pixel layers which cover a pseudorapidity range of $|\eta| < 4$ and four strip layers which cover a range of $|\eta| < 2.7$. The ID for comparison covers a range of $|\eta| < 2.5$. The design of the ITk provides an approximate constant minimum number of hits over the full range of $|\eta| < 4$ as shown in Figure 2(b). Thus this design allows to obtain a high tracking performance over its full η range at $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$ while the bandwidth and the pixel surface is kept at a minimum.

Beside the replacement of the detector hardware, an adaption of the Run-2 tracking software to the ITk was performed. As the expected number of hits is increased, tighter track requirements, compared to Run-2, can be applied[4]. The applied track selection cuts result in a high and stable tracking efficiency over the full covered range as shown in Figure 3(a). Since the requirements for the number of hits per track were increased compared to Run-2, the fake rate can be decreased as shown in Figure 3(b). These simulations demonstrate the potential in tracking performance of the ITk for the HL-LHC era.

Figure 2: R-z view of the ITk (a) and the obtained number of hits per η (b) [5].

Figure 3: Comparison between the ID at $\langle \mu \rangle = 20$ and the ITk at $\langle \mu \rangle = 200$ [6]. The left plot shows the tracking efficiency versus $|\eta|$, the right plot show the fake rate versus $|\eta|$.

2.1 Computing requirements

The ITk simulations are currently performed using the Run-2 software. Thereby the biggest contributions to the event processing time are given by the (Silicon) Track Finding and the Ambiguity Resolution as shown in Table 1. Furthermore a major contribution to the ID is given by the TRT and Back Tracking. The tuning of the track reconstruction setup is always done with the aim to achieve a maximum physics

Table 1: CPU requirements for the individual stages of track reconstruction using the Run-2 software as presented in Reference [3]. The tabular shows a comparison between the contributions of the ITk at $\langle \mu \rangle = 200$ and the ID at $\langle \mu \rangle = 20$ as well as the total amount. The numbers are given in units of HS06s.

Detector	$\langle \mu \rangle$	Cluster Finding	Space Points	Si Track Finding	Ambiguity Resolution	TRT+Back Tracking	Primary Vertex	Total ITk/ID
ITk Layout	200	22	6.5	78	97	-	6	219
Run-2	20	1.5	0.7	23	15	19	0.5	64

performance within the available computing budget. Nonetheless the overview of CPU requirements, shown in Figure 4(a), predicts that the ITk with the Run-2 software using cuts adapted for the HL-LHC conditions achieves a better CPU performance at $\langle \mu \rangle = 200$ than the ID during Run-2 at $\langle \mu \rangle = 60$. The achieved improvement is a combination of the design of the new tracking detector together with an adequate adaption

of the track reconstruction software.

These improvements in the Inner Tracking system have been used to extrapolate the full ATLAS event reconstruction time to the HL-LHC environment, see Figure 4(b). Within the scenario using the current computing performance (blue circles) the track reconstruction requires $\approx 45\%$ of the CPU resources. Furthermore this extrapolation is still far above the assumed available resources, shown as black solid lines. In

Figure 4: Left: CPU requirements for track reconstruction with the ID during Run-2 and the simulated ITK as a function of the mean pile-up $\langle\mu\rangle$. The contributions of the Track Finding and the Ambiguity Resolution to the total reconstruction are shown separately [5]. Right: Extrapolation of ATLAS CPU requirements as a function of time. The blue circles labelled as Baseline show the estimates with the currently unchanged track reconstruction, while Conservative and Aggressive R&D scenarios lead to the improvements shown as blue triangles. The solid black lines show the assumed available CPU resources [2].

order to speed up the track reconstruction two different approaches can be performed. The first one is a speed up of the existing track reconstruction code, the second one is the R&D of new approaches. The first topic will be discussed in the following section. An overview of the second topic is presented in Section 4.

3 Fast track reconstruction

The fast track reconstruction[7], originally motivated by the question of whether a high level software trigger would be possible for HL-LHC conditions, was a dedicated study to determine how the current ATLAS track reconstruction workflow can be modified and tuned in order to achieve the desired HL-LHC event throughput. The study was performed using the ITk detector geometry at a pile-up of 140 and 200. The goal of the study was to decrease the CPU requirements for track reconstruction as far as possible while the loss in physics performance should be kept to a minimum. The unmodified workflow, as shown in Figure 5, was then successively changed with the primary goal to minimise the event processing time. In this first assessment, slight degradation of physics performance was accepted in order to allow an aggressive estimation of achievable speed up factors. The performed modifications will be described in the following.

As a first step the Ambiguity Resolution, since it is the main contributor as seen in Table 1, will be

Figure 5: Track reconstruction workflow for the ITk geometry with all components involved.

disabled. Since this part performs due to historical reasons additional tasks, a precise track fit would be missing. Furthermore the b-tagging efficiency is assumed to be reduced due to the missing NN cluster splitting in jets. Some of the workload is thereby moved to the combinatorial track finding stage instead, in order to suppress the creation of ambiguities in the first place. In addition the combinatorial track finder performed in this workflow the task to estimate the final track parameters. Therefore the tracking cuts in the track finder were tightened as shown in Table 2. As the cuts become more strict a speed up effect is

Table 2: Applied tracking cuts in the track finder of the fast track reconstruction[7]. The default values are given in brackets. Here z_0 , the longitudinal impact parameter, is defined with respect to the mean position of the beam spot.

Requirement	Pseudorapidity interval		
	$ \eta < 2.0$	$2.0 < \eta < 2.6$	$2.6 < \eta < 4.0$
Pixel+Strip hits	≥ 9 (7)	≥ 8 (7)	≥ 7 (7)
unique hits	≥ 7 (1)	≥ 6 (1)	≥ 5 (1)
shared hits	≤ 2 (no cut)	≤ 2 (no cut)	≤ 2 (no cut)
p_T [MeV]	> 1000 (900)	> 400 (400)	> 400 (400)
$ z_0 $ [cm]	≤ 15 (20)	≤ 15 (20)	≤ 15 (20)

expected as well. Additionally an approximated material model and cluster correction was applied, while the full detailed cluster calibration remained unchanged for the fast track reconstruction chain.

The next modification considers the seeding. While during Run-2 approximately 20% of CPU time was spent in the seeding it is assumed to be increased up to 50% at HL-LHC pile-up. As the ITk will consist of five pixel layers and these cover the full range of $|\eta| < 4$, the pixel detector contributes the major amount of seeds, as shown in Figure 6. Therefore the goal of the study was to improve the purity of pixel seeds

Figure 6: Mean number of accepted seeds in the ITk pixel and strip detector versus $|\eta|$ [3].

while the seed finding in the strip detector is dropped entirely. The increased purity is thereby assumed to speed up the CPU times spent in road build and track finding, too. Additionally the recovery strategy for Bremsstrahlung[7] was also temporarily disabled in the track finding.

For the data pre-processing stage, code optimisations of the pixel detector and the strip clustering were performed. Since the strip space point formation is very CPU consuming and is only required for strip seeding, it was entirely removed from the workflow. The last aspect covers the RD53B front-end chip[8] of the ITk pixel detector. Its design allows to read out multiple pixels simultaneously in a tree-like way and therewith to read out pixel clusters. The underlying bit-coding achieves a significant data compression such that an event in the pixel detector is of comparable size to the strip detector. However there is no decoding software available yet. Therefore within this study the Run-2 raw data decoding was used and the event sizes scaled to ITk event sizes. For Monte Carlo events the decoding of simulated hits from ROOT[9] files was used.

3.1 Physics performance

In this section the physics performance achieved with the fast track reconstruction for particles with $p_T > 1$ GeV using the full range of the ITk is presented, starting with the reconstruction efficiency as shown in Figure 7. A slight degradation of the efficiency is observable for all pseudorapidity bins with more significant reductions in the ITk barrel-endcap transition region at $|\eta| \approx 1.5$ and at the very forward region. The dependency on the transverse momentum also shows a slight decrease in most bins with a more significant deviation in low- p_T regions. As the multiple scattering becomes a more dominant effect in low- p_T regions, this observation is an expected effect of the material model approximations. As a consequence of the

Figure 7: Track reconstruction efficiency for single μ with a p_T of 2 GeV (a) and 100 GeV (b) versus η . The dependency of the efficiency on p_T is shown for $t\bar{t}$ events with $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$ (c) [7].

reduced efficiencies, this results in a lower number of reconstructed tracks, see Figure 8(a). On the other hand the similar amount of reconstructed tracks indicates no significantly increased fake-rate. Moreover the reconstructed tracks have an almost identical amount of hits in the pixel and strip detector as shown in Figure 8(b) and (c) respectively.

The track parameter resolutions are shown in Figure 9 for single μ . Most of these distributions are in good agreement with the default reconstruction. Noteworthy is within this set the more significant loss of $\approx 20\%$ in the p_T resolution of 2 GeV single μ which is again an effect of the applied material model approximations. Furthermore a loss of $\approx 50\%$ in z_0 resolution is observed for 100 GeV single μ in the $|\eta|$ region around 2. This is a consequence of the applied cluster correction. The key message that can be derived from this set is that the sources are well understood and therefore can be improved in the future.

Since the initial motivation of the study was to reduce the CPU consumption, the achieved performance is shown in Figure 10. It is observable that an outstanding improvement was achieved. Compared to the default ITk track reconstruction a speed up of a factor 6-7 was achieved for 140 and 200 pile-up. Comparing the fast track reconstruction at $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$ to the Run-2 reconstruction at $\langle\mu\rangle = 60$ it becomes even around a factor 8 in speed up. Though this was still based on the Run-2 software without including any benefits of the

Figure 8: Mean number of reconstructed track (a), associated hits in the pixel (b) and strip detector (c) versus η [7].

Acts project[10]. However the therewith achieved performance promises a significant reduction in ATLAS computing requirements in the HL-LHC era covering the data processing and Monte Carlo reconstructions. Also heavy ion physics would benefit from these results, as high centrality heavy ion collisions impose a similar high multiplicity environment. A consequence of the reduction is then that the CPU resources spent in event generation and Geant4[11, 12] simulations will become the dominant part while tracking will be only a minor contributor.

4 Further R&D projects

The last section showed that the tracking can become sufficiently fast for HL-LHC conditions in the ATLAS experiment. It was also presented in Figure 7 and 9 that the achieved physics performance was reduced compared to the default reconstruction. In order to improve the physics performance, further R&D is required: one candidate here is the inclusion of software from the Acts project. This project is an open-source collection of tracking tools and algorithms from contributors of various collaborations. It provides a modular software design that provides easy accessible interfaces for R&D. It is crucial to improve all kinds of reconstruction (e.g. e/γ , μ , b -tagging,...) in the future.

Beyond this project there are further perspectives e.g. from machine learning. For that purpose the TrackML challenge[13], a public accessible track reconstruction competition, was held. Also efforts into adapting tracking to new hardware architectures like FPGAs or GPUs are items of investigation. All over many different ideas and inspirations are currently in the process of making in order to achieve the best possible performance for the HL-LHC conditions.

Figure 9: Resolution of d_0 , z_0 (the transverse and longitudinal impact parameters) and the relative p_T for single μ with 2 and 100 GeV versus η [7].

5 Conclusions

The expected pile-up provided by the HL-LHC will become a challenge for track reconstruction. In order to handle the increasing complexity, ATLAS will install the new tracking detector ITk which is designed for that purpose. For the track reconstruction software adaptations of the software used for Run-2 were performed which provided a significant improvement in CPU resource requirements but which is still above the expected available CPU resources. A fast track reconstruction was investigated for CPU requirement reduction by modifying and adapting the track reconstruction workflow. Thereby a speed up of a factor 8 between the ITk at $\langle\mu\rangle = 200$ and the Run-2 detector at $\langle\mu\rangle = 60$ was achieved. Since the study was focused on optimisation of the CPU performance a reduced physics performance was observed. In order to conserve a high physics performance standard in the context of fast track reconstruction the software project Acts will be involved in the future. This project provides by its structure an ideal ground for tracking R&D and is therefore expected

Figure 10: Reconstruction time for Run-2, default and fast ITk track reconstruction [7].

to become beneficial to all reconstructions. Beside the development in Acts, ATLAS is also actively investing into R&D to test new ideas and technologies concerning track reconstruction performance.

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Deep Sets for Flavor Tagging at the ATLAS Experiment

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ABSTRACT

Flavor tagging is a major client for tracking in particle physics experiments at high energy colliders, such as the ATLAS detector at the LHC, where it is used to identify the experimental signatures of heavy flavor production. Among other features, charm and beauty hadron decays produce jets containing several tracks with large impact parameters. This work introduces a new architecture for flavor tagging, based on Deep Sets, which models the jet as a set of tracks, not relying on any particular ordering or sequence. This approach is an evolution with respect to the Recurrent Neural Network currently adopted by the ATLAS experiment, which treats track collections as a sequence. The Deep Sets algorithm uses track impact parameters and kinematics within a permutation invariant architecture, leading to a significant decrease in training and evaluation time compared to the sequential recurrent algorithms. The Deep Sets algorithm is compared with current ATLAS flavor tagging benchmarks and methods are provided to explore and interpret the information learned by the network in the training process.

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1 Introduction

The process of identifying jets from b -quarks, called b -tagging, is crucial to the physics program of the ATLAS experiment [1] at the Large Hadron Collider. Since the b -hadron decays via the weak force, its characteristic “long” lifetime of ≈ 1.5 ps leads to an experimental signature of a displaced decay in the detector. ATLAS organizes the task of b -jet classification into two types of algorithms: *impact parameter (IP)-based* which takes as input the collection of tracks and looks for those that are displaced from the interaction point, and *vertex-based* which explicitly reconstructs either a single secondary vertex or the multiple displaced vertices of the cascade decay chain [2]. The final ATLAS b -tagger is a multi-layer perceptron trained on the outputs of these IP-based and vertex-based taggers [2].

ATLAS is a multipurpose detector comprising an inner tracking system surrounded by electromagnetic and hadronic calorimeters which are encased by muon spectrometers [1].* Tracks are reconstructed from hits in the inner tracker, and the identified primary vertex (PV) is the reconstructed vertex with the largest $\sum_i p_{T,i}^2$ of the associated tracks. Jets are formed by clustering particle flow objects [3] with the anti- k_T algorithm [4], and tracks are associated to jets using a p_T dependent ΔR association [2]. Algorithm training and evaluation is performed with simulated semi-leptonic $t\bar{t}$ events, produced in $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV proton-proton collisions. Events are generated using the PowhegBox [5–8] v2 generator interfaced to Pythia v8.230 [9] to model the parton shower, hadronization, and underlying event. The decays of b - and c -hadrons are performed by EvtGen v1.6.0 [10]. Particles are passed through the ATLAS detector simulation [11] based on GEANT4 [12]. More details can be found in [13].

This work presents the use of a permutation invariant Deep Sets architecture [14] and on the application of the Deep Sets formalism within particle physics known as Energy / Particle Flow Networks [17] to replace the currently deployed b -tagging Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). The training and inference speed-up of Deep Sets is characterized and further optimization improvements are shown. A linearized view of the network response is used to understand what the network has learned about the properties of b -jets, and we demonstrate the feasibility of including such a tagger in the current calibration workflow.

2 IP-based b -tagging Algorithms

2.1 Previous Work

For the lifetime-based taggers, a positive sign is assigned to the IP of tracks more consistent with being from a long-lived decay [2]. The distributions for the significances (or IP divided by the error) are shown in Figure 1 for tracks from b , c , and light quark or gluon (l) jets [13], with the jet labelling definition from [2].

Figure 1 shows that the jets with true displaced heavy flavor (HF) decays are more likely to have positive IPs, and this asymmetry is the key discriminating feature used by the IP3D algorithm which uses these histograms to define probability density functions (pdfs) for the track significances conditioned on the jet flavor. To aggregate information across the tracks in the jet, the track IPs are assumed to be independent to define a higher-level discriminant by multiplying the ratio of probabilities across the tracks in the jet: $D_{\text{IP3D},\{l,c\}} = \log \prod_{i \in \text{tracks}} p_b^{(i)} / p_{\{l,c\}}^{(i)}$. These pdfs for the tracks are defined for 14 exclusive categories depending on the hit patterns of the tracks to give a measure of the track quality in these discriminants [2].

Since this uncorrelated track assumption limits the expressivity of the IP3D algorithm, ATLAS also employs another lifetime-based tagger, RNNIP [15]. The recurrent architecture can operate on an arbitrary number of tracks in the jet since tracks are sequentially processed as the RNN continuously updates a fixed dimensional hidden state which is used to determine the probabilities for a jet to be classified as b , c , or l . For the RNNIP results included here, the tracks are ordered by decreasing s_{d0} . As neural networks (NNs) avoid the curse-of-dimensionality (sparsification of the entries as the number of dimensions grows) inherent

*ATLAS uses a right-handed coordinate system with its origin at the nominal interaction point in the centre of the detector and the z -axis along the beam pipe. The x -axis points from the interaction point to the centre of the LHC ring, and the y -axis points upwards. Cylindrical coordinates (r, ϕ) are used in the transverse plane, ϕ being the azimuthal angle around the z -axis. The pseudorapidity is defined in terms of the polar angle θ as $\eta = -\ln \tan(\theta/2)$. Angular distance is measured in units of $\Delta R \equiv \sqrt{(\Delta\eta)^2 + (\Delta\phi)^2}$.

Figure 1: Lifetime signed track significances in the (a) transverse and (b) longitudinal directions [13].

in histogram-based approaches, the low-level hit information is used instead of the IP3D categories, and variables sensitive to the kinematics of the decay are included. The full set and description of the currently adopted RNNIP inputs are shown in Table 1 [13].

Input	Description
s_{d0}	d_0/σ_{d0} : transverse IP significance
s_{z0}	$z_0 \sin \theta / \sigma_{z_0 \sin \theta}$: longitudinal IP significance
$\log p_T^{\text{frac}}$	$\log p_T^{\text{track}} / p_T^{\text{jet}}$: logarithm of fraction of the jet p_T carried by the track
$\log \Delta R$	Logarithm of opening angle between the track and the jet axis
IBL hits	Number of hits in the IBL: could be { 0, 1, or 2 }
PIX1 hits	Number of hits in the next-to-innermost pixel layer: could be { 0, 1, or 2 }
shared IBL hits	Number of shared hits in the IBL
split IBL hits	Number of split hits in the IBL
nPixHits	Combined number of hits in the pixel layers
shared pixel hits	Number of shared hits in the pixel layers
split pixel hits	Number of split hits in the pixel layers
nSCTHits	Combined number of hits in the SCT layers
shared SCT hits	Number of shared hits in the SCT layers

Table 1: Track feature inputs for RNNIP and DIPS (Deep Impact Parameter Sets) algorithms [13]. IBL (Insertable B-Layer) is the innermost pixel layer, and SCT (SemiConductor Tracker) are the strips layers.

The inclusion of RNNIP in the recommended ATLAS tagger has led to an increase in performance from the incorporation of the track correlations and the additional input features [16], but it's not clear whether using a sequence to model the jet is a necessary assumption for the performance gains. The ordering of the tracks for RNNIP was empirically determined rather than specified by the problem, and processing tracks sequentially is inherently a slow process.

2.2 Deep Sets Algorithm

For the reasons stated above, we were interested in looking at permutation invariant models for this task using a Deep Sets model. Adopting the notation of [17], the model can be expressed by

$$\mathcal{O}(\{p_1, \dots, p_n\}) = F\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \Phi(p_i)\right) \quad (1)$$

where for each track $p_i \in \mathbb{R}^m$ corresponding to the $m = 13$ features listed in Table 1, Φ is a NN that extracts per track features, the sum operation over the n tracks encodes the permutation invariance, and F is another NN which operates on the (permutation invariant) vector to account for the correlations between the tracks. The architecture used for these studies is illustrated in Figure 2, with an additional batch normalization layer [18] before applying the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) nonlinearity [19]. This architecture is based off the one in [17], although we additionally did experiments varying the number of layers and hidden units for the F and Φ networks. Most of the settings we considered yielded the same performance, and we show results with this architecture to keep the number of trainable parameters for the RNNIP and DIPS algorithms roughly the same. The implementation of the Deep Sets algorithm for b -tagging will be referred to as DIPS (Deep Impact Parameter Sets) in following sections.

Figure 2: Schematic for the implementation of the Deep Sets architecture [13], where the Φ network extracts 128 features for each of the tracks.

3 Results

The results here show retrainings for both the RNNIP and DIPS architectures with $t\bar{t}$ simulation as described in [13]. Of the 3 million jets in the training set, 20% are held out for a validation set for early stopping, and another independent test sample of 3 million jets is used for evaluating the models. For RNNIP, tracks are sorted by decreasing s_{d0} , and the baseline kinematic track selection considers the tracks with $p_T > 1$ GeV, $|d_0| < 1$ mm, and $|z_0 \sin \theta| < 1.5$ mm † , a tight selection adopted by both the IP3D and RNNIP algorithms. When quantifying the rejections and times, each model is trained five times and we report the averages across the trained models with errors given by the standard deviations.

3.1 Timing Studies

Since Deep Sets is not a sequential algorithm, the track feature extraction (with the Φ networks) can be parallelized, resulting in a speed-up of 3-4 as demonstrated by Table 2, with the DIPS hyperparameters chosen to roughly match the number of trainable parameters of RNNIP. Information from the NN's multi-class probabilities p_b , p_c , and p_l are aggregated into a single discriminant $D_b = \frac{p_b}{f_c p_c + (1-f_c) p_l}$, where f_c is a parameter chosen after the training is completed. For these studies we use $f_c = 0.07$, the c -quark fraction in $t\bar{t}$ events. The performance of these models is quantified through Receiver Operator Characteristic (ROC) curves, which are defined as the background rejection (1 / mistagging efficiency) versus b -jet identification efficiency, as shown in Figure 3. The speed improvement does not come at a loss in efficiency, and there is even a slight improvement in the model performance up to 20% for l -rejection and 5% for c -rejection.

† IPs are measured with respect to the reconstructed PV.

Model	# of parameters	GPU training time / epoch [s]	GPU eval time [s]	CPU eval time [s]
RNNIP	47k	241 ± 14	170 ± 2	685 ± 84
DIPS	49k	78 ± 4	46 ± 2	206 ± 98

Table 2: Timing metrics for trainings on Nvidia 2080 Ti GPUs, and GPU evaluations on an Nvidia Titan X GPU. The nominal value denotes the mean of five independent trainings (for sample-size of 3 million jets), while the error bar is the standard deviation [13].

Figure 3: Performance for RNNIP and DIPS models with the same inputs for (a) l -rejection versus b -efficiency and (b) c -rejection versus b -efficiency [13].

3.2 Performance Optimization

Figure 4 shows the results of two additional optimization studies [13]. Loosening the track selection to $p_T > 500 \text{ MeV}$, $|d_0| < 3.5 \text{ mm}$, $|z_0 \sin \theta| < 5 \text{ mm}$ increases both the l - and c -rejection performance by up to 40%. Adding in the IPs (d_0 and $z_0 \sin \theta$) for each track further improves the performance of the l -rejection by up to 200% with respect to the baseline DIPS. While the impact parameter significance carries combined information about both decay length and track quality, the impact parameters focus only on information about the track displacement regardless of the track reconstruction quality. Thus the two features carry information which is not totally correlated, thus giving the model additional handles to learn how track properties are distributed in the different jet flavors.

Physics analyses require a tagger that performs well across a broad kinematic range. As such, Figure 5 shows the l - and c -rejections with a 77% b -jet efficiency working point (WP) which is flat as a function of jet p_T and η . Figure 5 compares the RNNIP and DIPS models that use the baseline track selection to the Optimized DIPS model which includes the loosened track selection and IP inputs. The overall performance gains of Optimized DIPS persist across the kinematic regimes of interest.

4 Architecture Understanding

For the following studies we show results for DIPS with the baseline set of inputs and nominal track selection.

Figure 4: Light jet rejection (a) and c -jet rejection (b) versus b -jet efficiency for different track selections and input features [13].

Figure 5: Evolution of the background rejections with several algorithms, for a 77% efficiency b -tagging WP that is flat as a function of jet p_T shown for (a) l -rejection and (b) c -rejection, and flat as a function of jet η shown for (c) l -rejection and (d) c -rejection [13].

4.1 Saliency Maps

To investigate what the architecture has learned, we employ a method called saliency maps [20], originally used to understand what parts of an image convolutional neural networks focus on for classification. A saliency map represents a linearized version of the network response by considering the gradient of the discriminant with respect to the input features. For a single jet, $\nabla_{inputs} D_b \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, where n is the number of tracks in the jet and $m = 13$ is the number of features associated with each track. Information is aggregated across a sample of jets to observe trends, and thus a sample of b -jets that *failed* to be identified by the 77% efficiency working point was considered, as mistagged jets are in the regime where the gradients are still informative.[‡] Additionally, to ameliorate the dependence on track multiplicity, jets were required to have exactly $n = 8$ tracks, and in computing the average, the tracks defining the image were ordered by decreasing s_{d0} , as shown in Figure 6. The gradients in this image show how to modify this sample of jets to make them more b -like, illustrating what the model has learned about the characteristics of a b -jet. The significances are shown in the bottom rows, and demonstrate that the network wants at least five high IP tracks in the jet, consistent with the multiplicity expected from b -hadron decays. The leading tracks in s_{d0} are encouraged to be harder, consistent with expectations for the b -quark fragmentation function, and the leading track in s_{d0} is encouraged to have a larger opening angle due to the geometric constraints a highly displaced track has with respect to the jet axis. Finally, in the upper left hand portion of the image, the negative gradients for the tracks’ shared and split hits indicate that the high s_{d0} tracks in the jet need to be of good quality when relying on them for a b -tagging decision. These observations give a qualitative assessment that DIPS has learned sensible properties of b -jets.

Figure 6: Gradient of the discriminant D_b with respect to the jet inputs for b -jets with 8 tracks failing the 77% efficiency WP [13].

4.2 Flipped Taggers

In training the tagger and quantifying its performance, a simulation with known jet flavor labels is used, but when deploying a tagger in an analysis, *scale factors* (SFs) for each jet flavor are derived to correct for the efficiency modifications induced by the domain shift between simulation and data. As demonstrated in Figure 3, the $\mathcal{O}(1000)$ l -rejections mean that even if a calibration starts with a l -jet dominated sample, applying the tagger will reduce the l -jets to a level where the l -jet mistagging efficiency can no longer be directly extracted. For deriving the l -jet SFs, we calibrate a “flipped” definition of the tagger which

[‡]Considering instead b -jets above a specified threshold starts saturating some of the gradients.

has a similar discriminant distribution for l -jets but a much reduced performance for b -jets to avoid being overwhelmed by HF jets after the tagger application [21]. We do not plan to calibrate DIPS directly, but the b -tagger that gets trained on both DIPS and the other IP-based and vertex-based tagger outputs. But ensuring that DIPS has a flipped tagger definition with the desired properties can significantly aid the ability of the final b -tagger to flip successfully.

The key feature used for the DIPSFlip tagger is the symmetry of the track significances in l -jets, as shown in Figure 1 [13]. DIPSFlip takes the DIPS weights trained with our nominal sample, but at the evaluation time, modifies the inputs by multiplying the track significances by -1 . Thus, DIPSFlip tags become largely driven by tracks with large negative IP significances rather than large positive IP significances which dominate nominal DIPS tags. Figure 7 shows $1 -$ tagging probability for DIPS and DIPSFlip (in the solid and dashed lines, respectively) as the threshold on the b -tagging discriminant is varied. For the l -jets, the flipped and nominal tagger definitions are nearly overlapping, while the desired drop in efficiency for the heavy flavor jets is observed when using the flipped tagger definition, which is promising for using DIPS in defining a high-level flipped tagger.

Figure 7: Performance of the DIPS and DIPSFlip taggers. The dashed grey lines show the WPs that ATLAS uses for calibration [13].

5 Conclusions

In this work, we present a new lifetime-based b -tagger, DIPS, based on an architecture which is permutation invariant to the track reorderings. We show a 3-4 speed-up in training and inference with respect to RNNIP, and demonstrate input modifications which continue to boost the performance. These low-latency algorithms are promising not only to help reduce the computational overhead of the ATLAS reconstruction, but also for exploring the potential of implementing b -tagging in hardware triggers.

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The Track finder algorithm for the trigger system of the Mu2e experiment at Fermilab

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ABSTRACT

The Mu2e experiment at Fermilab will search for two charged-lepton flavor violating processes: $\mu^- \rightarrow e^-$ and $\mu^- \rightarrow e^+$ conversions in the field of an aluminum nucleus, improving by four orders of magnitude the search sensitivity reached so far. The signature of the Mu2e signals is represented by a ~ 105 MeV/c e^- and a ~ 92 MeV/c e^+ in the two channels respectively. The reconstruction and identification of the signal particle tracks in the Mu2e tracker is difficult due to the presence of spurious hits, low-energy Compton e^- and other lower momenta e^- generated in μ Decay-In-Orbit processes, $\mu^- N \rightarrow e^- N \bar{\nu}_e \nu_\mu$. The Mu2e trigger is based on the online track reconstruction, which exploits two pattern recognition algorithms followed by the fast track fit. Preliminary studies show that the online track reconstruction will deliver a trigger rate of a few hundreds Hz, which includes a rate of fake tracks below ~ 10 Hz. The trigger signal efficiency is expected to be larger than 96% w.r.t the offline reconstruction. A prototype of the TDAQ system has been built at Fermilab, and we report on its timing performance.

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1 Introduction

lepton flavor violation (LFV) has been observed in the neutral sector (neutrino oscillations), but not in the charged sector. In the Standard Model, the predicted rate of charged lepton flavor violating (CLFV) processes is below 10^{-50} s [1]. However, many theories beyond the SM predict CLFV processes with rates observable by currently constructed HEP experiments [1]. The Mu2e apparatus includes three superconducting solenoids as shown in Figure 1: (1) the production solenoid, where an 8 GeV proton pulsed-beam (period $\sim 1.7 \mu\text{s}$) hits a tungsten target, producing mostly pions; (2) the transport solenoid, which serves as decay “tunnel” for the pions, and makes also charge and momentum selection, creating a low-momentum μ^- beam; (3) the detector solenoid, which houses an aluminum Stopping Target, where the muons get stopped and form muonic atoms, and the detector system (in a 1T solenoidal magnetic field) optimized to detect electron and positron from the μ conversions. The entire detector solenoid and half of the transport solenoid are covered with a cosmic-ray veto system (CRV), made out of 4-layers of extruded scintillator bars. The detector consists

Figure 1: Mu2e experimental apparatus. The cosmic-ray veto system is not shown.

of a 3.2 m long straw tube tracker and a crystal calorimeter. Both the tracker and the calorimeter have cylindrical symmetry. The inner part of each detector has an opening which provides for the free passage of non-interacting beam and makes the detectors “blind” to low-momentum charged background particles produced in the stopping target. The tracker consists of 36 equally spaced tracking planes, made out of 6

Figure 2: Explosion of the Mu2e tracker.

rotated panels arranged over two faces. A panel represents the basic unit of the tracker; it consists of 2 two staggered layers of straw tubes and has 96 straws in total. A more detailed description of the detector can be found in references: [4, 5]. The coordinate system is right-handed. The Z-axis parallel to the detector solenoid axis and is positively oriented moving from the stopping target to the detector region, with the origin in the middle of the tracker. The Y-axis is normal to the plane where all the three solenoids lay, and is positively oriented in the opposite direction of the ground. Then the X-axis is defined by the vector product of the other two axis: $\vec{x} = \vec{y} \times \vec{z}$.

2 Trigger system architecture

Mu2e uses *artdaq*[9] and *art*[8] software as event filtering and processing frameworks respectively. The detector Read Out Controllers (ROC), from the tracker and calorimeter, stream out continuously the data, zero-suppressed, to the Data Transfer Controller units (DTC). The data of a given event is then grouped in a single server using a 10 GBytes switch. Then, the online reconstruction of the events starts and make a trigger decision. If an event gets triggered, we pull also the data from the CRV and we aggregate them in a single data stream. The trigger system needs to satisfy the following requirements:

1. provide efficiency better than 90% for the signals;
2. keep the trigger rate below a few kHz - equivalent to ~ 7 Pb/year;
3. achieve a processing time < 5 ms/event.

Our main physics triggers use the info of the reconstructed tracks to make the final decision. In the following sections, we describe the logic of the online track reconstruction as well as its expected performance.

3 Online track finder

The first stage of the track search is the hits preparation. The signals at both sides of the straw tubes are combined to reconstruct the hit time as well as the position along the wire. Then, we combine neighboring hits, within the same panel, to create a so-called “panel hit”. For a given real track, more than 90% of the panel hits group 2 straw hits. This step allows to improve the spatial resolution along the wire direction (by a factor $\sim \sqrt{2}$) and reduce the combinatorics in the next stages of the reconstruction. After that, we use a Multi-Variate-Analysis (MVA) algorithm to identify and flag as “background” the hits compatible with being produced by a low-momentum (a few MeV) Compton e^- . These flagged hits will be excluded from the pattern-recognition. After the hits preparation, we exploit two separate pattern-recognition methods: a

Figure 3: Graph of the online track reconstruction logic.

calorimeter-seeded (calo-seeded) and a tracker-seeded (trk-seeded) algorithm. Figure 3 shows a graph of the logic adopted.

3.1 Tracker-seeded pattern recognition

The pattern recognition proceeds in two steps: the hit time-clustering and the helix reconstruction. The time-clustering uses an MVA-based algorithm to identify peaks in the distribution of the hit time. To improve the accuracy of this procedure, the hit time is extrapolated to $z=0$ (the middle of the tracker), assuming: (i) a $\beta = v/c = 1$ and (ii) a track pitch angle equal to the average value expected for a conversion electron (CE). This also allows to factorize out the particle time of flight from the width of the peak we are looking for.

The helix reconstruction is divided into two main parts: (i) the circle reconstruction in the transverse plane (XY) and (ii) the line reconstruction in the ϕ -Z plane, where ϕ is the hit polar angle w.r.t. the helix axis, while z is the coordinate along the tracker central axis. The two steps are integrated into an iterative loop that performs a hit-clean up at each iteration to remove eventual outliers. The circle reconstruction starts by looping over all the possible triplets of hits (picked from different tracking faces); if a triplet covers a sufficient area, we evaluate the expected helix center (x_0, y_0) from the intersection of the two perpendicular

bisectors. When the loop is ended, the best estimate of (x_0, y_0) is extracted by taking the median of all the values collected. Once we have estimated the circle center, a loop is repeated over the hits to estimate the circle radius using again the median of all the single values.

Figure 4: Drawing of a signal helix in the tracker Y-Z longitudinal plane (left) and its projection in the ϕ -Z plane (right).

To perform the ϕ -Z reconstruction we need to resolve the 2π ambiguity of the hits. Figure 4 shows the origin of this problem; a typical signal track reconstructed in our chamber makes multiple loops, but given the presence of the hollow, only arches appear in the longitudinal plane Y-Z and in the plot ϕ vs Z, we see groups of hits for each loop. We need to add a factor $2\pi \cdot i$ to the ϕ of the hits belonging to the i -th loop, but to make this correction we need to know the particle angular velocity $d\phi/dz = 1/\lambda$. The first estimate of $d\phi/dz$ is obtained by making the histogram of $d\phi/dz_{i,j,k} = \frac{(\phi_j + 2\pi k) - \phi_i}{z_j - z_i}$, with $i, j \in (0, N-1)$ and $k \in (0, 10)$. The peak of the resulting distribution is used to assign each hit to the corresponding loop and thus resolve the 2π ambiguity. This allows us to create the histogram of $d\phi/dz_{i,j} = \frac{\phi_j - \phi_i}{z_j - z_i}$, whose peak is used as best estimate of the helix $d\phi/dz$. Figure 5 shows the distributions of the reconstructed momentum and

Figure 5: Distribution of the reconstructed momentum (left) and of the momentum resolution (right) for the tracker-seeded algorithm. Results were obtained processing a MC sample of CE overlaid with the expected background.

the expected momentum resolution. The distributions were obtained by processing a dataset of CE overlaid with the expected background sources. A Gaussian fit to the distribution of the momentum residuals shows that the expected resolution for a CE is $\sim 4\%$. The non-zero mean of the Gaussian fit is due to a bias introduced by the circle reconstruction.

3.2 Calorimeter-seeded pattern recognition

The calorimeter-seeded pattern recognition starts from grouping the hits in clusters before starting the helix search, but in this case, the calorimeter information (time and position) is driving the process. A calorimeter cluster with the reconstructed energy above 50 MeV identifies a group of hits in the tracker with: (i) a time gate of ± 40 ns around the calorimeter cluster time and (ii) a geometrical selection that includes only the hits laying in the same semi-plane identified by the calorimeter cluster in the XY transverse plane. Figure 6 illustrates how the calo-selection works on a typical event with a CE overlaid with the expected background.

Figure 6: Event display in the XY transverse plane of a typical CE event w/o any selection (left) and after applying the calorimeter selection (right). The black crosses represent the straw hits, the red circle the calorimeter cluster and the green circle the trajectory of the CE.

In this case, the helix reconstruction implements a 3D search. It starts by selecting a triplet with: the calorimeter cluster position, one hit (starting from the one closer to the Stopping Target) and the solenoid center (in the XY plane). A helix defined by these three points determines the initial search-road. Then we loop over all the hits and we pick only one hit per tracking face if it falls within the search road. As soon as the second hit is found, the solenoid center is dropped, and the helix parameters are updated and the procedure re-starts. The algorithm adjusts the helix parameters as the search progresses and new hits are added to the helix candidate. The helix parameters are updated using two different reduced- χ^2 fits: in the XY and the ϕ -Z planes. Each hit is weighted by using the inverse of the square of the expected uncertainty. The hit error is evaluated by projecting its uncertainties (along the wire and radial directions) on the \vec{r}_{helix} and $\vec{\phi}_{helix}$ directions for the XY and ϕ -Z fits respectively. This step is rather important as it allows to take into account the geometrical orientation of the straw tubes w.r.t. to the helix. Figure 7 shows the distributions of the reconstructed momentum and the momentum resolution. The distributions were obtained by processing a dataset of CE overlaid with the expected background sources. A Gaussian fit to the distribution of the momentum residuals shows that the resolution for a CE is $\sim 3\%$. We notice that in this case the mean of the Gaussian fit is at the level of ~ 0.5 MeV/c, which is a factor ~ 10 smaller than the previous case. Additional details can be found on this reference[6].

3.3 Track reconstruction

After a helix corresponding to a track candidate is found, a simplified Kalman fit is performed to improve the accuracy in the reconstructed track parameters and thus - the background rejection. This fit doesn't resolve the left-right ambiguity of the hits, nor applies any correction to take into account the energy loss by the particle along the trajectory. Figure 8 shows the distributions of the reconstructed momentum and the momentum resolution. The Gaussian fit to the distribution of the momentum residuals shows that the

Figure 7: Distribution of the reconstructed momentum (left) and of the momentum resolution (right) for the calorimeter-seeded algorithm. Results were obtained processing a MC sample of CE overlaid with the expected background.

resolution is about 1.4 MeV/c for the CE, which is about two times better than the momentum resolution after the pattern recognition.

Figure 8: Distribution of the reconstructed momentum (left) and of the momentum resolution (right) for the track reconstruction. Results were obtained processing a MC sample of CE overlaid with the expected background.

4 Expected track-trigger performance

The Mu2e Track trigger is implemented by applying a series of software filters after each step of the track reconstruction. These filters are set up with different settings and the *artdaq*[9] architecture allows to apply

all of them w/o running the reconstruction modules multiple times in the same event. This is especially important for minimizing the running time of the online processing. The expected performance of the track triggers was estimated w.r.t. the offline track reconstruction. In the case of the CE, the resulting efficiency is $\sim 98\%$ for the OR of the two algorithms, while it's $\sim 87\%$ or $\sim 90\%$ if we consider only the calorimeter-seeded or the tracker-seeded algorithm respectively. In the case of the Conversion Positron, the resulting efficiency is $\sim 96\%$ for the OR of the two algorithms, while it's $\sim 76\%$ or $\sim 90\%$ if we consider only the calo-seeded or the tracker-seeded respectively. A lower efficiency of the calorimeter-seeded algorithm for positrons is due to the inefficiency of the online calorimeter clustering algorithm. Figure 9 shows on the left the table with the breakdown of the expected track-trigger rates, while on the right the distribution of the rejection as a function of the proton bunch intensity (PBI). The total instantaneous trigger rate is expected to be ~ 700 Hz; we note that this number is dominated by low-momentum e^- from the Stopping Target and that it can be reduced considerably (either with a pre-scaler or by increasing the momentum threshold) w/o affecting the expected signal trigger efficiency. The same figure shows that the expected total rejection ranges from 2,000 to 5000 when $PBI_{test} / \langle PBI \rangle \in [1, 2]$.

Figure 9: Table with the breakdown of expected track-trigger rates (left) and distribution of expected trigger rejection as a function of the $PBI_{test} / \langle PBI \rangle$. In the legend, “Tpr” and “Cpr” refers respectively to the tracker-seeded and the calo-seeded algorithms, while “DeM” and “DeP” to downstream electron (Conversion Electron case) and downstream positron (Conversion Positron case).

We performed preliminary tests using the TDAQ test-stand that has been set up at Fermilab. A web-based GUI, powered by the “off-the-shelves” software[7], was used to conduct all the tests. Figure 10 shows the results of the preliminary timing tests that were performed. These results show that the requirement in the total-processing-time is matched only in the case where one event-builder/DAQ-server is run, while in case of 20 event-builders the time goes up to ~ 6.5 ms. We are still in the development stage and several possible solutions to mitigate this issue are being explored.

5 Conclusions

We presented the track trigger system of the Mu2e experiment at Fermilab. The software trigger runs two online pattern recognition algorithms: a tracker-seeded and a calorimeter-seeded algorithm. The expected momentum resolution of both helix search methods is in the range $[3, 4]\%$ for CE, which is improved by a factor ~ 2 by the fast Kalman fit. The resulting trigger efficiency for both CLFV signals Mu2e will be searching is above 96% w.r.t. to the offline reconstruction, while the expected background rejection is $\sim 2,000$ at nominal beam condition. The instantaneous track trigger rate is expected to be ~ 700 Hz. This number is dominated by the electrons from the in-orbit decays of captured muons, which can be reduced considerably w/o affecting the trigger efficiency for the signal processes. The preliminary timing tests that we performed with the TDAQ prototype at Fermilab are encouraging, but they also show that improvements are needed to match the requirement of 5 ms/event.

Figure 10: Distribution of the time/event spent by each of the reconstruction module used in the online track reconstruction (left) and of the total reconstruction time/event as a function of the number of event-builder run over the same DAQ server. The box labeled with “TrkPatRec” identifies the modules specific to the tracker-seeded algorithm, while the one labeled with “CalPatRec” the modules referring to the calo-seeded algorithm.

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Overview of online and offline reconstruction in ALICE for LHC Run 3

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ABSTRACT

In LHC Run 3, ALICE will increase the data taking rate significantly to 50 kHz continuous readout of minimum bias Pb–Pb collisions. The reconstruction strategy of the online-offline computing upgrade foresees a first synchronous online reconstruction stage during data taking enabling detector calibration, and a posterior calibrated asynchronous reconstruction stage. The main challenges include processing and compression of 50 times more events per second than in Run 2, identification of removable TPC tracks and hits not used for physics, tracking of TPC data in continuous readout, the TPC space-charge distortion calibrations, and in general running more reconstruction steps online compared to Run 2. ALICE will leverage GPUs to facilitate the synchronous processing with the available resources. For the best GPU resource utilization, we plan to offload also several steps of the asynchronous reconstruction to the GPU. In order to be vendor independent, we support CUDA, OpenCL, and HIP, and we maintain a common C++ source code that also runs on the CPU. We will give an overview of the global reconstruction and tracking strategy, a comparison of the performance on CPU and different GPU models. We will discuss the scaling of the reconstruction with the input data size, as well as estimates of the required resources in terms of memory and processing power.

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1 Introduction

ALICE (A Large Ion Collider Experiment) [1] is one of the four major experiments at the LHC (Large Hadron Collider) at CERN. It is a dedicated heavy-ion experiment studying lead collisions at the LHC at unprecedented energies. After the second long LHC shutdown from 2019 to 2021, the LHC upgrade will provide a higher Pb–Pb collision rate, and ALICE will have updated many of its detectors and systems [2]. In particular, the main tracking detectors TPC (Time Projection Chamber) and ITS (Inner Tracking System) will be upgraded [3]. The trigger driven readout of Run 1 and Run 2 of up to 1 kHz of Pb–Pb events is replaced by a continuous readout of all Pb–Pb events at 50 kHz. The continuous readout of pp collisions will happen at collision rates between 200 kHz and 1 MHz. ALICE is abandoning the hardware triggers and will switch to a full online processing in software. Also the computing scheme changes with the O² online-offline computing upgrade [4]. During data taking, the synchronous processing will serve two main objectives: detector calibration and data compression. With a flat budget and the yearly increases of storage capacity, recording and storing raw data as today is prohibitively expensive at 50 times the data rate. ALICE aims at a compression of the TPC data, the largest contributor to raw data size, of a factor 20 compared to the zero-suppressed raw data size of Run 2. By producing the calibration during data taking, ALICE will reduce the number of offline reconstruction passes over the data, where the first two passes serve the calibration today. The output of the synchronous data processing will be Compressed Time Frames (CTF). The CTFs together with the calibration data will be stored to an on-site disk buffer, and from there replicated to tapes. When the O2 computing farm is not fully used for the synchronous processing, e.g. in periods without beam or during pp data taking, it will perform a part of the asynchronous reconstruction, which reprocesses the data and generates the final reconstruction output. The part of asynchronous processing that exceeds the capacity of the farm will be done in the Grid. This asynchronous stage will employ the same algorithms and software as the synchronous stage, but with different settings, additional reconstruction steps, and final calibration.

2 ALICE detector upgrades and implications for reconstruction

Many detectors of ALICE are upgraded or replaced to operate at higher rates or with higher resolution. The important changes with respect to track reconstruction are in particular the new Inner Tracking System (ITS) and the upgraded Time Projection Chamber (TPC). The former ITS consisting of 2 layers of silicon pixels, 2 layers of silicon strips, and 2 layers of silicon drift detectors is replaced by 7 layers of silicon pixels improving the tracking close to the interaction region. A new tracking algorithm based on the Cellular Automaton was developed for the new ITS that can optionally use GPUs [5]. For the TPC, the entire readout system is replaced. During Run 1 and Run 2, the TPC was equipped with Multi Wire Proportional Chambers (MWPC) for the amplification and a gating grid to suppress the ion back flow. The gating grid could operate at a maximum rate of around 3 kHz, which is incompatible to the continuous readout at 50 kHz. Therefore, the MWPCs are replaced by Gas Electron Multipliers (GEM), which offer an intrinsic ion back flow blocking. This allows for the removal of the gating grid and enables continuous readout.

Still, the ion back flow is significantly larger as during Run 2. In particular, the majority of the ions are produced during the amplification, which means the ion density and the space-charge in the TPC scales linearly with the track occupancy and with the gain. Therefore, the increase of the Pb–Pb interaction from 10 to 50 kHz adds another factor of 5 to the space-charge. The electric field produced by the space-charge distorts the electrons during the drift leading in the worst case to a distortion of up to 20 cm for electrons created close to the central electrode at the inner radius of the TPC. These distortions must be corrected down to the intrinsic TPC resolution that is in the order of 100 μm . This will require a new calibration procedure and has implications for the track reconstruction.

Also the change from trigger driven readout to continuous readout has implications for the track reconstruction. For the triggered events, the absolute z coordinate of TPC hits can be computed from the drift velocity, the time the hit was measured in the TPC, and the time of the triggered vertex. The chicken and egg problem of the continuous readout is that the time of the vertex of a track is not known in advance but only after the hit is attached to a track and the track is attached to a vertex. But without the vertex time

the TPC hits cannot be converted from native pad, row, and time coordinates into x , y , and z coordinates ahead of time.

The third important change is the switch from processing individual events to processing time frames containing 10 to 20 ms of continuous data. In order to avoid complicating the reconstruction algorithms, all time frames are reconstructed independently. TPC collisions happening at the end of a time frame have parts of their tracks in drift detectors like the TPC detected in the following time frame. By construction, such tracks cannot be reconstructed. This renders the last 90 μs (maximum drift time in the TPC) of a time frame unreconstructible. A minimum time frame length of 10 ms is chosen such that the corresponding loss of statistics is below 1%.

ALICE will neither employ hardware nor software triggers but store all data in compressed form. This compression must happen in real time and process and store 50 times more collisions than during Run 2.

In summary, The new detectors and the new readout scheme yield many challenges for data processing. The most important ones are:

- Data must be strongly compressed in order to store 50 times as many compressed events as before.
- A calibration procedure for the space-charge distortions is required.
- Tracking in the TPC must work without absolute z coordinates of TPC hits in continuous readout.
- Online processing speed must improve to process 50 times more data than before.

3 Data processing in Run 3

The first stage of online processing happens in the First Level Processors (FLP), a farm of around 200 compute nodes receiving the optical links from the detectors. The FLP performs mostly simple, local compression steps on the single link level. In addition, calibration and quality assurance tasks that require all data coming in from the same link must run here, since afterwards the data will be distributed among the compute nodes. The FLP nodes are equipped with up to 3 FPGA boards, which provide the optical transceivers and have the possibility to run a user logic for data processing. In the TPC case, for example, the FPGA performs the common mode correction and the zero suppression. Overall, the FLP farm reduces the data rate of 3.5 TB/s coming from the detectors down to 635 GB/s.

The next stage is a farm of 250 to 500 Event Processing Nodes (EPN) housing in total around 2000 GPUs. The number of nodes will be decided when the final hardware is selected, which will define how many GPUs and how many processor cores are in one server. The EPN performs the bulk of the synchronous processing. Its data compression further reduces the incoming data rate from 635 GB/s to around 100 GB/s of CTFs. The CTFs are written to an on-site disk buffer and replicated to tape and to tier 0 and tier 1 data centers from there.

While there is no beam in the LHC, or when the EPN farm is only partially used for pp data taking, the EPNs will contribute to the asynchronous reconstruction, reading the CTFs from the disk buffer and creating the final reconstruction output. The EPN contribution will be around one third of the total asynchronous reconstruction workload while the rest will be performed by the tier 0 and tier 1 data centers.

4 TPC data compression

The TPC is by far the largest contributor to the raw data rate among the detectors, with 3.4 TB/s. Therefore, compression of the TPC data is most important and several elaborate compression steps are employed. The projected compressed TPC data rate is 80 GB/s. On the 10 GB/s level, other detectors contribute as well, so compression is applied but not as extensively as for the TPC.

The TPC compression runs in several steps:

1. The raw data are clusterized and only the obtained hits are stored, which allows for a better entropy compression later on.

2. All hit properties are stored in tailored custom fixed or floating point data formats using only exactly as many bits as needed to maintain the intrinsic TPC resolution.
3. Hits of tracks not used for physics are removed. This includes tracks of very low momentum below 50 MeV/c, secondary legs of looping tracks, track segments with high inclination angle that cannot be used in the track fit, and fake hits from noisy pads as well as charge clouds created by low momentum protons. Two strategies exist for the hit removal:
 - (a) Strategy A foresees positive identification of all hits that can safely be removed. In addition, the online tracking identifies the good tracks used for physics and protects all hits in their vicinity from removal.
 - (b) Strategy B runs only the online tracking and removes all hits not in the vicinity of good tracks. By design, this includes all hits removed by strategy A. Therefore, strategy B yields the higher data reduction factor, and the shorter processing time. But the caveat is that tracks not found during the online tracking are inevitably lost.

Strategy A is the baseline solution, but both strategies are implemented and can be switched easily later after a careful evaluation.

4. The entropy of the hit properties is reduced.
 - Hits attached to tracks are stored as residuals to the extrapolated track position, which have a smaller entropy than absolute hit positions.
 - Hits not attached to tracks are sorted by geometrical coordinates and the difference to the previous hit is stored.
 - Related hit properties, like cluster width, in different dimensions are treated together.
5. The final step is entropy encoding. While Huffman compression was used during Run 2, ANS (Asymmetric Numeral Systems) [6] encoding will be used in Run 3 to yield a higher compression.

By design, the TPC compression will require full online tracking. See [7] for more details.

5 TPC calibration

While there are many calibrations tasks, we focus on the TPC space-charge distortion (SCD) calibration, which is the most significant change compared to Run 2 and also the computationally most demanding task. The SCD calibration will employ two methods described in the following sub-sections:

5.1 Track based calibration

This method was developed and employed during Run 2 to correct for the space-charge distortions, although with a much smaller magnitude than expected in Run 3. In the track based calibration, TPC tracks are reconstructed uncalibrated with relaxed constraints and the tracks are matched to the inner detector (ITS) and the outer Transition Radiation Detector (TRD) and Time Of Flight (TOF) detector. Although originally designed primarily for particle identification, these detectors contribute significant tracking information necessary for the TPC calibration. This procedure is possible since the distortions are smooth, such that the track seeding still works. After the matching, the global track is refitted using only the information from the inner and outer detectors ignoring the attached TPC hits. Afterwards, the residuals of the TPC hits with respect to the refitted track give a map of the distortions in the TPC. The TPC volume is split in voxels, and inside each voxel the obtained distortions are inverted to obtain the correction map. Postprocessing steps such as smoothing are applied to correct for holes in the acceptance of TRD and TOF and other effects.

The advantage of this method is that it automatically applies a couple of other calibration, e.g. drift velocity or misalignment. However, a relatively large amount of tracks is needed to obtain the correction at the required precision, in particular since isolated tracks of peripheral collisions work best. Due to the larger data sample, the Run 2 calibration intervals of 40 minutes will be shortened to about 1 minute in Run 3, but this is still insufficient to correct for short term fluctuations in the distortions.

One cause of changes in the distortion magnitude are changes in the LHC luminosity leading to changes in the TPC occupancy and thus in the space-charge. This is compensated by scaling the correction map with the LHC luminosity.

But there are other causes of short term fluctuations like the LHC bunch structure and the Poissonian fluctuations of the number of collisions in a given time interval and collision centrality variations, which cannot be taken into account with the track based model. The corrections for these effects must be on a much shorter time scale of around 5 ms. These effects also existed during Run 2 but their order of magnitude was below the intrinsic TPC resolution. This changes in Run 3 and the track based model alone will be insufficient for the SCD calibration.

5.2 Integrated digital currents

Another method is the integration of the currents arriving at the TPC pads by just accumulating the ADC values received on a channel. From this one can compute the number of ions produced in the GEM amplification, the position of the ions in the TPC over time, the resulting space-charge, and the final distortions on the electrons. These numerical computations are quite compute-intensive and we aim at using a neural network to approximate the transformation from the currents to the correction map. Compared to the track based calibration the only input is the number of ions, so this method cannot correct for any other effect but the SCD by design. However, the integrated currents are available at a fine granularity such that short term corrections can be corrected for.

Naturally, this method requires the full ion history for a full ion drift time which is much longer than the electron drift time. Therefore, it was impossible to apply this with the trigger driven readout in Run 2 and unfortunately the non-continuous Run 2 raw data cannot be used to evaluate this method.

5.3 Combined method

The full correction of the distortions requires the combination of both methods. The track based calibration will correct for the average distortions. The current based method will correct for the distortion fluctuations. For this reason, the current based method is not applied on the currents themselves, but on the difference of the current and the average current. In this way, we obtain the difference for the fluctuation correction which we add on the average correction obtained from the track based method.

The track based method will require online TPC, ITS, TRD, and TOF tracking in the EPN farm, but only for around 1% of the total tracks selected from peripheral collisions. The hit to track residuals will be extracted online, and a postprocessing step between the synchronous and the asynchronous reconstruction phases will produce the final correction maps. The current based method will aggregate the currents already in the FPGA in the FLP farm.

6 Track reconstruction with continuous data

The processing of continuous data in the presence of space-charge distortions poses significant complications for the TPC tracking. Position-dependent corrections like for SCD cannot be applied ahead of time for TPC hits. The same holds for other effects like inhomogeneities in the magnetic field or the hit error parameterization. Therefore, the TPC tracking runs first standalone without such corrections. Since the effects are smooth, the track finding is not heavily affected. Track seeds are extrapolated to the beam line and the most likely z coordinate is computed under the assumption that the track is a primary and the vertex is at the origin. The track is refit with the corresponding corrections and then matched to ITS tracks, which are reconstructed standalone in the ITS. This matching fixes the time of the TPC track and enables the propagation into the outer detectors. The tracking algorithm has been derived from the Run 2 High Level Trigger (HLT) [8] and modified to suit the needs of Run 3. For more details see [9]

7 Reconstruction chain and performance

Summarizing the processing requirements, the synchronous reconstruction performs the calibration and the data compression. The TPC data compression requires full TPC tracking, both for the rejection of hits and for the track model compression. Other detectors perform only the ANS entropy compression and optionally

clusterization. The calibration requires tracking for the other detectors as well, but only for a small fraction of events in the order of 1%. Therefore, the dominant part of synchronous processing is the TPC tracking. ALICE will employ GPUs to speed up the TPC processing as it did during Run 1 and Run 2 in the HLT [8]. The TPC processing time on the GPU defines the number of GPUs required in the EPN farm, and thus the size of the farm itself.

While TPC tracking is also a significant fraction of the asynchronous reconstruction, it is not so dominant. First, the synchronous reconstruction already removed a significant fraction of the hits, which in turn speeds up the asynchronous reconstruction. Second, several tracking steps like the following of looping tracks are not needed in the asynchronous reconstruction. And last, all other detectors have to process all events in the asynchronous reconstruction compared to $O(1\%)$ in the synchronous. This makes for instance ITS tracking also computationally intensive. Without using the GPUs in additional steps of the asynchronous reconstruction, they would be idling most of time, considering that synchronous data taking of Pb–Pb events happens only during a few weeks in a year. ALICE is therefore aiming to use the GPUs also in many places during the asynchronous reconstruction, and a promising case is the full tracking chain of the central barrel region.

Figure 1: Overview of the compute-intensive reconstruction steps of the global barrel tracking chain and their state of GPU usage.

Figure 1 gives an overview of all barrel tracking steps that are promising candidates for the GPU in the long run. The baseline scenario is what is needed during the synchronous reconstruction to keep up with 50 kHz Pb–Pb data, and the required processing steps have been almost fully implemented on the GPU. Some consolidation and testing will be needed. Afterwards the focus will shift on the optimistic scenario to eventually port many if not all of these steps onto the GPU for the asynchronous reconstruction.

7.1 Processing large time frames

Several HEP experiments recording mostly pp events are struggling to utilize GPUs to the full extent since single collisions do not exhibit sufficient parallelism. General approaches are to combine many events into chunks and process them on the GPU in one go. While a heavy ion collision could fully load a GPU at the time of LHC Run 1, this is no longer the case today for modern GPUs with many more compute units. However, the time frames recorded by ALICE in Run 3 contain hundreds of such collisions, which will be sufficient parallelism also for future GPUs. Instead, the memory becomes the limitation since the full time frame and all temporary memory for its processing must fit inside the GPU. Therefore, memory usage is being optimized as much as possible. Processing of triggered events can happen on the GPU independently, which enables the reuse of GPU memory used for one collision as soon as it is finished. In the ALICE case, the full time frame with hundreds of collisions is processed at once and must not be split. Therefore, the memory is not reused for independent collisions but for consecutive reconstruction steps. More details are given in [10]. Overall, this poses a limit on the time frame size, and ALICE is currently working with a

compromise of 10 ms as the default length. This should eventually require around 16 GB of GPU memory and the unreconstructible ends of time frames will correspond to less than 1% of the total data.

Figure 2: Estimated processing time for one full time frame of 256 LHC orbits (~ 20 ms). The time is extrapolated linearly in the number of hits from the measurements of the processing time of shorter time frames. Times are measured on CPU (a) and GPU (b).

It is important to understand how the processing time is affected by the length of the time frame, in particular since the memory optimization is still ongoing and we still cannot process a full time frame on the GPUs we have. If, for instance, the processing time would grow more than linearly with the input data size, it would be imperative from the computing perspective to use shorter time frames or to optimize the algorithm. Figure 2 shows the extrapolated time (linearly in the number of TPC hits) for processing a full time frame based on the processing time of shorter time frames. The y axis shows the extrapolated processing time, the x axis shows the number of clusters. The distribution is pretty much flat for the CPU (Fig. 2 (a)), with only a slight speed-up for the smallest measurement on the left due to cache effects. In case of the GPU (Fig. 2 (b)), the smaller time frames take relatively longer for processing because the parallelism is limited, but starting from 8 million hits in the TPC, the processing time per hit remains more or less constant.

7.2 Comparison of GPUs and CPUs

Table 1 gives an overview of the processing times of several reconstruction steps on different GPU models and on an Intel CPU using a single core. For reference, we have measured the multi-core scalability of the CPU processing many independent events in parallel. Using 64 threads on an AMD Rome 64 core CPUs, we achieved a speed-up of around 54x of the overall processing time on the CPU. Using the SMT feature and all 128 threads, we see a speedup of around 70x.

Table 2 shows the relative processing time on several GPU models. Several particularities should be noted. Some steps (in Table 1 the dE/dx and the Track Fit) make extensive use of sort algorithms. We observed a severe performance degradation in these sorting steps on the GTX 1080 GPU, which we didn't investigate further since this GPU is end of life and not a candidate for our farm. Therefore, we excluded these kernels from the measurement of the GTX 1080. Table 1 shows that the cluster finding is extremely slow on the processor because the algorithm was developed for GPUs in a way that is very sub optimal for the CPU. The clusterization happens only during the synchronous processing which will anyway happen on the GPU, therefore its CPU performance is mostly irrelevant. For a fair comparison, we thus exclude the clusterization from the relative CPU performance value. Overall, an NVIDIA RTX 2080 Ti can replace around 56 CPU cores. This is in agreement with previous measurements, e.g. in [8] we reported that a GTX 1080 can replace around 40 CPU cores at the end of Run 2. Considering that the number of CPU cores

Processing step	AMD Radeon 7	RTX 2080 Ti	Intel CPU	2080 Ti / CPU
Zero Suppression Decoding	38 ms	19 ms	986 ms	52x
Cluster Finding	87 ms	79 ms	21343 ms	270x
Track Finding	109 ms	65 ms	8759 ms	135x
Track Fit	284 ms	243 ms	7204 ms	30x
Cluster Compression	137 ms	105 ms	1452 ms	14x
Synchronous Processing Total	657 ms	511 ms	39816 ms	78x
dE/dx Calculation	61 ms	22 ms	906 ms	41x
Asynchronous Processing Total	304 ms	237 ms	13381 ns	56x

Table 1: Processing time of reconstruction steps on GPU and CPU. The CPU was measured on an Intel CPU clocked at 4.5 GHz with the Skylake architecture (clock fixed, turbo disabled) on a single core.

GPU Model	Performance (relative)	Memory
NVIDIA RTX 2080 Ti	100.0%	11 GB
NVIDIA Quadro RTX 6000 (active cooling)	105.8%	24 GB
NVIDIA Quadro RTX 6000 (passive cooling)	94.5%	24 GB
NVIDIA RTX 2080	83.5%	8 GB
NVIDIA GTX 1080	60.1%	8 GB
NVIDIA V100	88.5%	32 GB
NVIDIA T4	59.3%	16 GB
AMD Radeon 7	77.8%	16 GB
AMD MI50	74.1%	16 GB
Intel Skylake 4.5 GHz (1 core)	1.77%	-

Table 2: Relative performance in the synchronous processing stage normalized to the performance of an NVIDIA RTX 2080 Ti. In case of the NVIDIA GTX 1080, all kernels that use thrust sort were excluded from the comparison, due to a severe performance degradation with that architecture. In the case of the Intel CPU, only the steps used in the asynchronous phase are compared, since the cluster finding of the synchronous phase is implemented in a way that is very slow on the CPU and thus not suited for the comparison.

is increasing and we are comparing to a single core, the ratio of GPU to CPU performance (comparing all shaders of a GPU to all cores of a CPU) didn't change much with respect to our previous measurements [8]. In particular, the new GPUs have more compute units as well.

The most promising GPU candidates for the EPN farm are the AMD Radeon 7, AMD MI 50, NVIDIA RTX 2080 Ti, and NVIDIA Quadro RTX 6000. With all GPUs, it is possible to build the EPN farm using around 2000 cards, in the NVIDIA case with even less. The final decision will be taken based on the costs of the overall farm. We did not observe large performance differences between the consumer grade GPUs (RTX 2080 Ti, Radeon 7) and the professional GPU (Quadro RTX, MI50). An important difference for us is the possibility for passive cooling in the server and continuous support. The NVIDIA RTX 2080 Ti with only 11 GB of memory would obviously require an additional shortening of the time frame below 10 ms, in case of the two AMD GPUs it is yet not fully clear whether the 16 GB will be sufficient for a 10 ms time frame, while the Quadro RTX 6000 will certainly be able to process the full 10 ms time frame.

8 Conclusions

For LHC Run 3, ALICE will switch to continuous readout of 50 kHz minimum bias Pb–Pb events without trigger. ALICE will collect 50 times as many events as before. Full online processing will happen in

software mostly on GPUs. During data taking, the synchronous processing will perform data compression and calibration. Computationally, the dominant part is the TPC tracking which will run on the GPUs. When there is no beam, the asynchronous processing will produce the final reconstruction output, and we aim to have as many processing steps as possible on the GPU. The most demanding processing tasks will be the TPC compression, the space-charge distortion calibration, and the tracking. TPC compression will be based on the Run 2 strategy, and in addition we will employ track model compression, remove hits not used for physics, and switch from Huffman to ANS encoding. The TPC SCD calibration will combine two methods: the track based method will calibrate for the average distortions and the current based method will correct for the fluctuations that come on top. The TPC tracking is derived from the Run 2 HLT tracking and was improved to achieve the same resolution as the Run 2 offline tracking and adapted to process continuous data. There are promising GPU candidates from both AMD and NVIDIA, which will enable ALICE to do full online processing with less than 2000 GPUs.

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A muon tracking algorithm for Level 1 trigger in the CMS barrel muon chambers during HL-LHC

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ABSTRACT

The electronics of the Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) Drift Tube (DT) chambers will need to be replaced for the High Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) operation due to the increase of occupancy and trigger rates in the detector, which cannot be sustained by the present system. New electronics are being designed that will forward asynchronously the totality of the chamber signals to the counting room, at full resolution. The new back-end system will be in charge of building the trigger primitives of each chamber out of this asynchronous information, aiming at achieving resolutions comparable to the ones of the offline reconstruction. The new improved functionality will help to improve the resilience to potential ageing situations. An algorithm for the trigger primitive generation that will run in this new back-end system has been developed and implemented in firmware. The performance of this algorithm has been validated through different methods: from a software emulation approach to hardware implementation tests. The performance obtained is very good, with optimal timing and position resolutions, close to the ultimate performance of the DT chambers. One important validation step was including the implementation of this algorithm in a prototype chain of the HL-LHC electronics, which has been operated with real DT chambers during cosmic data taking. The new trigger primitive generation has been implemented in the so-called AB7, spare uTCA boards from the present DT system which host Xilinx Virtex 7 FPGAs. The performance of this prototyping system has been verified and will be presented in this contribution, showing the feasibility of the design for the expected functionality during HL-LHC.

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1 Introduction

CMS is one of the two general purpose detectors at the LHC. It has been designed with a two-level trigger system: the Level 1 trigger (L1), implemented in custom-designed electronics, and the High Level Trigger (HLT), a streamlined version of the CMS offline reconstruction software running on a computer farm. Muon trigger and reconstruction are provided by the DT chambers in the barrel and the cathode strip chambers (CSC) in the endcap, both complemented by a system of resistive plate chambers (RPC). A more detailed description of the CMS detector can be found in [1].

The basic element of the CMS drift tube detector is the drift cell, described in [2]. Four staggered layers of parallel cells form a superlayer (SL), which allows for solving single-hit ambiguities and provides the measurement of two-dimensional segments. A chamber is composed of two superlayers measuring the r - φ coordinates (SL1, SL3), with the wires parallel to the beam line and separated by 23.5 cm, and an orthogonal superlayer measuring the r - z coordinates (SL2).

For the HL-LHC operation, also called Phase 2, the full DT electronics will be replaced with a new system and trigger primitive algorithms will be implemented in powerful FPGAs, resulting in a substantial improvement of the physics performance comparable to the current offline reconstruction system.

We present here an algorithm, called 'Analytical Method' (AM), to perform trigger primitive (TP) generation for the DT trigger system upgrade.

2 The Analytical Method. Performance evaluation

The **Analytical Method** is an algorithm for trigger primitive generation in the DT chambers in HL-LHC. It profits from the better electronics time binning in Phase 2 (1 ns instead of 12.5 ns at present). The algorithm is capable of computing a trigger primitive's crossing time, both in ns (t_0) and bunch crossing (BX) units, together with muon track position and local direction.

The algorithm has been implemented both in software as an emulator and in firmware. The inputs to this algorithm are the time and cell number of all signals detected in a superlayer and can be described in three steps: grouping, fitting and correlation.

The grouping step selects patterns of 3 or 4 fired DT cells compatible with a straight line in a single superlayer and their sub-patterns of 3 over 10 cells at a time in order to reduce combinatorics. All these patterns with their corresponding possible hit laterality (whether the signal was produced right or left of the cell wire) combinations are forwarded to the fitting step.

In the fitting step, once the group of hit cells is identified, thanks to the meantimer [5] property it is possible to compute unambiguously the bunch crossing corresponding to every subset of 3 hits within the group. For cases with 4 hits the BXs of each possible triplet are combined using an arithmetic mean, giving a unique BX for the 4-cells group. For the 3-cells groups, every laterality assumption providing a physical solution is considered. Finally, track parameters are computed using exact formulas from χ^2 minimisation.

As a final step, a correlation between the fits in both φ superlayers is attempted when the fitted times agree within ± 25 ns. If a match is found, the track parameters are recalculated in order to benefit from the larger lever arm given by the distance between SL1 and SL3. If no match is found, all per-SL primitives are kept.

After building the AM DT primitives and clustering the RPC hits, the information from both subdetectors can be combined into a Super-primitive (SP), exploiting the redundancy and complementarity of the two subsystems and combining DT spatial resolution and RPC time resolution.

2.1 Performance evaluation in simulation

The algorithm's performance has been evaluated in a 200 average pile-up simulated sample produced for the L1 Trigger Phase 2 Upgrade TDR [3]. In this sample, two prompt back to back muons are generated, with flat φ and p_T distributions, in a range of p_T between 2 GeV and 100 GeV.

In order to compute efficiencies, the denominator is defined as all the offline segments geometrically matched with a generated muon and the numerator as the trigger primitives reconstructed in the good BX

that match these segments. Figure 1 (a) shows the Barrel Muon Phase 2 trigger primitives efficiency with and without the RPC inclusion and considering the DT and RPC ageing scenarios predicted at the end of HL-LHC [3]. DT-only efficiency is in general very high except for some drops related to regions very affected by the DT ageing. The inclusion of RPC improves efficiency in these most affected regions.

Figure 1 (b) shows $sector\ \varphi$ resolution (position in global coordinates) computed with respect to the simulated hits in the muon chambers. $sector\ \varphi$ resolution is < 0.05 mrad for every chamber, improving a factor ~ 6 with respect to the Phase 1 trigger primitives.

Figure 1: (a) Barrel Muon Phase 2 trigger primitives efficiency with respect to offline segments and (b) position ($sector\ \varphi$) and core resolutions with respect to the simulated hits in the muon chambers. Both figures show results with and without the ageing scenario. More details can be found in [3].

2.2 Performance evaluation in data

The AM has been implemented in VHDL code in order to estimate its performance in real time conditions inside prototyping FPGAs. This activity is critical to estimate the resources required on the final back-end electronics that needs to be designed for HL-LHC. The first implementation of this algorithm has been performed in a Virtex 7 FPGA, in particular, the XC7VX330T-3FFG1761E, where the most occupied resources are the Slice LUTs (around 30%).

Tests of firmware-emulator comparison have been performed in a dedicated test stand at CIEMAT. DT hits from 10000 reconstructed $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ events in the 2016 collision data sample coming from all DT chambers in the CMS detector are provided as input. Using these hits, AM firmware generates the trigger primitives, which can be then compared to the ones obtained by the software emulator. Figure 2 (a) shows the level of agreement in BX when comparing the primitives obtained by the firmware and the emulator with the same hits and lateralities. The insert shows an agreement in the fitted time value at the level of Least Significant Bit (1 ns). This agreement is also reached in fitted position and local direction.

During the Long Shutdown 2 (currently ongoing) a complete exercise was made to instrument one sector (wheel +2 sector 12) of the CMS detector with the HL-LHC DT electronics front-end and back-end prototypes. This way, both Phase 1 and Phase 2 electronics can be run in real conditions inside the CMS infrastructure. One of these back-end boards (the so-called AB7) runs the AM firmware, so it can be validated using real cosmic muons. Figure 2 (b) shows the difference between the crossing time of incoming cosmic muons computed by the DT offline reconstruction and the primitives obtained by the Analytical Method firmware. The core resolution of this distribution is of few ns, while for the Phase 1 system the trigger output time is given in BX units (25 ns step).

Figure 2: (a) Difference in BX assignment between emulator primitives and event BX (blue) and firmware primitives and event BX (red) and (b) difference between the crossing time of incoming cosmic muons computed by the DT offline reconstruction and the Phase 2 AM DT local trigger in the Slice Test set-up. More details can be found in [3].

3 Conclusions

We have proposed a new algorithm for CMS DT trigger primitive generation for Phase 2. Studies in simulation show a performance comparable to the offline reconstruction system. The firmware implementation has been tested injecting DT hits from collision data, showing a good level of agreement with the software emulation. A sustained campaign of cosmics-muon data taking in one CMS sector has already shown the large improvement in time resolution that can be achieved for Phase 2 trigger primitives with respect to the present system.

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Parallelizable Track Pattern Recognition in High-Luminosity LHC

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ABSTRACT

The high instantaneous luminosity conditions in the High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider pose major computational challenges for the collider experiments. One of the most computationally challenging components is the reconstruction of charged-particle tracks. In order to efficiently operate under these conditions, it is crucial that we explore new and faster methods or implementations of charged-particle track reconstruction than what is being used today. Kalman-filter-based methods of the track pattern recognition that are currently used in the LHC experiments are inherently sequential and iterative and therefore cannot easily be accelerated through parallelization or vectorization by modern processors, such as graphics processing units or multicore processors. There have been attempts with great effort in vectorizing Kalman-filter-based methods of the track pattern recognition on modern processors with success. In this work, we instead start with a segment-linking-based algorithm that can be naturally parallelized and vectorized and is expected to run efficiently on modern processors. We established a preliminary segment-linking-based track pattern recognition for the CMS experiment using the Phase-II outer tracker and our findings and implications are presented here. This work is building on experience gained from a prototype of a similar approach studied in a different tracker layout geometry based on ideal detector simulation previously presented at CHEP2016.

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1 Introduction

The reconstruction of charged-particle tracks is crucial for the experiments at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) of CERN. Reconstruction of many objects, such as vertex, lepton, and jet reconstruction, as well as the b tagging, and the missing transverse momentum calculation all rely on the charged particle track reconstruction. Among the reconstruction steps, tracking is most time-consuming and its time scales exponentially with the multiplicity of the hits in the tracker. This leads to a computing challenge for the track reconstruction at the planned High-Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) era, where the number of overlapping proton-proton (pp) collisions (pileup) will increase by severalfold. Therefore it is crucial to investigate ways to speed up the track reconstruction algorithms in order not to suffer loss in tracking efficiency negatively impacting physics results of the experiments.

The industry is providing modern processors that utilize parallelism more and more to provide higher computing power to the consumer. To address the tracking challenge of the HL-LHC it is therefore pertinent to investigate algorithms that can exploit parallelism to best leverage the gains from the industry.

Several novel algorithms are being developed for the HL-LHC environment with a common theme of exploiting parallelism. Patatrack uses a cellular automata-based tracking algorithm on graphic processor units (GPUs) and builds pixel track seeds in parallel [1]. Exa.TrkX uses graph neural network-based algorithm for track building, which can easily be computed in parallel through vectorizing matrix multiplication computations [2]. Even the inherently sequential Kalman filter-based tracking algorithm is being vectorized by seeds, events, and subregions of the detector in the mkFit project to exploit the parallelism of modern architectures [3].

In this work, we present an algorithm approach that is inherently parallel thereby enabling opportunity for efficient tracking on modern architectures. The presented algorithm has a root in the segment linking algorithm used in the central outer tracker of the CDF experiment. Previously a similar algorithm was explored in a different context of exploring grouped layer tracker layout design in Ref. [4, 5], which showed a promising result of being able to reduce the combinatorics drastically with the additional benefit of tracking algorithm being inherently parallel. Adopting from previous work in Ref. [4, 5], the presented algorithm builds mini-doublets by associating hits left by the charged particle in the detector with each other and recursively associates pair of mini-doublets to tracklets and pair of tracklets to track candidates. Each step of the algorithm presented here only requires information of immediate neighbors and therefore can be run in multiple threads in parallel with relative ease. As a proof of concept, the preliminary algorithm is being developed in the context of CMS Collaboration’s HL-LHC outer tracker geometry [6], which is particularly suitable for applying such a parallel algorithm. We show a case study demonstrating the proof of concept of how such an algorithm would work in HL-LHC environment.

2 Segment linking in CMS HL-LHC Outer Tracker

CMS Collaboration is upgrading its tracker for HL-LHC [6]. The proposed design contains double-layered silicon modules with a gap size of ≈ 2 mm dubbed p_T modules in the outer tracker that can reduce occupancy of hits by requiring coincidences of hits between two layers consistent with a minimum p_T threshold. This is illustrated in Figure 1. This design choice was originally driven by enabling hardware-based track trigger capability for tracks with minimum p_T of 2 GeV [6]. However, as the p_T modules look for coincidences of hits in each module separately it also enables a unique opportunity to apply a parallel tracking algorithm.

The main tracking algorithm steps through several stages of building pieces that tracks consist of. First, the algorithm builds the mini-doublets in each p_T module by associating hits in each layer consistent with the minimum p_T threshold of 1 GeV. Then the mini-doublets in the neighboring modules on separate layers are linked together to form segments. Neighboring segments on distinct layer pairs are then linked together by applying a geometrical requirement that the pair of segments be consistent with a track hypothesis. The linked segments are dubbed tracklets. The segment linking can also occur skipping a layer to allow for missing hits by building tracklets with gaps. Figure 2 illustrates various objects: mini-doublets, segments, tracklets, and track candidates.

With various mini-doublets, segments, and tracklets built, one can build various kinds of track candidates

Figure 1: Proposed CMS tracker design for high luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) [6]. The p_T module concept is illustrated here. The double layered modules have a gap of size ≈ 2 mm and the coincidences of hits consistent with a track above a minimum p_T threshold can be applied to reduce occupancies.

by putting together the objects. For example, if no hits are lost for a given charged-particle trajectory, one can put together three segments across the six layers of the outer tracker to form a track candidate. If one or more hit is lost, then a linked segment with gaps can be used to form a track candidate. The seeds from inner pixel detectors can be used as “segments” as well to build track candidates but are not a requirement. Figure 2 illustrates the different kinds of track candidates that can be built from this algorithmic approach.

The benefits of such a segment linking algorithm in the outer tracker are apparent. The algorithm is easily parallelizable as the subroutines of the algorithm only require information from their immediate neighbors. Many tracking algorithms widely used today rely heavily on the inner tracker and its health, while the proposed algorithm does not. algorithm does not depend on the inner tracker or its health, while many tracking algorithms widely used today do. This also means that more extensive displaced tracking will come naturally.

Figure 2: Illustrations of the segment linking algorithm in the outer tracker. (left) Illustration of mini-doublets and segments. (center) Illustration of tracker segments in the outer tracker and their potential benefits. (right) Illustration of non-exhaustive list of possible track candidates that can be built from the presented algorithm.

3 Case study: building barrel tracks via segment linking

As a start, we focus on track candidate reconstruction with no missing hits in the barrel outer tracker. There are a total of 6 layers in the barrel outer tracker with each module in each layer having two hits leading to a total of 12 hits in the barrel outer tracker. As mentioned before this kind of track candidate has the

benefit of not relying on pixel track seeds. We will present the algorithm targeting these tracks and discuss the efficiency of the algorithm.

3.1 Mini-doublet building and efficiency

The first step is to build the mini-doublets using the p_T module concept. The target threshold is 1 GeV. In each module, the hits are associated and checked whether there is a pair of hits consistent with the minimum p_T threshold of 1 GeV. If they pass the requirements the pairs of hits are called mini-doublets. The efficiency of the mini-doublet for the innermost layer and the outermost layer is shown in Figure 3. The efficiency is defined to be the ratio of number of denominator tracks with a mini-doublet in a given layer reconstructed to the number of denominator tracks that leave all 12 hits in the barrel region. Figure 3 shows full efficiency soon after the targeted 1 GeV threshold. This mini-doublet formation is very important in reducing combinatorics. Most hits in the tracker come from low p_T tracks (i.e. < 1 GeV tracks) and by forming mini-doublets one effectively filters out hits from low p_T tracks which are not targeted by this algorithm and only increase combinatorial background. The effect can be seen from the Table 1 where the multiplicities of hits from a representative pileup 200 $t\bar{t}$ event in each layer are reduced by factor 3 to 7.

Layer	1	2	3	4	5	6
Number of hits	36k	28k	21k	17k	12k	6k
Number of mini-doublets	5.9k	3.8k	3.1k	3.7k	3.3k	2.2k
Ratio	6.1	7.3	6.8	4.6	3.5	2.7

Table 1: Number of hits and mini-doublets in each layer of the CMS HL-LHC outer tracker from a representative sample of pileup 200 $t\bar{t}$ events.

Figure 3: Mini-doublet efficiency as a function of p_T . Left is the mini-doublet efficiency for the innermost layer, and the right is the mini-doublet efficiency for the outermost layer.

3.2 Segment building and efficiency

The next step is to build the segments by associating two mini-doublets. To reduce combinatorics in associating the mini-doublets a module map is defined from a large number of simulated muon gun events. The module map is defined such that for a given reference module in a lower layer a list of compatible modules from a neighboring layer is assigned. When creating segments a mini-doublet in a reference module is only compared against mini-doublets from the compatible modules. The angles in the mini-doublets between the two hits and the angle between the mini-doublets are required to be consistent with a track hypothesis. The efficiency of the segment is shown in Figure 4. The efficiency is defined as the ratio of number of denominator

tracks with a segment in a given combination of layers reconstructed to the number of denominator tracks that leave all 12 hits in the barrel region. Soon after the targeted minimum p_T threshold, a good efficiency is achieved.

Figure 4: Segment efficiency as a function of p_T . (Left) Efficiency of segments formed by mini-doublets in layer 1 and 2 from the algorithm. (Center) Efficiency of segments formed by mini-doublets in layer 3 and 4 from the algorithm. (Right) Efficiency of segments formed by mini-doublets in layer 5 and 6 from the algorithm.

3.3 Segment linking (tracklet building) and efficiency

The next step is to build the tracklets by linking two segments. The same module maps used in the segment building are used to determine which segments to attempt to link. This is done by checking the compatibility between the outer module of the inner segment to the inner module of the outer segment of the two segments being linked. If these modules are deemed compatible then various geometrical constraints are checked. If the two segments pass all the requirements then the two segments are considered linked and become a tracklet. The geometrical constraints include the β angles the segments make against the chord drawn in $r - \phi$ plane between the innermost mini-doublet to the outermost mini-doublet and a constraint in $r - z$ plane between the segments and a few more angle compatibility requirements. If the two segments at hand are segments belonging to a single true charged particle track, the $\Delta\beta$ between the β angles will take a value close to zero, while for a pair of segments stemming from combinatorial backgrounds the value of the $\Delta\beta$ will not have a preferred value. This is illustrated in Figure 5 where the peak is visible above the flat combinatorial background from a representative pileup 200 $t\bar{t}$ events. The efficiency for the tracklets are reported for muon gun events, and also for pions and electrons from the pileup 200 $t\bar{t}$ events in Figure 6.

3.4 Track candidate building and efficiency

The track candidate with all hits in six layers for the barrel outer tracker can be simply built by putting together the tracklets from layer 1 to 4 with tracklets from layer 3 to 6 that have a common segment in layers 3-4. The case study presented here focuses on tracks with no hits missing. Other types of track candidates that allow for missing hits will be studied in the future. The efficiency of track candidates with no missing hits are reported for muon gun events, and also for pions and electrons from the pileup 200 $t\bar{t}$ events in Figure 7.

4 Conclusion and outlook

The reconstruction of charged-particle tracks is crucial for the LHC experiments to be successful. In the planned HL-LHC era, the increase in pileup will bring a computational challenge to tracking. To exploit the gains from the industry, we presented here a naturally parallelizable algorithm for the HL-LHC in the

Figure 5: $\Delta\beta$ distribution of tracklets in the barrel outer tracker. (Left) Illustration of how a good and bad segment linking looks like (Center) $\Delta\beta$ distribution for segment linking between segments in layer 1-2 to layer 3-4. (Right) $\Delta\beta$ distribution for segment linking between segments in layer 2-3 to layer 4-5. The $\Delta\beta$ value of correct pairing results in a peak near zero, while the combinatorial background from bad linking is uniformly distributed.

Figure 6: Tracklets efficiency as a function of p_T . The first (second) row shows the tracklet efficiencies for tracklets formed from layer 1-2-3-4 (3-4-5-6) for (left) muon-gun events, (center) pions, (right) electrons from a representative sample of pileup $200 t\bar{t}$ events.

context of CMS experiment. This algorithm links hits to segments, segments to tracklets, and ultimately builds track candidates, where each step can be executed in parallel. The specific algorithm presented here is applied to the outer tracker of the CMS tracker for the HL-LHC. The benefit from building track candidates

Figure 7: Efficiency of track candidates without missing hits as a function of p_T .

with the outer tracker includes complementarity to the inner tracker seeded tracking and a natural extension to displaced tracks among others. As a case study, track candidates with no missing hits in the barrel outer tracker have been studied. The study targeted tracks down to 1 GeV and shows that a good efficiency can be achieved. For future, the performance of the algorithm in the endcaps will be checked as well as building different kinds of track candidates that can allow missing hits and incorporate pixel seed tracks and extend the algorithm to cover wider phase-space.

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A novel reconstruction algorithm for an imaging calorimeter for HL-LHC

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ABSTRACT

The CMS endcap calorimeter upgrade for the High Luminosity LHC in 2027 uses silicon sensors to achieve sufficient radiation tolerance, with the further benefit of a very high readout granularity. Small scintillator tiles with SiPM readout are used in regions permitted by the radiation levels. A novel iterative reconstruction framework (TICL) has been developed to fully exploit the granularity and other significant features of the detector such as precision timing. The inputs to the framework are clusters of energy deposited in individual calorimeter layers delivered by a density-based algorithm which has recently been developed and tuned. This talk will describe the approaches being considered and show selected first results.

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1 Introduction

The first ten years of the LHC operation have been characterized by a remarkable success, exceeding initial expectations. The next big milestone on the accelerator front is the high-luminosity (HL) upgrade of the LHC [1]. At the HL-LHC a significant increase of the instantaneous luminosity is expected, which could reach values up to $7.5 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, about 5-7 higher than the current one, leading to a total integrated luminosity at the end of the HL-LHC data taking of around 3000 fb^{-1} , $20\times$ larger than the one collected thus far. This provides a great opportunity for sensitive tests of the standard model parameters and searches for new physics signals. However, the significant increase in the instantaneous and integrated luminosities comes at the price of almost an order of magnitude increase in the number of multiple proton-proton collisions in the same or neighboring bunch crossings (referred to as pileup), and the significant increase of the radiation levels.

Both of these effects pose major challenges for the experiments, which need to be upgraded to cope with the harsher data taking conditions. To this end, the CMS experiment has planned an extensive upgrade program [2]; the upgraded detectors are designed not only to sustain the HL-LHC conditions, but also to fully exploit the HL-LHC physics potential thanks to their novel capabilities. One of the major CMS upgrades is the replacement of the current electromagnetic and hadronic endcap calorimeters with a high granularity calorimeter (HGCAL) [3].

2 The CMS HGCAL upgrade

The design of the CMS endcap calorimeter upgrade was motivated by the physics requirements in this region, while preserving radiation tolerance under the harder HL-LHC conditions. The region covered by the endcap calorimeters ($1.5 < |\eta| < 3.0$) is essential for the success of the LHC physics program, where processes initiated by vector boson fusion and exotic signals play a major role. Therefore, the upgraded detector should provide the necessary capabilities to identify single objects with kinematic thresholds similar to the current ones, powerful jet flavour identification (e.g., quark-gluon separation), high- p_T particle identification (“tagging”) where the decay products of the initial particle are often merged into a single jet, and more.

Taking all these motivations under consideration, the most promising detector upgrade is an imaging calorimeter with very fine lateral and longitudinal segmentation, complemented by precision timing capabilities. HGCAL is a sampling calorimeter using extensively silicon sensors ($\sim 6\text{M}$ channels) as active material to achieve radiation tolerance, with the additional benefit of a very high readout granularity. In regions with lower radiation levels, small plastic scintillator tiles with individual SiPMs readout are employed.

Each endcap consists of 50 sensor+absorber layers with a total thickness of about $10 \lambda_I$. The first 28 layers form the electromagnetic section, CE-E (about $25 X_0$ and $1.3\lambda_I$). The active element consists solely of silicon sensors of different thicknesses (120, 200, 300 μm) and cell sizes (~ 0.5 , $\sim 1.2 \text{ cm}^2$). The hadronic section, CE-H, is composed of 12 fine sampling layers followed by 10 layers with twice as thick absorbers. In the first eight layers of CE-H, silicon sensors of thickness of 200 or 300 μm , and size of a cell $\sim 1.2 \text{ cm}^2$, alone are used. In the remaining layers, some of the area at larger radius, where the radiation dose is smaller, is instrumented with scintillator tiles. In order to reliably operate the silicon sensors and the scintillator tiles after irradiation, the entire HGCAL detector will be operated at -30°C .

3 Particle reconstruction in HGCAL

The design of HGCAL has great potential for the application of advanced pattern recognition techniques. The possibility of a five-dimensional (x, y, z , energy and time) particle shower reconstruction is ideally suited for particle flow algorithms. However, the large channel count and the severe pileup conditions are some of the challenges that require breakthroughs in many areas of the reconstruction chain to fully exploit the HGCAL potential, without jeopardizing the overall reconstruction timing. The success of this program relies on a coherent effort in all these areas which translates into designing a versatile reconstruction framework to explore, test and validate new approaches.

3.1 The iterative clustering framework

Motivated by the requirements discussed previously, we developed "The Iterative CLustering" (TICL) framework. TICL is a modular reconstruction framework designed to fully exploit the HGCal potential by processing the energy deposited by particles on the HGCal sensors (RecHits) and returning particle properties and probabilities. Figure 1 illustrates the TICL building blocks (components). The highly modular structure of TICL enables us to study different approaches for each step of the reconstruction chain, by simply modifying only the relevant parts. Moreover, TICL follows an iterative approach; separate TICL configurations ("iterations") can be designed to reconstruct different particle species. Lastly, TICL is conceived with parallel processing in mind, suitable for the upcoming era of heterogeneous computing in high energy physics. In the remaining section, we present in more detail some of the key ingredients of TICL.

Figure 1: Illustration of the building blocks of TICL. Each box corresponds to a different component of the TICL framework, and the arrows indicate possible connections between the components.

3.1.1 Layer cluster formation ("2D clustering")

One of the fundamental ingredients of TICL is grouping RecHits in the same HGCal layer that originate from the same particle, broadly known as clustering, to form the "Layer Clusters". The clustering relies on the "clustering by energy" (CLUE) algorithm [4]. CLUE, inspired by [5], is a fast and fully parallelizable algorithm, exploiting the concept of local energy density flow.

To achieve fast performance, CLUE starts by organizing the RecHits by their proximity in a fixed grid in the $\eta - \phi$ space, and uses a spatial index for efficient neighbourhood queries. Therefore, for each HGCal layer, a fixed-grid spatial index is constructed, registering each RecHit according to their $\eta - \phi$ coordinates. Then, the clustering procedure can be summarized in three main steps. First, CLUE calculates the local energy density of each RecHit, defined as:

$$\rho = \sum_j \chi(d_{ij}) E_j, \quad (1)$$

where i is the current RecHit, j the RecHits within a distance d_c (including RecHit i), E_j the energy of each RecHit, and $\chi(d_{ij})$ a convolution kernel, which in the current implementation has the form:

$$\chi(d_{ij}) = \begin{cases} 1 & d_{ij} = 0 \\ 0.5 & d_{ij} \leq d_c \\ 0 & d_{ij} > d_c \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

In the next step, CLUE computes for each RecHit the quantity δ , i.e. the distance to the closest RecHit with higher ρ , and establishes a connection between these two RecHits (important for parallelizing the algorithm). At the final step, the RecHits are labelled as “seeds”, “followers”, and “noise.” RecHits with $\rho \geq \rho_c$ and distance $\delta \geq \delta_c$ are promoted to be seeds, whereas RecHits with $\rho < \rho_c$ and distance $\delta \geq \delta_0$ are denoted to be “noise.” All other RecHits are associated to their closest seeds. The parameters ρ_c , d_c , δ_c , and δ_0 are tuned based on physics arguments. The current configuration for silicon and scintillator sensors is summarized in Table 1. With the proposed tuning the algorithm is extremely robust against noise, while, as it will be seen in Section 4, is able to cluster almost all of the particle’s deposited energy in the sensitive layers.

	ρ_c	d_c	δ_c	δ_0
silicon	$9 \times \sigma_{\text{Noise}}$	1.3 [cm]	1.3 [cm]	2.6 [cm]
scintillator	$9 \times \sigma_{\text{Noise}}$	$0.0315 [\eta \times \phi]$	$0.0315 [\eta \times \phi]$	$0.063 [\eta \times \phi]$

Table 1: Summary of the current values of CLUE’s tunable parameters. The term σ_{Noise} refers to the one standard deviation of the expected noise distribution.

3.1.2 Particle shower reconstruction (“TICL iteration”)

Another fundamental ingredient of TICL is the “iteration”, which combines information from the various TICL components to reconstruct the particle shower, which within TICL, is referred to as a “Trackster”. The skeleton of a TICL iteration can be summarized as follows:

- **Building blocks:** the layer clusters returned by CLUE
- **Seeding regions:** identify the regions of interest and the layer clusters compatible with these regions. A seeding region can be global, i.e. it spans the full HGCAL acceptance, or local (e.g., a small region around a track propagated to the HGCAL entrance surface).
- **Pattern recognition:** the algorithm that links together layer clusters among different layers to reconstruct the particle shower i.e., a Trackster. Section 3.1.3 presents details of the current implementation.
- **Linking and classification:** identify the Trackster type and improve the energy measurement with the aid of traditional or machine-learning-based techniques.
- **Masking:** option to mask the layer clusters used in this iteration. This results in a significant reduction of the combinatorics in later iterations, which comes with the advantage of less computing requirements and improved reconstruction performance.

The overall goal of TICL is to follow an iterative approach: first reconstruct simpler objects (e.g., electrons), mask the layer clusters used in this iteration, then reconstruct more complicated ones.

3.1.3 A TICL Trackster

A TICL Trackster aims to link the layer clusters associated to each TICL iteration. It is a Direct Acyclic Graph [6] created by a pattern recognition algorithm, which links layer clusters to form three-dimensional objects (i.e., the reconstructed particles’ showers). Therefore, each vertex of the graph is a layer cluster, and the connections between the vertices are the edges of the graph.

The pattern recognition method currently implemented in TICL is based on the Cellular Automaton (CA) algorithm [7]. The CA algorithm aims to group entities with similar properties (e.g., layer clusters associated with the same particle) by exploring information between the entity under question and the entities in its neighbourhood. Usually, a fixed rule is applied to all entities simultaneously. The CA implementation in HGCAL reconstruction can be streamlined in three steps.

The first step is responsible for the generation of “doublets”, i.e., connections between successive layer clusters. For a layer cluster LC_N in the HGCAL layer N , a search window in layer $N + 1$ is opened. The

search window is obtained by projecting the spatial dimensions of LC_N in $\eta - \phi$ to layer $N + 1$. To account for the lateral shower evolution, in conjunction to the HGICAL design specifications, the search window is extended by $\Delta\eta \times \Delta\phi$ of 0.05 (0.1) for $|\eta| < 2.1$ ($|\eta| \geq 2.1$). This is graphically shown in Fig. 2 (a). Layer clusters contained in the search region are connected to LC_N , and form doublets. Timing information is used, whenever it is available, to reject layer clusters originating from pileup interactions. To account for detector inefficiencies or the shower properties, the doublet formation could be carried out even for layer clusters belonging to non-consecutive layers. The maximum number of missing layers is a tunable parameter and can vary between iterations. Additional selection on the minimum number of RecHits to form a layer cluster can be also applied to suppress layer clusters stemming from noise.

The second step in the pattern recognition is the doublet linking. Doublets are linked if two angular requirements are satisfied: an angular compatibility between each outermost doublet and the origin of the seeding region, and a minimal alignment condition between the two doublets. The two conditions are illustrated in Fig. 2 (b). The angular requirements may vary between different iterations.

The third and final step in the pattern recognition is to connect all doublets satisfying the above angular requirements to form a Trackster. Ideally a single Trackster should be created for each particle interacting with HGICAL. There are currently four prototype iterations: the track-seeded iteration, targeting e^\pm and charged hadrons; the electromagnetic iteration targeting γ ; the hadronic iteration targeting neutral hadrons; finally, the MIP iteration focusing on particles that deposit a very small amount of energy in HGICAL, such as muons.

Figure 2: (a) Basic principle of the pattern recognition algorithm used in TICL. (b) Illustration of the angular requirements between doublets; compatibility between the outermost doublet and the origin of the seeding region (left), and minimal alignment condition between the two doublets (right).

4 TICL performance with single particles

Preliminary results of the single-particle energy response and resolution in events with no pileup interactions, for showers reconstructed using the latest TICL developments, are presented [8]. No corrections are applied for ECAL rear-leakage (for photons) or for hadronic non-compensation for pions (i.e. software compensation). Moreover, the results shown in this section use information solely from HGICAL, without combining information from other CMS subdetectors.

In order to access the performance of individual steps of the TICL reconstruction, different energy sums are compared:

- **Rec/able:** the reconstructable energy, obtained by summing the energy of all RecHits produced by the generated particle

- **Clustered:** the sum of the energy in the layer clusters returned by the CLUE algorithm having at least one RecHit associated with the generated particle
- **TICL:** the sum of the energy in the shower reconstructed using TICL
- **TICL (non-interacting):** the TICL sum where the showers are restricted to those resulting from pions that have not interacted in the tracker volume in front of HGCAL.

The TICL performance on electromagnetic shower reconstruction is evaluated using events with a single photon (γ). Figure 3 shows the energy response and resolution as a function of the generated γ energy. The γ s are generated at $|\eta| \sim 1.9$ directly in front of HGCAL and thus reach HGCAL unconverted. It can be seen that CLUE manages to cluster almost all of the deposited energy. The showers reconstructed by TICL contain a large fraction of this, although the fraction varies with energy and the non-linearity induced will require correction. To compare the energy resolution consistently across the different energy sums, the resolution in each energy sum is corrected for the differences observed in the response. The correction has a negligible impact on the results. The energy resolution is fitted with a two-parameter function with the form: $\sigma_E/E = s/\sqrt{E} \oplus c$, where s (c) is the stochastic (constant) term. No noise term is included in the fit since its magnitude is negligible. The results of the fit are summarized in Table 2. The constant term for the “reconstructable” energy is higher than expected due to rear leakage which will have to be corrected for. This is confirmed by selecting events with almost no energy in the last layer of CE-E. In those cases, the constant term for the Rec/able case drops to 0.6%.

Figure 3: Energy response (left) and resolution (right) as a function of the generated γ energy. The different scenarios are detailed in the text.

The TICL performance in reconstructing hadronic showers is evaluated using events with single- π^+ , generated at $|\eta| \sim 1.9$. Figure 4 shows the energy response and resolution as a function of the generated π^+ energy. The effect of hadronic non-compensation can be seen in the Rec/able energy, almost all of which is clustered. The showers reconstructed by TICL contain a large fraction of this energy. Similarly to the electromagnetic showers, the energy resolution as a function of energy is fitted with a two-parameter function of the same form. The results are summarized in Table 2.

The HGCAL layers are instrumented with different types of active elements, i.e., silicon sensors of different size and thickness in the CE-E, or even different types (silicon sensors and scintillator tiles) in the CE-H. The exact configuration depends on the layer depth and η . Therefore, it is important to evaluate the robustness of TICL reconstruction performance across η . Figure 5 shows the energy resolution of single- γ and single- π^+ with $E = 100$ GeV, as function of the particle’s η , where stable performance is observed.

Figure 4: Energy response (left) and resolution (right) as a function of the generated π^+ energy. The different scenarios are detailed in the text.

	Rec/able	Clustered	TICL	TICL (non-interacting)
	Electromagnetic showers			
stochastic term [%]	23	23	25	-
constant term [%]	0.9	0.9	0.9	-
	Hadronic showers			
stochastic term [%]	72	72	80	72
constant term [%]	5.5	5.9	8.7	8

Table 2: Results of the two-parameter fit: $\sigma_E/E = s/\sqrt{E} \oplus c$, in the energy resolution achieved on electromagnetic and hadronic showers using the TICL framework. The different scenarios are detailed in the text. The constant term for the reconstructable energy in electromagnetic showers improved to 0.6% when events with no energy released beyond the last layer of CE-E are selected.

Residual differences in performance across η are due to the different HGCALE configurations discussed earlier in the section. Further tuning of the reconstruction algorithm is foreseen to account for these effects.

5 Conclusions

We present a novel reconstruction framework, “TICL”, for imaging calorimeters like HGCALE. TICL has been designed as a modular framework to exploit the full potential of such detectors. Preliminary studies on single particle reconstruction in events with no pileup were presented showing very good performance. Additional activities, like heterogeneous computing and advanced machine learning techniques are also worked out in parallel.

Figure 5: Relative energy resolution as a function of η of the generated γ (left) and π^+ (right). Both particles are generated with $E = 100$ GeV in a sample with no pileup interactions.

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An optical network for accelerating real-time tracking with FPGAs

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ABSTRACT

The “Artificial Retina” is a highly-parallelized tracking architecture that promises high-throughput, low-latency, and low-power consumption when implemented in state-of-art FPGA devices.

Working on not-built events, the “Artificial Retina” needs a dedicated distribution network of large bandwidth and low latency, delivering to every FPGA the hits required to perform track reconstruction. This is a technologically challenging aspect of the system which has not yet been tested in a life-size application.

The upgraded LHCb DAQ is an ideal environment for a preliminary test of this methodology. Since the upcoming LHC Run-3, the LHCb Level-0 hardware trigger will be removed. The experiment will readout, build and deliver events to the High Level Trigger system at the full LHC collision rate of 30 MHz. The present work is part of a wider Real Time Analysis project, which has been formed with the purpose of organising data processing within this novel environment. The “Artificial Retina” represents an R&D project towards future fast technologies for real-time tracking.

We used as benchmark the reconstruction of tracks within the new VELO-pixel detector, that is composed of a limited number of readout units. We introduce the design of the fast optical network, carrying a total bandwidth of ~ 15 Tb/s, studied for performing VELO tracking in real time. and the results of our tests of an actual prototype assembled and integrated in a vertical slice of the upgraded LHCb DAQ.

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1 Introduction

Computational needs required by high energy physics (HEP) experiments keep increasing, not just for event reconstruction but also for data distribution to the server farms. As an example, during Run-3 the LHCb Event Builder will have to handle the sizeable bandwidth of 40 Tbps. If the current approach is adopted also in Run-5, the required bandwidth will increase by an additional factor of 10, at least. In this view, it is valuable to explore new solutions based on heterogeneous computing.

Modern FPGAs have the capability to perform highly-parallel processing, with high throughput and low latency. This allows us to develop a tracking system that can operate at the very first processing level in a high-rate environment like the LHC [1]. With such a system we can instrument just the desired sub-detectors and replace hit data with tracks in real time. Thus, the data volume is reduced by providing trigger primitives, even before performing Event Building.

As shown in Figure 1(a), data from different layers are typically read out separately by the DAQ. Following our approach, data could be forwarded to several Tracking Boards. Track reconstruction requires to combine data from several different layers, hence Tracking Boards need to exchange information through a Patch Panel. If the entire process is completed within few μs , tracks can be added to the event record before data are forwarded to the Event Builder.

To answer these needs, we have developed the “Artificial Retina” tracking architecture which grants highly-parallel tracking to be implemented at the very first processing level of a HEP experiment.

Figure 1: Schematics of the data flow in a tracking system that can operate at the very first level of processing (a), and its integration in the LHCb Event Builder (b).

2 The “Artificial Retina” architecture

The “Artificial Retina” is a highly-parallel tracking architecture formally similar to the “Hough transform”, a method already applied to find lines in image processing.

The track parameters space is represented by a matrix of cells (Figure 2a). The center of each cell corresponds to a reference track in the detector that intersects the layers in specific spatial points called receptors.

Each cell computes a weighted sum of hits nearby the reference track. The weights are proportional to the distance between the hits and the receptor. The resulting sum approaches the number of subdetector layers as the set of hits gets closer to the reference track (Figure 2b).

Subsequently, the cells search local maxima in the matrix of weighted sums. Track parameters are reconstructed by interpolating the responses of cells nearby the local maxima (Figure 2c).

Figure 2: Track reconstruction steps with the “Artificial Retina” architecture.

To reach high-throughput, cells work in a fully-parallel way, being spread over several chips to overcome FPGA size limitations without increasing latency. Each FPGA processes a portion of every event, differently to the usual HEP approach in which each CPU inside HPC farms reconstructs a set of events.

The crucial backbone of the “Artificial Retina” is a Distribution Network capable of exchanging data quickly and effectively between FPGA boards.

3 A dedicated distribution network

Each Tracking Board is paired with a DAQ board, so that it only gets data from a portion of the sub-detector. A custom network redistributes the hits by track parameter coordinates, performing something similar to a “change of reference system”. Furthermore, by using Lookup Tables (LUTs) the Distribution Network delivers to each cell only the hits close to its receptors (Figure 3), resulting in a smaller number of hits to be processed by the cell. This allows the system to reach higher throughput.

Figure 3: Hits routing from the detector coordinate space to the track parameters space. Hits coming from a specific region are delivered only to the cells in the corresponding region.

We designed a modular Distribution Network, with the dispatcher as the basic block. It has two inputs and two outputs, being able to send any input to any output (even both) according to the LUT routing scheme. Combining a sufficient number of dispatchers it is possible to build a Distribution Network with the desired number of inputs and outputs. The network is implementable within the same array of FPGAs performing the tracking, in separate and independent locations of the chip.

Modern FPGAs have numerous high-bandwidth transceivers (XCVRs), that can be used to implement optical serial links between the boards. Optical serial links allow to exchange hits between several boards with great flexibility, connecting distant boards, increasing the number of links on a busy path, or implementing only useful paths.

4 Prototype throughput and latency performance

We built a prototype of the “Artificial Retina” system based on Intel Stratix-V FPGAs and tested its track reconstruction performances with simulated events. The simulated detector is composed by a generic 6 axial-layers layout. Input data are stored in circular buffers injecting ‘realistic’ hit data at 30 MHz, as in LHC running. Since data come from different readout units, it is crucial to simulate realistic time skews between several inputs. At Run-3 running conditions the maximum expected delay is $\sim 10 \mu\text{s}$. We delayed one input by this value to stress the internal buffers and ensure the tolerance to input latencies.

While testing the buffer size remained under control, and the output rate matched the input one. We verified that every track has been correctly reconstructed comparing the actual output with the tracks reconstructed by a C++ simulation of the system.

We did split the system between two FPGAs: one with the Distribution Network and one containing the Cells. The boards were interconnected by 12 optical fibers. In this configuration we achieved the same event rate as when the system is implemented in a single FPGA, demonstrating that the “Artificial Retina” can be distributed over more FPGAs without decreasing the throughput [2]. In this configuration we measured a latency of $\sim 0.4 \mu\text{s}$.

5 Application to LHCb

Our system will be part of a testbed that the LHCb experiment is deploying for the specific purpose of testing new computing accelerators during data taking in the upcoming LHC Run.

LHCb is a forward spectrometer designed to study b and c physics. It is being upgraded and in 2021 will start to acquire data with an almost completely new detector and trigger system [3]. Instantaneous luminosity will increase by a factor of 5, and to take full advantage of the increased statistics, the upgraded LHCb will have a trigger-less readout system. The full inelastic collision rate of 30 MHz will be processed by the fully-software trigger (HLT). The Event Builder will handle the sizable bandwidth of 40 Tbps.

Figure 1(b) shows how the “Artificial Retina” can be integrated in the LHCb DAQ system. In LHCb data flow from the detector to the Event Filter Farm (EFF) through the Event Builder nodes and its network. The Tracking Boards could be installed in the Event Builder nodes, reading hits from the DAQ boards and providing tracks. The Event Builder performs the building, seeing the “Artificial Retina” like a virtual sub-detector.

Reconstructing tracks in the LHCb Vertex Locator (VELO) is the most time consuming task in the first stage of the HLT reconstruction, requiring the 48.3% of the overall processing time. Hence, this sub-detector represents an interesting use case for the implementation of the “Artificial Retina”. We already performed studies concerning the physic performance of an “Artificial Retina”-based VELO tracker [4]. However building a large network among the Tracking Boards is technically challenging, and demonstrating the feasibility of a life-size network is an important step for the realisation of the system.

6 Life-size network prototype

The VELO detector is composed of 52 silicon pixel modules, of which 38 are placed in the forward region. The remaining layers are mainly used to optimise the primary vertex precision. A single DAQ board acquires data from a VELO module, therefore we need at least 38 Tracking Boards to read data from the forward region. To ensure an appropriate bandwidth between the boards, we split the VELO track parameters space in 4 quadrants. Cells of the same quadrant share a major numbers of hits, requiring a highly interconnected network between the corresponding FPGAs. Cells of different quadrants can also share hits, but needing less bandwidth, the network implemented is simpler.

We can implement 4 full-mesh networks, one for quadrant, 10 FPGAs each. Then the i -th FPGA of a network is connected to the i -th FPGA of the other three networks creating a full-mesh of full-meshes (Figure 4). Hit exchange between not directly connected FPGAs require a hop, increasing the communication latency. However the total latency remains below the μs limit.

Figure 4: Network topology of a full-mesh network of 4 full-mesh sub-networks based on 10 FPGAs each.

This configuration requires 12 links for each FPGA. Several off-the-shelf FPGA boards are equipped with 16 XCVRs, so this topology is implementable without the need for custom hardware.

We are building a prototype of a 10-node full-mesh network in the LHCb Data Center using half-sized FPGA cards. The first operational plan is to process simulated data, gradually moving to parasitic operation on real VELO data during Run-3 data taking.

We performed a preliminary test with 5 cards in a full-mesh configuration (Figure 5). Every board sends pseudo-random sequences (PRBS31) to the other 4 FPGAs through 10 Gbps optical links. We tested the system for 23 consecutive days at maximum speed, without detecting transmission errors on all but one link. The Bit Error Rate (BER) of the links is lower than $2 \cdot 10^{-16}$ (CL = 95%). The BER of the fault link is $\sim 10^{-13}$. By reducing the transmission speed, the errors disappeared.

Figure 5: The hardware used for the test. The cables go to a patch panel (left) that allows to interconnect the FPGAs (right) with the desired network topology.

Afterwards we implemented a realistic Distribution Network using simulated hits, written into the FPGAs memories, from different events, instead of pseudo-random sequences. Special words, called EndEvent, separate hits of different events, while carrying the event identification number. Data reading on different FPGAs is not synchronised, for a better correspondence to the actual environment in which the system will be placed. In each FPGA a network of Dispatchers routes hits to 8 different lines according to the FPGA of destination. We based the data transmission on the Intel SerialLite II, which provides flow control, preventing transmission when the receiving buffer is full. Having implemented 8 lines using only 5 FPGAs, some XCVRs are closed in serial loopback. The Cells require that the events coming from the XCVRs are aligned, at their receiving side. If an EndEvent is missing or a transmission error modifies the event ID, the alignment can not be ensured and an error flag is raised. This is useful to monitor the correct behaviour of the Distribution Network and of the XCVRs. As a debugging step, we can also read the output data from the host computer, and compare it with the simulation. During a 5 weeks test we did not detect any error.

7 Conclusions

In future HEP experiments event building and tracking will become more challenging. In this view, it is important to explore new solutions based on heterogeneous computing. The “Artificial Retina” is a highly-

parallel tracking system that can provide efficient real-time processing of data already at pre-build level, takings full advantage of modern FPGAs capability.

A fast dedicated Distribution Network is a crucial element of the system, which allows to collect data from several DAQ nodes, overcoming FPGA size limits, while reaching high-throughput and low-latencies. We designed a network suitable for a real application in LHCb, and we now have a life-size prototype in advanced state of realisation, processing simulated data. Our system will be part of a testbed that LHCb is deploying for the specific purpose of testing new computing accelerators. The plan is to perform parasitic operation on real VELO data during Run-3 data taking.

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Displaced Event Classification Using Graph Networks

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ABSTRACT

Long-lived massive particles, predicted in numerous Standard Model extensions, are a particularly difficult target for online event reconstruction. This work presents a study of detecting the presence of displaced vertices in a collider experiment in several environmental conditions. In particular Graph Neural Networks performing classification on input hit-level data are shown to perform well in the task of separating prompt against displaced events with results translating, with some degradation, into more busy environments. Furthermore, promising results are shown for identifying events from a benchmark supersymmetric process with future work investigating higher pileup environments.

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1 Introduction

LHC searches for new physics involving massive long-lived particles (LLPs) often rely on the LLP decay products to select events online. Current selection methodologies optimised for prompt decays can become very inefficient when these decay products have low energy. The direct identification of displaced decays is limited by the fact that running a full track and vertex reconstruction at a sufficient rate during active data-taking, is computationally infeasible. Identifying the presence of displaced decays from raw detector hits would allow to mitigate the selection inefficiency.

In the Standard Model, heavy particles like top quarks and weak bosons decay very close to the interaction point. However, there are several sources of displaced decays of light particles, such as B and K mesons, and interactions of primary hadrons with the detector material. Many theories for physics beyond the Standard Model (BSM) predict LLPs that could decay producing high-mass displaced vertices within the inner tracking volume stressing the need to accurately discriminate between light and heavy secondary vertices [1].

The problem will be studied using simulated detector hits and represented in cylindrical coordinates (r, ϕ, z) . A supersymmetric (SUSY) particle production process, shown in Figure 1, was chosen as benchmark signal, while the Standard Model multi-jet production was used to model the backgrounds. Event-level classification will be used to identify of an interesting event features, such as the presence of a secondary vertex. This is a challenging problem as the per-event topology is highly variable both in size and connectivity. Recently, Graph Neural Networks have shown promise in track reconstruction and will be further investigated here in the context of event selection.

Figure 1: The principal process under study is the pair production of supersymmetric charginos, denoted $\tilde{\chi}_1^\pm$, which decay into two neutralinos, $\tilde{\chi}_1^0$, and two W bosons. Because of their weak coupling (λ'') to quarks, the neutralinos decays into three quarks which fragment and hadronise into jets. For this study both supersymmetric particles are simulated with a mean life-time of 1 ns and are thus long-lived.

2 Graph Neural Networks

To effectively discriminate different types of events, an algorithm needs to consider the event topology. Due to the underlying physics, the number of final state particles is highly variable each event and as a consequence both the topology and the number of detector hits are as well. This sparse and dynamic structure is challenging for many deep learning approaches such as dense (e.g. as investigated in our previous work [2]), and convolutional neural networks.

Convolutional neural networks have recently seen successful application to calorimeter data, for example in jet classification, due to the image-like structure of the data. However, particular care needs to be taken due to the sparsity of the data [3]. The tracking detector modeled in this work can be construed as image planes, similar to a typical image interpretation of a calorimeter, however, in a tracking detector sparsity issues are more pronounced.

Both recurrent and convolutional neural networks have seen recent successes in online event classification using reconstructed particles as inputs [4]. However, since it relies on reconstructed inputs its applicability to displaced signatures is limited.

Recently, graph neural networks coupled with an explicit graph construction step have been showing promise in processing sparse, structured data by directly operating only on active elements allowing the architecture to be applied to low level detector hits. Ferrel et al. demonstrated its potential for application to primary track reconstruction in [5].

A strategy similar to that of Ferrel et al. was adopted for this work with the addition of the aggregation network from [6] to provide a per-event binary classification output for event selection. In [5] the per-segment output is scalar, we use a multidimensional output (3–4 depending on the target). For this experiment internal dense networks are all single layer networks with the same width, yielding a single hyper-parameter to control the entire network capacity. A schematic overview of the architecture can be seen in Figure 2. The network design, training and data loading was implemented using pytorch (v1.1.0).

The graph building step consists of generating segment candidates from the input hits based on the angle between two hits and the origin. The segment candidate is additionally extrapolated to the beamline crossing, and if the deviation in z is too large the candidate is excluded.

The training operates on graph data, taking as input an event after the graph building step. Two targets are used during training: a per-event output (Marked A in Figure 2) classifies the event as either displaced, or as containing an LLP, depending on the task; and a per-segment output (Marked E in Figure 2) is used to guide the hidden representation to classify segments into categories fake, prompt, displaced, and optionally, whether the segment was generated by a supersymmetric particle.

To evaluate the architecture described in this section, three tasks of increasing difficulty were defined: Task 0, the initial task, prods the general applicability of the approach to separating displaced events from prompt ones in a simplified 2D environment; Task 1, the second task, introduces realistic physics processes and particle propagation in a 3D environment; Task 2, the third and final task, further looks at separating events containing a supersymmetric signature from events lacking such a signature putting increased requirements on the network to .

Figure 2: The network architecture consists of four dense networks. The input network transforms the initial input hits, labelled X, to a hidden representation, labelled P. A separate graph construction step yields candidate segments for the input hits. The collection of segments is labelled G. The edge network outputs classification predictions for each segment, labelled E, while the node network refines the hidden representation for each hit. The application of the edge and node networks are repeated for a set number of times. Finally the hidden representation is passed to an aggregation network producing an event wide prediction, labelled A. The final output comprises the edge predictions and the event prediction during training while during evaluation the output consists solely of the aggregation network output.

3 Datasets and generation

For this experiment a dedicated simulation setup was developed to describe a simplified collider detector. The geometry and the layout was inspired by the silicon part of the ATLAS inner detector geometry. Eight barrel layers and 12 end-cap layers were included, corresponding to the silicon-pixel and silicon-strip components, with the active surfaces modeled as perfect cylinders and disks respectively. The interaction point between a simulated particle track and the detector surface was recorded as an exact hit in three dimensions, r , φ , and z . Particles were propagated in a uniform 2 T magnetic field. The simulation did not include multiple scattering, hadronic interactions, nor hit resolution effects. MadGraph5 aMC@NLO 2.7.2 [7] was used to generate the hard-scatter event, and parton showering was performed with Pythia8 [8]. Finally Delphes [9], with a custom module, was used for particle propagation. For the simulated event samples including the effects of pile-up interactions in proton-proton collisions, a varying number of simulated minimum-bias interactions were overlaid on the hard-scattering event, following a Poisson distribution. These interactions were generated using Pythia 8.2.

Three datasets were generated to perform the studies presented in this document, including two different SUSY production modes: an electron-positron collision environment with low track-multiplicity, and a proton-proton collision environment with larger track-multiplicity.

- $e^+e^- \rightarrow \chi^+\chi^-$ — A low track-multiplicity environment used for training. Events have on average 26 tracks and 200 hits. A total of 10^6 events were generated, and after pre-processing 10^5 were used in further experiments.
- $pp \rightarrow \chi^+\chi^-$ — The proton-proton collision version of the process is busier and was generated both without and with pileup ($\mu = 10$) used for evaluation. Events have typically 200–300 (900–950) tracks and 1100–1500 (4400–4900) hits in the $\mu = 0$ ($\mu = 10$) dataset depending on the value of the supersymmetric particle masses. A total of 10^5 (10^4) events were generated for the $\mu = 0$ ($\mu = 10$) dataset.
- $pp \rightarrow jj$ — A typical multijet background used for evaluation. A total of 10^4 events were generated with a mean of about 200 tracks and 1000 hits per event.

Example events from these processes can be seen in Figure 3. The mean lifetime of the supersymmetric particles is set to 1 ns and their masses lie in the 100-300 GeV range (see task descriptions in Section 4 for exact values).

Figure 3: View of the xy -plane of a typical event in the simulated detector. True particle tracks are visible as dashed lines, solid markers are detector hits. Two marker colors have specialised meaning: A red marker indicates the position of the primary vertex, and a green marker indicates a displaced vertex.

For the electron-positron dataset a pre-processing step was conducted by: excluding trivial events with only 2 visible tracks, and, as in our previous work, introducing a gap of 5 cm between prompt and displaced events to facilitate learning. This means no events containing a secondary vertex in the range $0 < R < 5$ [cm] are retained.

In addition to the three dimensional datasets defined above, a two dimensional dataset was used for an initial step of the investigation. This dedicated dataset simulates a slice in the detector xy-plane and is concerned only with in-plane particle-like tracks. Tracks are generated independently and no event-wide energy-momentum conservation is required. Eight barrel layers were used in the simulation, similar to the three dimensional setup. The generation process can be tuned to produce a number of tracks from the primary vertex. For displaced vertex generation, a set number of tracks originating from the primary vertex are selected and a secondary vertex is placed along their trajectory. Secondary vertices are required to appear inside the tracking volume and the selected primary tracks are subsequently removed.

For all datasets, besides the two-dimensional toy data, a pre-processing step was applied limiting the number of hits per track to the ten first, including only hits from the barrel region. This as a simple way to limit control the momentum of considered tracks, and to simplify the graph construction step.

4 Case studies

Three tasks of increasing difficulty were defined to investigate the efficacy of the network. The first two, denoted Task 0 and Task 1, investigate how the network scales from a simple to a more realistic collision environment. The last task, most interesting for future application, investigates the network's ability to discriminate displaced vertices coming from different processes.

4.1 Task 0 – 2D environment

The initial task investigated involved separating prompt events (no displaced vertex) from those with a displaced vertex. A simpler version of the full architecture described in Section 2 was applied to the two dimensional dataset as an initial test of the suitability of the approach.

Figure 4: Showing two displaced events, in (a) correctly identified, and in (b), with an incorrect prediction. Solid orange lines indicate true particle path. For segments, red solid lines indicate a true segment, while grey indicate a fake segment. A blue round marker indicates the primary vertex, and a blue cross indicates a secondary vertex. Note that the background-like displaced event contains no track segments from the displaced tracks.

The network was trained using a small, $O(10^3)$ events, dataset with an equal distribution of prompt and displaced events. For evaluation an independent sample generated with the same process as the training data was used.

The network accurately classified all events containing a segment originating from a displaced vertex. Interestingly the network misclassified events where a displaced vertex lay within the detector volume and generated hits, but failed to generate detectable segments, as can be seen in Figure 4.

The failure mode is not expected to significantly impact inference in a production environment, but highlights a limitation of the network to exploit hits lacking connectivity information.

4.2 Task 1 – Displaced event classification

The second task investigates how well the network performance translates to different levels of pileup by training in a low track multiplicity process and evaluating in increasingly more busy environments. The classification target was to separate prompt events from displaced events.

For training the electron-positron dataset was used, while for evaluation an independent part of the electron-positron data was used together with the proton-proton version of the SUSY process, both with and without pileup. When included, the pileup is set to $\mu = 10$. The datasets span a range of track multiplicities of 30–900, about half an order of magnitude.

The mass for the chargino was set to 181 GeV, while the mass of the neutralino was set to 96 GeV.

The performance of network on the three different datasets can be seen in Figure 5. The background rejection is measured as the inverse efficiency of selecting a background event as signal. The network can learn the simple environment well, but the performance is degraded for the two proton-proton datasets with the high pileup environment performing only slightly better than random chance.

The degradation across processes is driven primarily by two factors: The electron-positron sample has a margin of 5 cm around the interaction point not present in the proton-proton samples, and the different track multiplicities in the environments. The relatively stable performance retained across a seven-fold increase in track multiplicity is promising. The performance degradation could be recovered with a dedicated training targeting proton-proton collisions at a higher pileup level.

Figure 5: ROC curves from Task 1 and 2. In (a): Outcome of Task 1, discriminating displaced from prompt events across three different physics processes of increasing difficulty. The network was trained on data similar to the electron-positron set shown here in blue, where the best performance is reached. When transitioning to process environments not explicitly trained for, some performance is retained, but at a pileup of $\mu = 10$ most separation power is lost. There is an approximately seven-fold difference in track multiplicity between subsequent processes. In (b): Outcome of Task 2, separating a displaced SUSY event from a multijet background. Note that the good performance is mostly driven by a difference in track multiplicity between the two samples.

4.3 Task 2 – Displaced SUSY event classification

The final task studies how well a SUSY process can be isolated from both prompt and other displaced events.

The network was again trained on electron-positron data where prompt events constitutes the majority of the background, with a smaller amount of events where the SUSY particle decayed close to the interaction point and gave rise to further Standard Model decays. For evaluation, the proton-proton SUSY process (without pileup) was combined with the multijet dataset.

The mass for the chargino was set to 281 GeV, while the mass of the neutralino was set to 196 GeV, an increase of 100 GeV from the previous task to increase the detector activity in the simulated data.

Note that in the previous two tasks, the signal and background were both drawn from the same dataset. In Task 2 however, they are drawn from different sets. As a result there is an imbalance with the signal sample having a higher track multiplicity due to the SUSY particles decaying into jets.

The result after training on the evaluation data can be seen in Figure 5. A high background rejection (a factor ~ 100) can be seen up to a signal efficiency of about 50 percent.

The problem setting in task 2 is the most relevant for a fully implemented algorithm. The output of the classifier could be used as an independent trigger channel, or incorporated into an experiment trigger-menu.

Future studies will be aimed improving the independence of the performance on track multiplicity as this is one of the main discriminants that the algorithm is currently is exploiting. However, it can be noted that as the pileup level is increased, the difference between the signal and background will diminish.

5 Conclusion

This paper investigates the application of Graph Neural Networks towards identifying high-mass displaced vertices from raw detector hits without an explicit track and vertex reconstruction step. The investigation is carried out in three steps of increasing complexity. The first task investigates the applicability of graph networks to characterise displaced events in a trigger environment while the final two tasks investigate, respectively, how the performance of the setup translates to different detection environments, and the performance identifying a specific signal process against a multi-jet background. Examples have been shown of a retained ($\sim 20\%$) signal efficiency in the regime of high background rejection (a factor ~ 100).

Interesting directions for future research include a full time complexity analysis, the network training using proton-proton processes with realistic levels of pileup and simulating a more detailed detector environment.

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Track Reconstruction on Free-Streaming Data for PANDA at FAIR

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ABSTRACT

High event rates of up to 20 MHz and continuous detector readout make the event filtering at PANDA a challenging task. In addition, no hardware-based event selection will be possible due to the similarities between signal and background. Therefore PANDA is among a new generation of experiments utilizing a fully software-based event filtering. Track reconstruction will play a key part in the online filtering at PANDA where it will be used together with the event building.

To ensure the quality of the track reconstruction, the existing quality assurance algorithm has been modified to be able to cope with free streaming data. This proceeding addresses a candidate for online track reconstruction algorithms for free streaming data based *e.g.* on a 4D Cellular Automaton procedure. The quality assurance procedure and the results from the tracking at different event rates and level of event mixing are also presented.

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1 Introduction

At modern particle physics detectors, advanced trigger systems are divided into several levels. Commonly, the first level is a hardware trigger sorting the detector hits into *events*. At a higher level, the data rates are further reduced by a software-based event filter utilizing *e.g.* tracking or Particle IDentification (PID) information. At the upcoming PANDA (antiProton ANnihilations at DArmstadt) experiment [1] at FAIR (Facility for Antiproton and Ion Research), it will not be possible to use a hardware-based event filtering due to the similarities between signal and background. PANDA will utilize a fully software-based event filtering where *e.g.* online track reconstruction will be used for making trigger decisions. This makes PANDA part of a new generation of experiments employing this strategy, such as CBM [2]. Other experiments [3] actively invest in designing fully software-based trigger systems.

Track reconstruction on hits which are pre-sorted in events is referred to as *event-based* track reconstruction. On the other hand, track reconstruction performed on hits sorted in time without being associated to an event is referred to as *time-based* track reconstruction. The online track reconstruction at PANDA will therefore be time-based since there is no hardware trigger.

2 The PANDA Experiment

PANDA offers unique possibilities to explore QCD in the confinement domain where the relevant degrees of freedom for describing the strong interaction are not yet determined. The four physics pillars of PANDA include nucleon structure investigations, hadrons in nuclei, spectroscopy of charm and exotic states as well as strangeness physics.

Antiprotons, delivered by the HESR (High Energy Storage Ring) will impinge on a stationary proton target. The beam momentum will range between 1.5 GeV/c and 15 GeV/c. At the start setup of PANDA, an initial luminosity of $\mathcal{L} \sim 10^{31} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is foreseen with an average interaction rate of ~ 2.0 MHz. At later stages of PANDA, this is planned to increase to $\mathcal{L} \sim 2 \cdot 10^{32} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and an average interaction rate of 20 MHz at 15 GeV/c beam momentum. The earlier stage of PANDA is the focus of this paper. The interaction rate between the antiproton beam and the target will be Poisson distributed. The HESR will be filled to 80% with a 2 000 ns revolution time which leads to an active time of interactions of 1 600 ns and a dead time of 400 ns.

In order to fulfill the physics requirements, the PANDA detector, shown in Fig. 1, is designed to cover an almost full 4π solid angle. It is generally divided into two parts, the barrel shaped target spectrometer which covers the interaction point and the forward spectrometer placed downstream the beam pipe to measure forward going particles. The main distinction between the two parts is the magnetic field; a solenoid field will be present over the barrel spectrometer and a dipole field will be present over the forward spectrometer. Both parts will perform online and offline track reconstruction as well as PID and calorimetry. The central tracking detector at PANDA is the Straw Tube Tracker, which is described in detail Sec. 2.2. The additional detectors mainly dedicated to track reconstruction are: a Micro Vertex Detector based on silicon strip and pixel sensors, planes based on the Gas Electron Multiplier technique and planes consisting of drift tubes in the forward spectrometer.

The official PANDA software, PandaRoot [5] is an extension of FairRoot [6] and is based on the analysis and data processing framework ROOT [7].

2.1 Time Sorted Data

A comparison between the event-based simulation and the time-based simulation is shown in Fig. 2. The first stage, where the Monte Carlo data is generated, is the same in both cases and all data are sorted event-wise. In the event-based simulation, the data are also sorted event-wise in all subsequent stages all the way to the analysis stage. This means that at the reconstruction stage, tracking is done on data already pre-sorted event-wise. However, in the time-based simulation at the digitization stage, the hit data is sorted in time and placed into bursts, *e.g.* 2 000 ns long intervals corresponding to the antiproton beam revolution time. A consequence of this is that the track reconstruction is performed on hits sorted time-wise and events will be

Figure 1: The PANDA detector setup with all sub-detectors highlighted.

mixed as depicted in Fig. 3. The data in the event-based simulation is synchronous from the simulation stage to the analysis stage. In the time-based case, the data is asynchronous with the simulation stage already at the digitization stage and from the reconstruction stage onwards, the data is synchronous.

For the time-based track reconstruction, there are two approaches to adjust the burst intervals in a way so that hits from one track do not end up at the edges of an interval so the track risk being present in more than one burst of data. The first way is to place the cut between the burst in the HESR dead time where there are no interactions. The other way is to cut the bursts where a gap in the hit data is found. For the results in this proceeding, the first approach is used. No special treatment is given to hits close to the burst boundaries.

2.2 The Straw Tube Tracker

The main tracking detector of PANDA is the Straw Tube Tracker (STT) [4]. It consists of 4 224 closely packed single channel readout drift tubes arranged in hexagonal layers. The tubes are placed in 27 radial layers with 19 layers of tubes placed parallel to the beam pipe for xy -reconstruction and eight central layers with tubes tilted by $\pm 3^\circ$ for z -reconstruction. It will cover a radial distance 15-41.8 cm. The STT comprises of single channel read-out drift tubes consisting of aluminum coated Mylar tubes with a diameter of 10 mm and a gold-plated tungsten-rhenium anode wire in the center. The gas inside the tubes will be Argon-based (90%) with carbon dioxide (10%) as a quench gas. When a particle traverses a tube, electrons in the gas are excited. Due to an applied electric field, the electrons start travelling towards the anode wire knocking out more electrons which in turn do the same, giving rise to an avalanche effect.

The time it takes for an electron to reach the wire is called the *drift time*. The maximum drift time is that of the electrons originating close to the tube wall and is about 250 ns. A circle centered around the anode wire and going through the point of closest approach of the particle trajectory to the wire is called the *isochrone*. The isochrones provide valuable information for the tracking since their radii give the distance between the passage of the high energy particle and the tube wire. This leads to the position resolution in the $r\phi$ -plane of $150 \mu\text{m}$. It should also be noted that the isochrone radius can not be measured directly but can be obtained from the pulse shape and a reference time. The resolution of the pulse shape is 1-2 ns on

Figure 2: Comparison between the time-sorted data and the event-sorted data in the different simulation stages.

Figure 3: The time structure of the hits for for event-based data and for time-based data.

average however, the part of the pulse time currently available in the software is dependent on the isochrone radius.

2.2.1 Event Structure in the Straw Tube Tracker

The time between the start of two consecutive events at 2.0 MHz can be seen in panel a) of Fig. 4. The average time is 500 ns and a peak at smaller time differences is observed. The STT is among the slower tracking detectors as compared to, *e.g.* the Micro Vertex Detector, and there will be an overlap of events in the detector, *i.e.* hits from several events will be present in the detector simultaneously. Panel b) and c) of Fig. 4 illustrates the one event in the STT and 40 events respectively. The latter case is around the average number of events expected within one burst at the maximum event rate of 20.0 MHz so it represents the extreme case. It is clear that overlapping events complicates the track reconstruction.

3 4D Cellular Automaton

A Cellular Automaton [10] based clusterization procedure has been implemented in PandaRoot [8, 9]. It utilizes STT information and the procedure is illustrated in Fig. 5. Panel A), illustrates the trajectories of two particles traversing the STT. The tubes which are hit and give a signal are given an index as displayed in panel B). The state of a tube is defined by the number of active neighbors it has, *i.e.* the number of directly

Figure 4: Panel (a) shows the average time between the start of two consecutive events at 2.0 MHz interaction rate. One example event in the STT (b) and 40 events (c) which is around the average number of events at 20.0 MHz.

adjacent tubes which have also given rise to a signal. Tubes with one or two active neighbors are referred to as unambiguous and marked green in panel B). Tubes with three or more neighbors are referred to as ambiguous and marked red. The unambiguous hit tubes are treated first. The index of each tube is set to the lowest of the indices of its neighbors. This is done iteratively until all hits in one cluster of unambiguous hits have the same index and it is the lowest of all indices in the cluster as shown in panel C). The ambiguous hits are given all indices of their neighbors, panel D), and are assigned to an adjacent cluster of unambiguous hits after a track fit has been performed. The track fit is a Riemann paraboloid fit [11, 12]. Mainly the xy-information is used by the Cellular Automaton but methods for utilizing the z-component also exist, see ref. [13]. One advantage of this algorithm is that it does not assume the interaction point as a constraint so it can be used to reconstruct particles originating from displaced vertices.

The Cellular Automaton is well suited for hit level parallelization and a GPU version of the code exist. A speedup of roughly 100 has been achieved on a GeForce GTX 750 Ti GPU as compared to a i7 3.4 GHz processor.

In order to run the algorithm with event mixing, a 4D version of the algorithm has been developed where time-stamps are utilized in addition to the spatial neighbor relations. The time-stamps are included in a straight forward way by using a cut on the time stamps. If two hits which have been spatially clustered together occur closer to each other in time than this cut they are accepted as neighbors but if they occur further apart in time, they are rejected. The cut value can be varied but the default value is 250 ns which corresponds to the maximum drift time of the electrons in the tubes.

Figure 5: The Cellular Automaton procedure. A description is given in the text.

4 Tracking Quality Assurance

The standard quality assurance for tracking in PandaRoot contains all features needed to evaluate the efficiency and assess the quality of the tracking. It gives high level information such as momentum resolutions

and low level information such as the number of true, false and missing hits in each tracking detector. Tracks are divided into six categories according to their hit content, these categories are:

1. **Fully Purely Found:** all hits belonging to the true MC track were found. No impurities from false MC tracks are allowed.
2. **Fully Impurely Found:** all hits belonging to one true MC track were found and impurities are allowed as long as the hits from the true track comprises at least 70% of all hits in the reconstructed track.
3. **Partially Purely Found:** the majority ($> 50\%$) but not all hits in a reconstructed track belong to a true MC track and no impurities of hits from other MC tracks is allowed.
4. **Partially Impurely Found:** impurities are allowed and at least 70% of all hits in the reconstructed track belongs to one true track. Not all hits from the true MC track were found.
5. **Ghost Track:** the reconstructed track does not match a true track. A ghost track appears when the requirement for a single MC track to be reconstructed is not fulfilled or the impurities from false MC tracks exceed 70% of the number of all hits in the reconstructed track.
6. **Clone Track:** one true MC track has been reconstructed more than once. While the *original* reconstructed track is the one with the most hits matching the true track, remaining tracks belonging to the same true track are defined as clones. There is no requirement of shared hits between an original track and its clone.

One track can only belong to one of the categories. The number of tracks in the first four categories make up the number of correctly reconstructed tracks whereas the number of tracks in the last two categories make up the number of incorrectly reconstructed tracks.

In order to compare the reconstructed track to the relevant track set, an ideal track finder exists in PandaRoot. This track finder gives the tracks which can be reconstructed in a certain sub-detector. It is based completely on the ground truth information and the user can decide what hit requirement in the different sub-detectors to use. The resulting tracks are referred to as *ideal tracks* and the realistically reconstructed tracks are compared to the ideally reconstructed tracks for determining the efficiency.

5 Results

Generic background events for $\bar{p}p$ reactions at a beam momentum of 6.2 GeV/c were used for all results in this section. No prior filtering on particle momentum or displaced vertices is performed. The efficiency as a function of the interaction rate is shown in Fig. 6 for both the 3D algorithm (panel a)) and the 4D algorithm (panel b)). The efficiency is calculated as the total number of found tracks over the number of ideal tracks with at least six STT hits. The full efficiency is high and stable for both algorithms over the entire range. For the 3D algorithm the efficiency varies between 89% at 0.5 MHz and 77% at 4.0 MHz. In contrast, the efficiency ranges between 89% at 5.0 MHz and 84% at 4.0 MHz for the 4D algorithm. The efficiencies for all track categories are quite similar at 0.5 MHz for both algorithms. The reason for this is that the level of event mixing is so low that it almost corresponds to the event-based track reconstruction. As the level of event mixing increases, the effect of the timestamp utilization becomes more pronounced.

The clone and ghost rates as functions of the interaction rate are shown in Fig. 6 panel c) for both algorithms. The clone and ghost rates are calculated as the total number of clones or ghosts over the number of ideal tracks with at least six STT hits. The rates are both quite high, especially the clone rate. Both increases with increasing interaction rate due to the increasing level of event mixing. At 0.5 MHz interaction rate, the 3D and 4D algorithm yield similar results. The higher the interaction rate, the more the results diverge from each other and the timestamp utilization greatly helps suppressing both the ghost and clone rate. At 4.0 MHz, the ghost rate is reduced by almost 50% when using timestamps. Since both the clone and ghost rates are high, developments of clone merging and ghost suppression techniques are currently ongoing.

The performance of the part of the tracking obtaining the neighborhood relations was tested and the results can be seen in panel d) of Fig. 6. Due to the increasing number of hits being processed in each data burst with increasing interaction rates, the processing time also increases.

Figure 6: Efficiency vs. the interaction rate for the 3D algorithm (a) and the 4D algorithm (b) as well as the ghost and clone rate vs. the interaction rate for both algorithms (c). The different track categories are included. The processing time per data burst is shown in panel d).

Figure 7: Efficiency vs. the time-cut (a) and the fake rate vs. the time-cut (b). The different track categories are included.

The effect of varying the time-cut was also investigated, the results can be seen in Fig. 7 for the efficiency (panel a)) and the clone and ghost rate (panel b)). The time-cut is varied between 50 ns and 500 ns. When tightening the time-cut, the total efficiency decreases. The efficiency is stable in the region between 100 and 500 ns time cut and the sub-categories of correctly found tracks are stable within the range 250 to 500 ns time cut. The number of fully purely found tracks rapidly decreases for time cuts lower than 250 ns whereas the number of partially pure tracks increases. This indicates that true hits are rejected even at time cuts slightly lower than 250 ns. The most dramatic effect of tightening the time-cut can be seen in the clone category (blue line, panel b)). A clone rate around 1.5 is observed at larger values of the time-cut and this is reduced to almost 0.5 at a 50 ns time-cut.

6 Conclusions

A 4D Cellular Automaton based hit clusterization procedure is available for PANDA. This track finder can be used for tracking particles originating from displaced vertices. The hit clusterization can assume time-based hit data and first results are promising. The efficiency is high, 84-89%, over the range of interaction rates of 0.5-4.0 MHz. The time-stamp utilization helps to suppress the clone and ghost rate as well as keeping the efficiency stable over the relevant range of interaction rates. During the online data taking at PANDA, this might be run together with a primary track finder.

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Low- p_T tracking for ATLAS in nominal LHC pileup conditions

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ABSTRACT

In the most recent years of data-taking with the ATLAS detector at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), the minimum transverse momentum (p_T) of default track reconstruction was 500 MeV. This bound was set to reduce the event reconstruction time and to save disk space, which are challenges in high pileup environments. However, most proton-proton collisions at the LHC result in a large number of soft particles, and the reconstruction of these soft particles in high pileup conditions can provide important information for many analyses. This note explains a method of tracking in high pileup conditions where low- p_T tracks are reconstructed in a second tracking pass after the default tracking is performed. In order to prevent a large increase in the per-event reconstruction time, tracks with p_T below 500 MeV are only reconstructed within a “region of interest”, which is defined event-by-event. Examples of applications for this technique are searches for photon-induced physics at the LHC, charm tagging, and SUSY searches.

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1 Introduction

In an average proton-proton (pp) interaction with center-of-mass energy of $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) [1], more than half of the charged particles produced have a momentum transverse to the beamline (p_T) of less than 500 MeV [2]. The production of such low- p_T particles involves momentum transfers (q^2) in the non-perturbative regime of Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD), making the prediction of distributions associated with such particles difficult, including their multiplicity and p_T . However, by the same principle of asymptotic freedom in QCD, a high- q^2 interaction between partons within the colliding protons can be treated as decoupled from the low- q^2 physics associated with the interactions between the remnants of the protons, which is called the underlying event (UE). Because of this, experiments which focus on the study of high energy phenomena at the LHC, such as ATLAS [3], optimize their instrumentation and algorithms for the reconstruction of particles with p_T typically of order ≥ 1 GeV rather than 0.1 GeV. In most analyses, particles with $p_T < 500$ MeV are not relevant, so for the most recent years of data-taking with ATLAS, the minimum reconstructed track p_T allowed was 500 MeV. Having this threshold reduces the time taken by the reconstruction algorithm and reduces the storage space required for analyzed events. However, there are many analyses in ATLAS that can benefit from the reconstruction of low- p_T particles; for example, searches for photon-induced physics can use better UE reconstruction to isolate events of interest, and charm-tagging and some SUSY searches use low- p_T particles in reconstructing particle decays that proceed through small mass differences.

Crucially, most analyses that can benefit from the use of low- p_T tracking need to use the bulk of ATLAS data, which in Run 2 averaged more than 30 pp interactions per bunch crossing (“nominal pileup”). There have been analyses in ATLAS looking at low- p_T physics in the past, such as [2]; however, these studies are performed with specialized beam conditions that make crossings with more than 1 pp collision very rare, rendering the integrated luminosity of these runs very small ($151 \mu\text{b}^{-1}$ in [2], compared to 140fb^{-1} collected in Run 2). Because of these special conditions, the normal restrictions due to event reconstruction time and storage space are avoided.

In this note, an algorithm for the reconstruction of low- p_T tracks designed to be used in nominal LHC pileup conditions is presented. The performance of the algorithm is explored in detail, and potential means of improvement are investigated.

2 Tracking in ATLAS

Tracking in ATLAS is performed as follows [5]:

1. Create “seeds” from space points in 3 different layers (either 3 pixel hits [6, 7] or 3 semiconductor tracker (SCT) hits [8], potentially with extra confirmation hits).
2. Extend seeds through additional layers using a Kalman filter to create “candidates”.
3. Perform ambiguity solving on candidates to create final tracks, with the goal of reconstructing exactly 1 track per particle.

Certain restrictions are placed on the number of hits that must be used to make a track, on the number of hits missing where expected along a track, and on the amount of hit sharing between tracks. Nominally, the seeds must have a predicted p_T greater than 500 MeV, where the predicted p_T is determined by interpolating a curve between the hits that comprise the seed, corresponding to the momentum-dependent curvature of a charged particle in a magnetic field. In the study performed in [2], this algorithm was adjusted to allow tracks down to 100 MeV, but otherwise the steps involved were the same.

When considering high- p_T particles alone, seed finding is a question of finding three hits that form a line in space (or small deviations from a line), as high- p_T particles curve relatively little. As tracks with lower and lower p_T are allowed, an increasing number of hit combinations must be considered, as more significantly non-linear sets of hits may have been caused by a curving charged particle. This is problematic in nominal LHC pileup conditions, because a large number of hits are created on the active components of the ATLAS inner detector (ID) [3, 7] in each bunch crossing.

In order to alleviate this combinatorics problem, the new algorithm for low- p_T tracking involves two stages. First, the default tracking algorithm is run as described above with a minimum track p_T threshold of 500 MeV. The detector hits used by these tracks are then removed from consideration, and the track reconstruction algorithm is run again on the remaining hits, where seeds with a predicted p_T down to 100 MeV are accepted and the hit requirements for final tracks are slightly relaxed.

In addition to the two-pass tracking setup, a “region of interest” (RoI) for tracking has been implemented to reduce the reconstruction combinatorics problem. The RoI is a region of set distance longitudinally along the beamline centered around a location of interest to the analysis. This center can be set either based on reconstructed objects, such as leptons or jets, or based on the location of some truth-level collision of interest in a simulated sample. In the second low- p_T tracking step, seeds are found iteratively and rejected if their longitudinal beamline projection falls outside of the RoI. Seeds that are accepted are then potentially extended into candidates and eventually finalized tracks. The size of the RoI is adjustable, and determining what value to use will be discussed below.

To guide the determination of the RoI size and to evaluate the algorithm’s performance overall, three metrics are used:

- Efficiency of reconstructing truth-level charged particles (with matching as defined in [5]):

$$\text{Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Number of charged particles with at least one matched track}}{\text{Number of charged particles}}. \quad (1)$$

- Fake rate, as shown in Eq. (2), where a fake track is one constructed from detector hits created by multiple different charged particles, which is to say that it does not correspond to any truth level object’s trajectory. A more exhaustive explanation of the metric used to determine a fake track is given in Sec. 6 in the context of seeds; the arguments there generalize to tracks.

$$\text{Fake rate} = \frac{\text{Number of fake tracks}}{\text{Number of tracks}}. \quad (2)$$

- Impact on the reconstruction time.

The following study was performed on a Powheg+Pythia8 [9, 10] Z boson sample, where the Z boson was forced to decay to two muons with invariant mass between 60 and 110 GeV. The sample had a charged particle filter applied, such that there were fewer than 12 truth particles with $p_T > 500$ MeV and $\eta < 2.5$ originating from the Z boson-producing interaction. The pileup conditions of the sample approximate those of data taking at the LHC from 2015 to 2018. In this study, the RoI center for each event is set based on the truth-level muon information.

3 Setting the RoI size

Figure 1 illustrates the above performance metrics in the context of determining an RoI size. The top half of Figure 1a shows the efficiency as a function of the RoI size for hard-scatter tracks in a simulated sample, and the bottom half of that plot shows the fake rate for tracks near the hard-scatter interaction location. Similarly, Figure 1b shows the impact on the reconstruction time. By considering Figure 1, the following conclusions are reached:

- A small RoI (< 10 mm) is fast but has lower efficiency and high fake rate.
- A large RoI (> 100 mm) has low fake rate, has generally lower efficiency, and is time intensive.
- A medium RoI size (around 30 mm) has close to maximal efficiency, at the cost of medium fake rate and a moderate impact on the reconstruction time.

Because of this, 30 mm is chosen for the RoI size parameter of the algorithm, though it can be adjusted at run time. To some extent, the size of the RoI is driven by the fact that seeds have much poorer pointing resolution than tracks. Though tracks typically have a resolution better than $\mathcal{O}(1)$ mm, using a too small RoI results in lost efficiency, as seeds rejected due to pointing outside the RoI may end up being extended into tracks that would point into the RoI.

Figure 1: (a) Tracking efficiency and fake rate as a function of the Region of Interest (RoI) size for two different truth particle or track p_T ranges. Only truth particles originating from the hard-scatter interaction are considered for the tracking efficiency, and only tracks pointing to the hard-scatter interaction location within 1 mm longitudinally along the beamline and with a transverse displacement from the beamline of less than 1 mm are considered for the fake rate. (b) Impact of RoI size choices on the reconstruction time. The black squares show the fractional increase in the total reconstruction time over the default setup. The blue triangles show the fractional increase in the tracking time alone, where the tracking time is defined as the time spent in both the default tracking pass and in the low- p_T track pass [4].

4 Efficiency and fake rate

Figure 2 shows the efficiency and fake rate now as a function of $p_{T, \text{truth}}$ and $p_{T, \text{track}}$, respectively. In Figure 2a, the efficiency is also shown for default-tracking alone. It can be seen that the low- p_T tracking algorithm gives a smooth and gently decreasing efficiency as $p_{T, \text{truth}}$ decreases down to about 200 MeV. In the very low- $p_{T, \text{truth}}$ regime below 200 MeV, the efficiency falls off quickly. The fake rate stays below 10% down to $p_{T, \text{track}}$ of 250 MeV. The fake rate increases quickly in the very low- $p_{T, \text{track}}$, where approximately one out of three tracks are expected to be fake.

The natural question that is raised then is how to improve the efficiency and/or decrease the fake rate. Given the structure of the ATLAS track reconstruction algorithm, to increase the efficiency one would naturally want to create more seeds or else to accept more candidates. Alternatively, to decrease the fake rate, one would prefer fewer seeds or perhaps to accept fewer candidates. To investigate what avenues of improvement are most promising, let's examine where in the reconstruction process efficiency is being lost and the general quality of the seeds being created.

Figure 2: (a) Tracking efficiency as a function of the truth particle p_T . The black line indicates the efficiency when default tracking alone is run, and the blue points indicate the efficiency when both default and low- p_T trackings are run. The truth particles considered here originate from the hard-scatter interaction. (b) Fake rate as a function of the reconstructed track p_T , where the tracks are restricted to point near the hard-scatter interaction location. The reconstructed tracks considered here have to point to within 1 mm of the hard-scatter interaction longitudinally along the beamline and be displaced from the beamline by less than 1 mm in the transverse direction. Both default and low- p_T tracks are included when considering fake rate [4].

5 Where is efficiency lost?

Figure 3 shows the seed efficiency, candidate efficiency, and the previously shown track efficiency as a function of $p_{T, \text{truth}}$. The definitions for seed efficiency and candidate efficiency are the same as that in Eq. (1), but with “matched seed” and “matched candidate” respectively instead of “matched track”. Matching here is a question of which truth particle contributed the most energy to the hits comprising the seed/candidate/track [5]. It can be seen that consistently across almost all $p_{T, \text{truth}}$ values, over 90% of truth particles have at least one matched seed, and that above about 200 MeV, typically less than half of the seed-to-track efficiency loss occurs in the seed-to-candidate stage. In the very low- $p_{T, \text{truth}}$ regime, the drop in seed-to-candidate efficiency is more dramatic. Given that such a high fraction of truth particles have at least one matched seed, does that mean that the efficiency can be improved simply by accepting a higher fraction of seeds? And why is the very low- $p_{T, \text{truth}}$ efficiency drop between seed and candidate efficiency so dramatic? Answering these questions requires an investigation of the seed quality.

6 Seed quality

The primary metric for understanding the seed quality is the “truth match probability”. This is the weighted fraction of hits on a track created by the truth particle to which the seed is matched, where pixel hits receive a higher weight than SCT hits. Seeds are formed from 3 pixel hits or 3 SCT hits, though occasionally extra confirmation hits are used, typically resulting in a seed with 4 or 5 SCT hits. If all 3 hits on a seed are from the same truth particle, the match probability will be 3/3 or 1. If all three hits on the seed are caused by different truth particles, the match probability will be 1/3 or 0.333. This latter case is considered a fake seed as it is comprised of a random collection of hits. A seed is considered “fake” if the match probability

Figure 3: Efficiency for the three steps of ATLAS tracking as a function of the truth particle p_T . Seed efficiency (red diamonds) is defined here as the likelihood for a stable, charged truth particle within tracking acceptance to have at least one matched seed. Candidate efficiency (blue triangles) and track efficiency (black squares) are defined analogously for candidates and tracks respectively. The truth particles considered here originate from the hard-scatter interaction [4].

is less than 0.5.

Figure 4 shows the proportion of good and fake seeds as a function of the predicted $p_{T,seed}$. In the very low- $p_{T,seed}$ regime, almost half of the seeds are fake. This calls into question the idea of simply “accepting more seeds” to improve the efficiency. If the seed is fake, one cannot expect it to be extended through additional hits to make a candidate, which could explain the large seed-to-candidate efficiency drop. Given the high fake rate, loosening selection criteria would likely lead to a large increase in fake rate rather than a gain in efficiency.

7 Reducing the fake rate

Whereas increasing the efficiency requires creating additional seeds or loosening criteria, decreasing the fake rate is a matter of tightening seed-to-candidate-to-track selections. In order not to suffer a large loss in efficiency by doing this, one must start out with an adequate number of seeds per track. Figure 5a shows the difference in z_0 between low- p_T seeds and tracks, where both the seed and track are matched to the same truth particle. While the fake seeds can point almost anywhere, low- p_T tracks typically have about two good seeds pointing within 5 mm along the beamline. Figure 5b shows the average number of seeds per track as a function the p_T of the truth particle to which both are matched, where the seeds must have z_0 within 5 mm of their track. For truth particles that have a track, there are typically about two good pointing seeds per track regardless of $p_{T,truth}$. This suggests that there might be some redundancy allowing for tightened selection criteria in the tracking algorithm.

Increasing the efficiency for very low- p_T tracks will be difficult; there is a large combinatorial background such that almost half of the seeds are comprised of hits of random origin. An increase in efficiency will come at a high cost in fake rate. However, reducing the fake rate without a drastic loss of efficiency might be possible by tightening seed or track selection criteria. One option is to do this at reconstruction level, which would likely have the added benefit of reducing the reconstruction time. In order not to throw out any information though, this could also be done offline at track level. For example, there could be a set of track selections based on p_T , η , number of pixel hits, number of SCT hits, or number of holes. Any reduction

Figure 4: Seed composition as a function of the seed p_T , where the seed p_T is an estimate from the 3 (or more) hits that comprise the seed. The seeds considered for this plot are required to point to within 5 mm of the hard-scatter interaction longitudinally along the beamline and to have a transverse displacement of less than 2 mm. The blue region shows the fraction of seeds where the truth matching probability is greater than 0.5 (“good”), and the red area shows the fraction of seeds where the truth matching probability is less than 0.5 (“fake”) [4].

in fake rate will come with a loss of efficiency, but the appropriate balance of efficiency and fake rate is a somewhat analysis-specific question.

8 Conclusions

Low- p_T tracking can be a useful tool for many analyses, and the algorithm presented in this note can extend tracking down to about 200 MeV in nominal LHC pileup conditions with relatively high efficiency and low fake rate. In the very low- p_T regime below 200 MeV, the efficiency tends to be low and the fake rate high, but some tightening of selection criteria for seeds or tracks can likely alleviate the fake rate at least. The working point presented increases the track reconstruction time by 300% and the total event reconstruction time by 100%. Therefore, this would not be viable to run on all events but is acceptable for pre-selected events passing initial analysis cuts, which is a typical use case. The algorithm is currently neither intended to be used for a full reprocessing of data nor to be run by default on all ATLAS simulation analyses.

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Figure 5: (a) Distribution of the absolute difference in longitudinal distance along the beamline (z_0) of seeds and tracks created in the low- p_T tracking pass, where both the seed and track are matched to the same truth particle. The blue region shows “good” seeds, and the red area shows “fake” seeds. This is a stacked plot; the y-axis represents the average number of matched seeds per track for a given track-seed position difference. (b) Average number of seeds created in the low- p_T tracking pass per track, where both the seed and track are matched to the same truth particle, as a function of the p_T of the truth particle to which both are matched. The seeds are required to be within 5 mm of their track longitudinally along the beamline and to have a transverse displacement from the beamline of less than 2 mm. The blue region shows “good” seeds, and the red area shows “fake” seeds [4].

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A Quantum Graph Neural Network Approach to Particle Track Reconstruction

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ABSTRACT

Unprecedented increase of complexity and scale of data is expected in computation necessary for tracking detectors of the High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) experiments. While currently used Kalman filter based algorithms are reaching their limits in terms of ambiguities from increasing number of simultaneous collisions, occupancy, and scalability (worse than quadratic), a variety of machine learning approaches to particle track reconstruction are explored. It has been demonstrated previously by HEP.TrkX using TrackML datasets, that graph neural networks, by processing events as a graph connecting track measurements can provide a promising solution by reducing the combinatorial background to a manageable amount and are scaling to a computationally reasonable size. In previous work, we have shown a first attempt of Quantum Computing to Graph Neural Networks for track reconstruction of particles. We aim to leverage the capability of quantum computing to evaluate a very large number of states simultaneously and thus to effectively search a large parameter space. As the next step in this paper, we present an improved model with an iterative approach to overcome the low accuracy convergence of the initial oversimplified Tree Tensor Network (TTN) model.

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1 Introduction

Particle track reconstruction is a common problem in most particle physics experiments. At collider experiments, particles are accelerated to speeds very close the speed of light and collide in bunches at rates of $\mathcal{O}(10MHz)$. In each collision, new particles are created and they scatter in all directions. These particles pass through particle tracking detectors and create signals which are called *hits*. Particle tracking algorithms aims to distinguish these signals and identify the trajectory of the particles.

CERN created the kaggle TrackML challenge in 2018 to invite researchers from all backgrounds to solve the particle track reconstruction problem [1]. Later, the simulated dataset created for the challenge became popular among researchers to test and benchmark new ideas in the field.

In a few years, the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) at CERN will be upgraded to become the High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC). This upgrade, which will ramp up the rate of collisions, comes with many challenges, one of which is the particle track reconstruction problem [2]. Although, the novel particle tracking algorithms can manage the current rate of collision rates, they suffer from higher collision rates as they scale worse than polynomially. Therefore, the search for faster particle track reconstruction algorithms is very important.

There are many initiatives to bring faster solutions to particle track reconstruction. Researchers in the field explore novel methods such as Machine Learning and Quantum Computing. The HepTrkX team proposed a Graph Neural Network (GNN) approach to solve the particle track reconstruction problem using the kaggle TrackML challenge dataset [3]. Other researchers also proposed new methods using Quantum Annealing to tackle the challenge [4].

In this work, we present our updated results on the Quantum Graph Neural Network approach, which combines the novel GNN method of the HepTrkX project with the quantum circuit model [5].

2 The Dataset and Classical Approach

This work uses the publicly available TrackML dataset [1]. The dataset contains spatial coordinates of each hit created by particles which are created during simulated collisions. Each of these collisions are called as events and the dataset contains 10000 event files. Among these files only 100 events are used due to restrictions in simulation times. Quantum Circuit simulations on both CPU and GPU use extensive resources and time as the number of qubits increase. In the case of our model, it takes around a week of CPU time to train the model over 100 events for a single epoch.

The TrackML data is created using a simulated detector having a similar geometry to most LHC experiments. The detector has horizontal (barrel) layers near the center of collisions and vertical (endcap) layers outside. The particle beams propagate along the z -axis and collide around $z = 0$. The TrackML detector layout can be seen in Figure 1. The produced particles of these collisions scatter through all directions. This work only uses the barrel region hits to simplify the track reconstruction problem as the ambiguity of the tracks is much higher for endcap hits.

The HepTrkX GNN approach converts the dataset consisting of spatial coordinates of hits to a graph dataset. A set of loose selection criteria is applied to each hit in order to eliminate illogical connections in the graph. This is way, it is ensured that the preprocessing step takes a very short amount of time and graphs are not fully connected in order to minimize run time. The selection criteria determined by the HepTrkX team is respected in this work and can be seen in Table 1 [3].

Table 1: Selection applied to TrackML dataset for preprocessing.

$ p_T $	$> 1GeV$
$\Delta\phi$	< 0.0006
z_0	$< 100mm$
η	$[-5, 5]$

Figure 1: TrackML Detector Layout [1].

The coordinate definitions used to describe the data is as follows. ϕ is the angle along the transverse plane (xy plane) and $|p_T|$ is the magnitude of momentum along the same plane. η is the pseudorapidity measures the azimuthal angle with respect to the beam axis (z -axis).

An event contains $\sim 8k$ hits, therefore the model requires a huge amounts of memory to load a single event. As the detector geometry is cylindrically symmetric along the ϕ and the z direction, the data set is divided into 8 in the ϕ and into 2 in the z direction to reduce the size of each event. Therefore, the new graph dataset contains 1600 subgraphs of originated from 100 events.

An example subgraph can be seen in Figure 2 and the distribution of the subgraphs for each coordinate variable, in Figure 3. The distribution of r and z can easily be explained by referring to the geometry of the detector in Figure 1. The distribution in ϕ is uniform as expected since the geometry is symmetric along the transverse plane.

Figure 2: 1 of 16 subgraphs created from a single event. (a,b) are subgraphs in cylindrical coordinates and (c) is a subgraph in Cartesian coordinates. Red represents Ground Truth, while Blue shows Fake edges created using loose cuts.

3 The Quantum Graph Neural Network Approach

Quantum circuits have been previously shown to be able to handle classification tasks previously [8, 9]. Although, Quantum Machine Learning has not yet been shown to outperform classical Machine Learning, scientist are trying new methods achieve speed-ups for certain tasks. High Energy Physics is no exception to this trend [7]. In this work, we explore the use of Quantum Circuits to perform track segmentation.

Figure 3: Histogram of hits crated using 1600 subgraphs in cylindrical coordinates.

In order to integrate Quantum Computing and GNNs, the Neural Networks of Edge and Node Network have been replaced by two Quantum Circuits. The new model flow can be seen in Figure 4. There are many Quantum Circuits that perform binary classification tasks in the literature [8, 9]. The Tree Tensor Network (TTN) model is chosen due to its simplicity among these circuits. The TTN circuits are implemented using PennyLane along with its Tensorflow interface. PennyLane provides the necessary gradients of the Quantum Circuits during the training step while Tensorflow is used for optimization and constructing the model pipeline [6, 10].

Figure 4: The Quantum Graph Neural Network model used in this work.

The new hybrid model, which is called the Quantum Graph Neural Network (QGNN) takes a graph as an input. The model begins with an Input Layer, which is a single layer Neural Network used to increase the dimension of the input and increases the dimension of the data to the required number from 3. 3 is the original size of the input as there are 3 spatial coordinates for each hit. Then a Quantum Edge Network (QEN) is applied to each edge of the input graph which outputs an edge feature. The output edge feature is passed into each edge to update their value. This information is used by the Quantum Node Network (QNoN), which is applied to each node of the graph. The output of the QNoN is used to update nodes in the hidden layers. Recursive iterations of Edge and Node Networks allow the information to propagate from lower detector layers to above layers. Finally, a QEN is applied to obtain the final segment classification. The use of TTN inside QEN and QNoN is almost identical except the amount of qubits used. QEN is applied to each edge one by one, therefore the size of input is 6 (amount of spatial coordinates for 2 nodes) in the case of no hidden dimensions. These coordinates are mapped to $[0, 2\pi]$. Then, the $R_y(\theta)$ gate is used encode the information to each qubit. The encoding can be represented with the simple equation below.

$$R_y(\theta) |0\rangle = \cos(\theta/2) |0\rangle + \sin(\theta/2) |1\rangle \quad (1)$$

The TTN circuit is applied afterwards and a measurement is taken. To perform a simple state tomography on the output qubit, the process is repeated many times and the expectation value is calculated. This value is used as the edge feature. By applying the QEN to each edge, the edge features for all edges are calculated. The same process is repeated for the QNoN case. The only difference between the QEN and the QNoN is the size of the circuit and the inputs being nodes, rather than the edges. At the final step of the QGNN, edge features for all initial edges are obtained. These values are used to calculate a weighted binary cross entropy loss taking into account the ratio of the true edges to the false edges. Then the ADAM optimizer of the Tensorflow is used to update the variables of the TTN circuits of both QEN and QNoN. In this work, the QGNN model with the Quantum Circuits of QEN and QNoN used shown in Figure 5 is used with one hidden dimension.

Figure 5: Quantum Circuit of QEN is given on the left. Quantum Circuit of QNoN is given on the right. The numerical values are from an example data.

1400 subgraphs are used to train the QGNN and 200 subgraphs are used in the validation set for a single epoch. 3 independent experiments were conducted to test different iterations. The training results are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 shows that the model can achieve an Area under the ROC curve (AUC) of 0.80 and a binary cross entropy loss of 0.5. While 1.0 is the perfect score for AUC, the model seems to perform well considering its simplicity. It was expected that the model performance to get better as the number of iterations increases. However, higher iteration runs performed similar to $N_{it} = 1$ or even worse. There are two main reasons leading to this. First, simple TTN models do not represent the data more than the current best results, therefore it defines a less than perfect ending point for the training. The second issue is related to the vanishing gradient problem. It is known that Recurrent Neural Networks suffer from this problem and the QGNN is no exception. Therefore, as the N_{it} increases the learning rate slows down. These two major issues will be investigated deeply in future work.

Figure 6: Validation Set results for a single epoch of training with different iteration values.

4 Future Work

The work presented here is the first full demonstration of a Quantum Graph Neural Network that can classify track segments with good precision and accuracy. There is a need for more detailed work to further increase the performance of the model. Future work should include the following;

- Extending the size of the hidden dimension, which was limited to 1 in this work.
- A detailed analysis of the vanishing gradient problem.
- Trying different Quantum Circuit architectures to achieve better accuracy.

5 Conclusions

This work presents a first implementation of a Quantum Graph Neural Network dedicated for solving track reconstruction problem. Although the presented model uses the simplest form of Quantum Circuits in literature and the minimum number of qubits that can be used, it performs well. Current results show that a simple QGNN model performs very similar to sophisticated track reconstruction models. However, there is still more to be done to achieve this. It is also important to note that this work currently only uses simulations and does not consider practical applicability or possible speed-ups.

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Exploring (Quantum) Track Reconstruction Algorithms for non-HEP applications

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ABSTRACT

An increase in simultaneous collisions is expected creating a challenge for accurate particle track reconstruction in High Luminosity LHC experiments. Similar challenges can be seen in non-HEP trajectory reconstruction use-cases, where tracking and track evaluation algorithms are used. High occupancy, track density, complexity and fast growth therefore exponentially increase the demand of algorithms in terms of time, memory and computing resources. While traditionally Kalman filter (or even simpler algorithms) are used, they are expected to scale worse than quadratically and thus strongly increasing the total processing time. Graph Neural Networks (GNN) are currently explored for HEP, but also non-HEP trajectory reconstruction applications. Quantum Computers with their feature of evaluating a very large number of states simultaneously are therefore good candidates for such complex searches in large parameter and graph spaces. In this paper we present our work on implementing a quantum-based graph tracking machine learning algorithm to evaluate Traffic collision avoidance system (TCAS) probabilities of commercial flights.

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1 Introduction

While conventional machine learning techniques have the ability to deal with today’s generated amount of data succinctly, it is interesting to explore if novel techniques such as quantum computing have the possibility to outperform existing techniques. This possibility and the analogy between track reconstruction in particle physics and aviation has led to a collaboration between researchers at gluoNNet, CERN openlab, Middle East Technical University Ankara, Caltech and DESY. There are striking similarities between particle track reconstruction and tracking of air plane routes. In both cases, there is a huge increase of the amount of data expected, in particle physics during the upcoming High Luminosity run of the LHC [1], in aviation due to the use of ADS-B [2] emitters and an expected explosion in the use of drones. Particular similarities between particle physics and aviation are for instance the detector hit and the broadcasted timestamp of the airplane as both include position and time information. In this scenario, particles correspond to airplanes, an event Id in physics to an airplane’s transponder Id and the particle Id’s to the aircraft type. Track reconstruction of airplanes has in this study two major aims: understanding incidents and understanding triggers of a deviation from their own flight path compared to the optimal route. As a next step, these tracking algorithms could be applied to online data for predicting flight paths based on the available data. These predictions could be used for optimisation of airport capacities for starting and landing and for improving flight safety, leading to a better prediction of emergency situations and an earlier warning than the Traffic Collision Avoidance System (TCAS) currently provides.

2 Dataset

The dataset used in this study contains the CAT 21 information [3] related to civilian aircraft usages, covers the month of April 2019 and has been kindly provided by Aireon [4] and the Irish Aviation Authority [5]. It covers a month’s worth of data that correspond to 500 GB, which is relatively small compared to data sets used in high energy physics. At the moment, not every aircraft is equipped with an ADS-B device broadcasting information to the ground station. The dataset includes information such as the unique aircraft identifier and its position in degrees. The aircraft’s position broadcasted in degrees of Longitude and Latitude is used in this study as well as the geometric height defined as the projected height to the earth’s ellipsoid in WGS-84 coordinates [3]. There are three additional parameters relevant for the analysis, which are the type and weight-class of the aircraft referred to as emitter category as well as the aircraft’s flight number. However, the latter is only available if it is known prior to departure and computed in the aircraft’s onboard computer. The Quantum Graph Neural Network (QGNN) uses this information for the reconstruction of the aircraft’s flight path.

3 Quantum Graph Network

Figure 1: Structure of iterative application of the Quantum Node Network and Quantum Edge Network. Pictures taken from [8].

The underlying classical graph neural network (GNN) from [6] consists of an edge neural network and a node neural network and are applied iteratively after each other. In this work, both edge network and node network have been rewritten as quantum circuits via Tensor Tree Networks (TTN). These are chosen for simplicity and implemented using PennyLane [7] providing the necessary gradients of the Quantum circuits during the training. The Tensorflow interface is used for optimisation and constructing the model pipeline [9].

Figure 2: Quantum Node Network (a) and Quantum Edge Network (b) are composed of Tensor Tree Networks (TTN). The underlying TTNs differ in the amount of qubits. 6 qubits are used to cover two sets of three spatial coordinates corresponding to two edges. The hidden features correspond to classical neural network layers. The obtained output of the Quantum Edge Network serves as input for the Quantum Node Network. Numerical values are example values. Pictures taken from [8].

The graph data consists of the timestamp, and the graph matrices indicate the relation between the different emitter Id's. A graph contains information about the relation of two spatial points, which are in total 6 coordinates. The graph data set is then ingested into an Input layer network - a single layer neural network - to increase the dimension of the input. This is necessary to obtain the number matching to the three spatial coordinates. Then, the graph data serve as the input of the hybrid Quantum Graph Neural Network (QGNN) consisting of Quantum Edge Network and Quantum Node Network that are applied iteratively and visualised in Figure 1.

3.1 Quantum Edge Network and Quantum Node Network

The Quantum Edge Network (QEN) consisting of 6 qubits is applied to each graph containing information of two edges described by two times three spatial coordinates. The output edge feature is passed into every edge to update their values. Their coordinates are then mapped in the physics case to $[0, 2\pi]$, whereas in the case of aircrafts their broadcasted position in Longitude and Latitude is used. This output is ingested into the Quantum Node Network (QNoN) and applied to each node of the graph for updating the hidden layers. The QNoN is applied to all possible neighbours that might be connected through the available edges. Both network architectures are visualised in Figure 2.

3.2 Tensor Tree Network

The TTN of the QEN differs from the TTN used for QNoN in the amount of qubits. There are 6 qubits in case of the QEN and each qubit corresponds to one spatial parameter. Additionally, there are two qubits representing hidden layers corresponding to classical neural network layers. $R_y(\theta)$, the rotation gate for performing around the Y axis of the Bloch sphere is then applied to encode the information of the spatial coordinates into the qubit.

$$R_y(\theta) |\theta\rangle = \cos(\theta/2) |0\rangle + \sin(\theta/2) |1\rangle \quad (1)$$

In case of the QEN, a measurement of one qubit is taken as displayed in Figure 2. For calculating the expectation value, the results of multiple measurements are then taken into account. This outcome is then the new input for the Edge feature. The same procedure is applied in case of the QNoN. For optimisation purposes of the variable in the TTNs in both QEN and QNoN, Tensorflow's ADAM optimiser [9] is used. The ADAM optimiser is a stochastic gradient descent method based on adaptive estimates for lower-order measurements [10].

4 Conclusions

This quantum computing simulation represents the initial stage of a track reconstruction algorithm that could be used in aviation for the purpose of improving the Traffic collision avoidance system (TCAS). Analogous simulations in particle physics show that this model performs well [8]. Further developments of the model and circuit are needed as this case only represents a static and a procedural case. The applicability of such a QGNN does not yet outperform available classical approaches due to the limited access to real quantum computers.

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Parallelizing the Unpacking and Clustering of Detector Data for Reconstruction of Charged Particle Tracks on Multi-core CPUs and Many-core GPUs

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ABSTRACT

We present results from parallelizing the unpacking and clustering steps of the raw data from the silicon strip modules for reconstruction of charged particle tracks. Throughput is further improved by concurrently processing multiple events using nested OpenMP parallelism on CPU or CUDA streams on GPU. The new implementation along with earlier work in developing a parallelized and vectorized implementation of the combinatoric Kalman filter algorithm has enabled efficient global reconstruction of the entire event on modern computer architectures. We demonstrate the performance of the new implementation on Intel Xeon and NVIDIA GPU architectures.

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1 Introduction

The reconstruction of charged particle trajectories (tracking) is a pivotal element of the reconstruction chain in Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) [1] as it measures the direction and momentum of charged particles, which is then also used as input for nearly all high-level reconstruction algorithms: vertex reconstruction, b-tagging, lepton reconstruction, jet isolation and missing transverse momentum reconstruction. Tracking by far is the most time consuming step of event construction and its time scales poorly with the detector occupancy. This brings a computing challenge to the upcoming upgrade of the accelerator from the Large Hadron Collider (HLC) to the High-Luminosity LHC (HL-HLC) where the instantaneous luminosity will increase by an order of magnitude due to the increased number of overlapping proton-proton collisions.

To address this challenge, the parallel Kalman filter tracking project MKFIT was established in 2014 with the goal of enabling efficient tracking on modern computing architectures. Over the last 6 years, we have made significant progress towards developing a parallelized and vectorized implementation of the combinatoric Kalman filter algorithm for tracking [2, 3, 4, 5]. This allows the efficient global reconstruction of the entire event within the projected online CPU budget. This also opens the possibility of deploying MKFIT into the CMS High Level Trigger (HLT), where the performance requirements are particularly strict. The current goal is to test the algorithm online in Run 3 of the LHC.

Global reconstruction necessarily entails the unpacking and clustering of the hit information from all silicon strip tracker modules before the hits are processed by MKFIT. The current CMS HLT, on the other hand, performs hit and track reconstruction on demand, i.e., only for software-selected regions of the detector. Therefore, we have recently begun to investigate how to implement the unpacking and clustering steps efficiently for the entire detector at once. This document highlights the latest development in enabling parallelization of unpacking and clustering on modern computing architectures. We start from a standalone version of the unpacker, which uses simulated raw data and calibration data, along with simplified versions of many related CMSSW classes.

2 Parallelization

The CMS strip tracker data are organized by Front End Drivers (FEDs). Each FED consists of 96 optical channels with 256 strips per channel [6]. In every CMS event, only the strips that are measured to be above a threshold are recorded. In zero suppression mode, the measured signal within a FED is stored like a variant of compressed sparse row (CSR) format, where the channel and strip numbers correspond to the row and column numbers (Figure 1). Besides the event-based strip tracker data, pre-measured calibration data, e.g., gain and noise values for each strip, must also be unpacked by FED channels.

Figure 1: Raw data format from CMS strip tracker

Data layout is paramount to performance, and therefore we choose the structure-of-array (SoA) layout. The SoA approach maximizes spatial locality on streaming access and thus improves sustained bandwidth on both modern CPUs and GPUs. The unpacking step transforms all event-based strip tracker data and pre-measured calibration data to the SoA format in order to provide optimal performance for the clustering step. Specifically, we construct a map of the channel locations and attributes on CPU. The construction can only be done sequentially, but can overlap with raw data transfer. We then unpack the data to SoA format, which can be done concurrently for each channel on a multicore CPU or GPU. Unpacking is the most time consuming step since it involves irregular data access pattern and is particularly costly on GPU.

The CMS clustering is based on the “three thresholds” algorithm [6]. First only strips with signal-to-noise ratio larger than the “channel threshold” are recorded and we call these strips as active strips. Our

parallel implementation is based on the fact that every candidate cluster will have at least one active strip with signal-to-noise ratio larger than the “seed threshold”, which we call seed strips. We start by building an array of indices of seed strips. We then form a cluster around a seed strip by determining the left and right boundaries, computing the cluster charge, and checking it against the “cluster threshold”. For each cluster that passes the “three thresholds”, we output its left and right boundaries, centroid and optionally ADC values. Figure 2 shows the workflow of the parallel clustering algorithm. The seed seeking stage can be parallelized over all strips and the cluster forming stage can be parallelized over all seed strips. The input data for these tests is a simulated data sample of $t\bar{t}$ events with an average pileup per event of 70 using the Phase 1 CMS geometry in 2018 with realistic detector conditions. For this TTBar PU70 data sample, the strip number and the seed strip number are roughly 800,000 and 150,000, respectively.

Figure 2: Parallel clustering algorithm workflow

3 Optimization

In order to maximize the hardware usage and improve the overall throughput for the standalone program, we have enabled concurrency in processing multiple events. On CPU, this is achieved with OpenMP nested parallelism by creating two levels of OpenMP parallel regions, one inside the other. The outer level is used to handle different events while an inner level is used to handle sets of strips within a single event. To maintain good memory locality in nested parallelism, it is important to ensure that threads are given affinity to specific cores. It is also important that memory is placed locally to the processor that accesses the data. On GPU, we use CUDA streams to launch multiple events concurrently on the same device. This not only maximizes GPU utilization, it also reduces data transfer overhead by overlapping communication with computation. We rely on a cached memory allocator developed in CMSSW [7] based on one in the CUB library [8] for GPU memory allocation. This has significantly reduced the memory allocation and deallocation overhead in processing multiple events.

4 Performance Results

We evaluate the parallel performance of the standalone program on Tigergpu, the GPU cluster at research computing of Princeton University. Each node in Tigergpu is equipped with two 2.4 GHz Xeon Broadwell E5-2680 v4 processors on the host and four 1328 MHz NVIDIA P100 GPU as accelerators. For CPU results, each test uses all 28 cores with nested parallelism. For GPU results, we use OpenMP to stream multiple events concurrently on a single GPU. Table 1 shows the wall-clock time and throughput results in running 840 events, where all events are copies of a single TTBar PU70 event. On CPU, the best performance is

observed in running 14 events concurrently with 2 cores per event, while on GPU, running 2 events/streams concurrently results in the best performance. Note that the performance comparison is between running the code on a single GPU and on 28 CPU cores.

2x2.4 GHz Xeon Broadwell E5-2680 v4			1238MHz NVIDIA P100		
NxM	time (s)	throughput (events/s)	N	time (s)	throughput (events/s)
1x28	1.7	492	1	1.36	615
2x14	2.1	400	2	1.29	649
4x7	1.67	502	4	1.41	595
7x4	1.57	532	7	1.46	574
14x2	1.50	560	14	1.53	548
28x1	2.10	400	28	1.54	546

Table 1: Performance comparison in running 840 TTBar PU70 events. N is the events concurrency and M is the CPU parallelization within one event. The reported number for each test is the average of 10 trials.

5 Conclusions

We have enabled parallelization of unpacking and clustering of CMS silicon strip detector data and demonstrated its performance on both multi-core CPUs and many-core GPUs. Overall, we observe that a single GPU (P100) outperforms two sockets Intel Broadwell CPU (2x14 cores 2.4 GHz Xeon Broadwell E5-2680 v4) by 24% in average. Next, we will integrate the implementation with CMSSW and convert clusters to global hit coordinates in order to provide the necessary input for MKFIT.

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Rescuing VBF Higgs Invisible Events with Novel Vertex Selection

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ABSTRACT

ATLAS has developed a new approach for primary vertex selection in events containing an invisible Higgs boson decay in vector-boson fusion (VBF) under current LHC as well as HL-LHC conditions, integrating calorimeter and tracking information to mitigate the impact of pileup vertex merging. A new way to handle forward jets outside the current tracking acceptance is also introduced using the concept of vertex confidence. The new algorithm is insensitive to pileup density and improves the average vertex selection efficiency from 80% to 88% in current LHC conditions, and from 88% to 97% in HL-LHC conditions, under tight VBF Higgs event selection cuts.

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1 Introduction

The event reconstruction in the ATLAS experiment [1] requires the identification and selection of a hard-scatter (HS) primary vertex among the multiple interaction vertices reconstructed in each event. Currently the HS vertex candidate is selected based on the largest sum of squared transverse momenta (p_T) over the associated tracks.* While this method works very well in events containing hard physics objects within the tracker acceptance, it suffers from low efficiency in final states containing forward and/or low p_T jets, such as in the case of events containing an invisible Higgs boson decay (e.g. $H \rightarrow ZZ^* \rightarrow 4\nu$, see Appendix A) in vector-boson fusion (VBF), later referred to as VBF Higgs invisible events, where the correct primary vertex is chosen correctly only 80% of the time.

In order to overcome this challenge and improve the signal acceptance for VBF Higgs invisible events, we introduce two novel ideas. First, we propose a new vertex selection algorithm that combines tracking with calorimeter jet information to overcome the challenge of events with low p_T jets. This new algorithm improves the vertex selection efficiency by 10%. Second, to address the case of events containing forward jets outside the tracking acceptance, we introduce the concept of vertex confidence. We classify events as high/low confidence based on the amount of track p_T associated to hard jets. Events in which the majority of the total jet p_T is outside the (pseudorapidity) η acceptance of the tracker ($|\eta| > 2.5$) are classified as low vertex confidence events and no vertex is chosen for this category. For VBF Higgs invisible events, we find that the new algorithm selects the correct primary vertex 97% of the time for the high confidence events. The remaining events are classified as low confidence VBF events, for which no attempt is made to assign a HS vertex even though there is still a VBF jet signature.

In LHC Run 4, where the upgraded ATLAS Inner Tracker (ITk) [2] provides an extended acceptance of $|\eta| < 4$, the new vertex selection algorithm improves upon the current selection technique by 10% under the busier HL-LHC conditions in terms of pileup (PU).

2 Datasets and Event Selection

Samples of simulated $H \rightarrow ZZ^* \rightarrow 4\nu$ events in ATLAS Run 3 (Run 4) conditions, with a center-of-mass energy of 13 (14) TeV and a mean number of proton-proton interactions μ of 60 (200) per bunch crossing are used, assuming the ATLAS ITk geometry layout and reconstruction performance for Run 4, as described in Ref. [2].

Physics event selections ensure that every event has a vertex of interest, setting the theoretical maximum vertex selection efficiency at 100%. A key challenge in studying primary vertex identification is the fact that physics event selections depend on the choice of the primary vertex. For example, in order to suppress background PU interactions, jets are required to have a large fraction of their track p_T pointing to the selected HS primary vertex. This is typically achieved by requiring jet $R_{p_T} > 0.1$, where R_{p_T} [3] is defined as:

$$R_{p_T} = \sum_{\text{tracks}} \frac{p_{T(\text{track})}}{p_{T(\text{jet})}} \mathbb{1}(\Delta R < 0.4). \quad (1)$$

Here we sum over tracks attached to the selected HS primary vertex, $\mathbb{1}$ is the indicator function, and ΔR is the distance between the track and jet in the $\eta - \phi$ space. Since the R_{p_T} condition requires the definition of an HS vertex, it biases the measurement of the vertex selection efficiency. This is because VBF Higgs events in which the selected vertex is not the true HS primary vertex do not pass the jet selection due to low R_{p_T} with respect to the incorrect vertex, and are not considered in the calculation of the efficiency, leading to an overestimation of the vertex selection efficiency.

To overcome this, a new event selection is defined that is unbiased with respect to the choice of the vertex. The idea is to ensure that every event has a VBF Higgs invisible vertex that is identifiable under typical VBF jet criteria. To achieve this, truth level information from the simulation is used to impose the VBF jet criteria on reconstructed jets that come from the VBF Higgs invisible HS interaction. This ensures

*There exist specialized vertex selection algorithms that use photons to identify the HS vertex as in the case of $H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ [4]. These will not be discussed in this report as the vertex selection algorithms under consideration do not utilize detector objects beyond tracks and calorimeter jets, and are hence in principle generally applicable.

that all identifiable VBF Higgs events are considered for the calculation of the vertex selection efficiency regardless of the choice of vertex, leading to a vertex-unbiased event selection.

3 Current Approach and its Limitations

The current approach to find the HS vertex in an event is to identify the vertex with the largest scalar summed squared track transverse momentum,

$$\text{sumPT} = \sum_{\text{tracks}} p_{\text{T}}^2. \quad (2)$$

One limitation of this method is that it becomes vulnerable to selecting high p_{T} vertices resulting from the merging of nearby PU vertices, which occurs when the typical distance between such vertices is comparable to or smaller than the vertex resolution. This effect is illustrated in Figure 1(a), where the sumPT vertex selection efficiency shows a downward trend with increasing average local PU vertex density. This consequence of merged PU vertices is exacerbated for VBF Higgs invisible events due to low visible p_{T} because of the invisible particles in the final state. This is related to the general limitation of the method when applied to low visible p_{T} interactions, as events often contain PU interactions that have sumPT larger than the HS interaction, even without the effect of PU vertex merging. This is highlighted in Figure 1(b) where sumPT gives an efficiency of 88% despite PU vertex merging being addressed by ATLAS in HL-LHC conditions thanks to improved tracking resolution and vertex reconstruction [2].

Figure 1: Vertex selection efficiency as a function of the PU density, defined as the local density of vertices at the primary vertex in the event. The default sumPT selection method (square) is compared with the proposed sumPTw selection (circle). Error bars are statistical errors. Best fit linear functions are drawn through the sets of points with 1-sigma error bands to visualize the slopes with respect to the PU density. (a) LHC Run 3 conditions, (b) HL-LHC Run 4 conditions. Note that the efficiencies are larger for Run 4 than for Run 3 as the increased tracking acceptance at the HL-LHC [2] allows for tracks inside forward HS VBF jets. From Ref. [5].

4 New Technique

A new vertex selection technique is developed to tackle the two limitations discussed above. To handle merged PU vertices, one can exploit angular correlations between the tracks from the HS vertex and the high p_{T} HS jets in the event. The tracks from merged PU vertices are not strongly correlated in angles with

each other, or with these jets, because they originate from independent close-by interactions. Therefore one can resolve the substructure associated with vertices and groom the tracks attached to the vertices such that tracks correlated to HS processes are selected preferentially. To address the problem of low visible p_T HS interactions, one can leverage the fact that, in general, VBF jets have higher p_T than PU jets; the high HS jet p_T can be used to preferentially weigh the sum over track p_T for the HS vertex.

Based on these insights, we propose a new algorithm for vertex selection in VBF Higgs invisible events that makes use of the track-jet correlations within each vertex, based on maximizing an augmented version of the standard sumPT algorithm that projects tracks onto hard jets,

$$\text{sumPTw} = \sum_{\text{tracks}} p_{T_w} = \sum_{\text{tracks}} p_{T(\text{track})}^2 p_{T(\text{closest jet})}^2 \frac{1}{\Delta R} \mathbb{1}(\Delta R < 0.4) \mathbb{1}(p_{T(\text{jet})} > p_{T(\text{threshold})}). \quad (3)$$

Here $\mathbb{1}$ is the indicator function, $p_{T(\text{threshold})} = 30$ GeV is used, and ΔR is the distance between a track and the closest jet with sufficient p_T in the $\eta - \phi$ space. This projects tracks onto jets and adds the weighted p_{T_w} as defined above. Thus sumPTw is a bolstered measure of the total vertex sumPT in jets. Since merged PU vertices are made of two or more independent interactions, their tracks are not correlated in the $\eta - \phi$ space with the HS interaction. Therefore by projecting their tracks onto hard jet axis directions, their large sumPT is significantly reduced. Additionally the use of the $p_{T(\text{closest jet})}$ term adds a weight that is larger for the HS interaction.

Figure 1 shows the new sumPTw algorithm performance versus the standard sumPT algorithm. The former flattens the PU vertex density dependence of the vertex selection efficiency in Figure 1(a). This demonstrates the robustness of sumPTw against merged PU vertices. The new algorithm also improves the average vertex selection efficiency from 80% to 88% in Figure 1(a), and from 88% to 97% in Figure 1(b), which is an approximately 10% improvement in each case compared to the current approach. The improvements in the average efficiencies, particularly in the case of Figure 1(b), can be attributed to the jet p_T weight term that helps the otherwise low visible p_T of the HS vertex.

5 Experimental Challenges and Future Improvements

The sumPTw algorithm mitigates the effects of PU vertex merging and low visible p_T that limits the performance of vertex selection in VBF Higgs invisible events. However, the new method applied in Run 3 conditions underperforms when compared to HL-LHC conditions. This is due to the expanded η acceptance of the tracker in ATLAS at HL-LHC [2].

To address the reduced tracking coverage in Run 3, an event category is defined which captures events where the majority of the total jet p_T is outside the η acceptance of the tracker. These events contain HS vertices that have very few tracks inside the tracker, and thus have low sumPT or sumPTw. Referred to as low confidence events, they are defined by the presence of more than one jet in the $|\eta| > 2.1$ region of the detector that has $p_T > 30$ GeV and $R_{p_T} < 0.1$ with respect to all the vertices in the event (20% of the events used). All other events, referred to as high confidence events, by definition have high p_T jets within the tracker η acceptance, and thus the HS vertex has all of its tracks within the tracker (80% of the events used).

The performance of sumPTw on high confidence events as compared to all the events in Run 3 is shown in Figure 2(a). It can be seen that the performance of sumPTw on high confidence events in Run 3 has parity with the performance of sumPTw on all the events with the expanded tracker of the ATLAS detector at the HL-LHC from Figure 2(b). This is due to events in both cases having a HS vertex that has all its tracks within the tracker. One can also compare the performance of sumPT and sumPTw on high confidence events and note the improvement in average efficiency from 88% to 97%, as seen in Figure 2(b).

This justifies the idea that the efficiency for sumPTw seen in Figure 1(a) is limited by events with HS p_T outside the tracker η acceptance. By defining the high/low confidence events one can address the effect of the limited tracking η acceptance in Run 3. For the high confidence events one can identify the HS vertex with 97% efficiency, whereas for the low confidence events no attempt is made to assign a HS vertex even though there is still a VBF event signature.

Figure 2: Vertex selection efficiency as a function of the PU density, defined as the local density of vertices at the primary vertex in the event. (a) The sumPT_w selection on all events (circle) is compared with the sumPT_w selection on high confidence events (cross). (b) The default sumPT selection (star) is compared with the proposed sumPT_w selection (cross) on high confidence events. Error bars are statistical errors. Best fit linear functions are drawn through the sets of points with 1-sigma error bands to visualize the slopes with respect to the PU density. From Ref. [5].

Finally, the challenge of PU interactions with high p_T jets, referred to as hard QCD PU interactions, prevents the sumPT_w performance from reaching 100% efficiency in both Figure 1(b) and Figure 2. When the event has hard QCD PU interactions, the PU vertices have tracks pointing along hard PU jets and thus get selected by sumPT_w. This final limitation is a shortcoming of topology-agnostic vertex selection algorithms; they can't distinguish between different topologies. For this reason sumPT_w can pick a hard QCD PU vertex instead of the VBF Higgs HS vertex. This paves the way for a more sophisticated vertex selection algorithm which extends the innovations presented here and combines them with topology discriminating properties. Such an algorithm would then be able to distinguish hard QCD PU from HS vertices, despite competing summed scalar transverse momenta, etc.

6 Conclusions

ATLAS has developed a new approach for primary vertex selection that integrates calorimeter and tracking information to mitigate the impact of pileup vertex merging and handle hard-scatter interactions with low visible p_T . The new algorithm is insensitive to pileup density and improves the average vertex selection efficiency for events containing an invisible Higgs boson decay in vector-boson fusion inclusively from 80% to 88% in LHC Run 3 conditions and from 88% to 97% in the HL-LHC Run 4 conditions. A possible avenue for improvement upon the new algorithm proposed here involves developing an algorithm that exploits topological information and can handle pileup interactions with high p_T jets.

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A Appendix: Feynman Diagram for VBF $H \rightarrow ZZ^* \rightarrow 4\nu$

Figure 3: Feynman diagram for VBF $H \rightarrow ZZ^* \rightarrow 4\nu$. The quarks that radiate the vector bosons form the two forward jets that make up the distinct VBF jet signature. In the invisible final state, it becomes crucial to capture the tracks inside the two VBF jets for identify the hard scatter primary vertex.

Performance of Belle II tracking on collision data

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ABSTRACT

The tracking system of Belle II consists of a silicon vertex detector (VXD) and a cylindrical drift chamber (CDC), both operating in a magnetic field created by the main solenoid of 1.5 T and final focusing magnets. The tracking algorithms employed at Belle II are based on a standalone reconstruction in SVD and CDC as well as on a combination of the two approaches, they employ a number of machine learning methods for optimal performance. The tracking reconstruction is tested on the collision data collected in 2018 and 2019. The first experience with data introduced additional challenges which are mitigated with the introduction of new algorithms such as track finding seeded by calorimeter clusters and CDC cross-talk filtering.

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1 Introduction

The focus of the Belle II experiment is the study of CP-violation and rare decays of B mesons. The experiment is located at the SuperKEKB collider, which provides e^+e^- collision at a center of mass energy of 10.58 GeV. This energy is just above the mass of the $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance, which almost exclusively decays to a pair of B mesons. Furthermore, the asymmetric beam energies of 4 and 7 GeV, respectively, lead to a forward boost of the $B\bar{B}$ system so that lifetime of the B mesons can be studied.

The peak luminosity of the SuperKEKB collider is 40 times higher than the one of the predecessor KEKB, achieving up to $L = 8 \times 10^{35} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. This is achieved by a significant reduction of the beam size ('nano beam' scheme) and increased beam currents. Over the full lifetime, SuperKEKB is expected to deliver an integrated luminosity of 50 ab^{-1} . So far about 30 fb^{-1} have been recorded by the Belle II experiment. The current tasks SuperKEKB is facing is to increase the instantaneous luminosity while the beam background levels have to be reduced.

The design of the Belle II experiment shown in Figure 1 is motivated by this high instantaneous luminosity and the challenges that come with it. The tracking system is made up of three tracking detectors: the pixel detector (PXD) and the strip vertex detector (SVD), which are commonly summarized as the vertex detector (VXD), as well as the central drift chamber (CDC). The PXD is installed right outside the beam pipe and consists of two layers, based on the DEPFET Pixel Technology, but currently only the first layer and four modules of the second layer are installed. One of the advantages of this technology is a very low material budget of about 0.2% of a radiation length. The PXD allows for a very precise measurement of the impact parameter of tracks as the inner layer is installed at a radius of just about 1.4 cm. The SVD encloses the PXD and consists of four layers of double-sided silicon strip detectors, which corresponds to a thickness of about 0.7% radiation lengths, and it has an excellent hit time resolution of about 3 ns. This allows the SVD to provide robust tracking despite the background levels, also for standalone tracking. The outermost tracking detector is the CDC, which consists of 56 layers of wires grouped in alternating superlayers of axial and stereo wires. Stereo wires are skewed by an angle between 45.4 and 74 mrad in the positive and negative direction with respect to the axis of the beam and are necessary to determine the longitudinal position of tracks. Most importantly, the CDC has a very high momentum resolution as it covers the major part of the tracking volume up to $l \times r = 2.3 \text{ m} \times 2.2 \text{ m}$.

Figure 1: Technical drawing of a section of the Belle II detector [10].

The combination of these three detectors is perfectly suited for the tracking challenges of the $\Upsilon(4S)$ events that are the focus of the studies of the Belle II experiment. A typical $B\bar{B}$ event consists on average of eleven tracks with a soft momentum spectrum, most of which are tracks from charged pions, as depicted in Figure 2.

Furthermore, high backgrounds from the machine are expected, i.e. the number of background hits

Figure 2: (a) Normalized distributions (log scale) of transverse momentum of primary charged particles as simulated for $\Upsilon(4S)$ events and (b) relative fraction of charged particle types in these events [1].

is about two orders of magnitude larger than the number of signal hits. On the other side, many analyses require a precise measurement of primary and secondary vertices. Given the forward boost, the flight distance of the $B\bar{B}$ system is in the order of just 10–100 μm . Often a technique called 'Full Event Interpretation' (FEI) [3] is used, where the idea is to reconstruct the full decay chain in the event including all particles that participated. To that end, it is necessary to reconstruct all tracks down to a transverse momentum p_T of approximately 50 MeV. Moreover, no fake or duplicate tracks should be found.

2 Background Suppression and Track Finding

Before the actual track finding is performed it is necessary to reject as many background hits as possible, while preserving as many signal hits as possible. For each of the subdetectors designated approaches have been developed, of which the background suppression in the CDC is briefly described here as a showcase. Currently, a classical approach is employed: each CDC hit is required to have a minimum of deposited charge and time over threshold, i.e. short pulses are rejected, too. This simple selection is very efficient in rejecting hits from machine background, as well as so-called cross talk hits. Cross talk describes a feature of the ASIC read-out chips, where neighboring channels can light up if a signal hit is registered. To further reduce the contribution from cross talk hits, which typically have a small charge and peculiar time structure, a designated filter was developed targeting these exact properties.

The track finding is structured in a very modular manner, which is also reflected in the actual implementation. This modularity of the track finding sequence allows for reordering of the independent modules in case it is needed, i.e. it can be adapted according to the background condition, a potential degradation of the detector performance, etc. Furthermore, it is very convenient to add novel track finding approaches. The current sequence is summarized in Figure 3.

The CDC track finding consists of two independent algorithms and is used as the baseline. In the second step, SVD hits are added to the previously found tracks making use of a Combinatorial Kalman Filter (CKF). The third step considers the unused SVD hits and tries to reconstruct tracks out of them. These SVD standalone tracks are then extrapolated to the CDC again via another CKF. Finally all independently found tracks are merged to a single collection that is then extrapolated to the PXD in the final step by a third CKF.

In the following sections, the basic idea behind each of the steps of the track finding sequence is given. More information can be found in the recently submitted Belle II Tracking Paper [1].

Figure 3: The current sequence of the Belle II track finding algorithms (a), and the corresponding subdetectors for each one of the steps (b).

2.1 CDC Track Finding

The CDC track finding consists of two algorithms: a global approach based on Legendre Parameters and a local approach using a Cellular Automaton.

The global track finder is performed in three main steps, which are illustrated in Figure 4. These steps only consider hits in axial wires, i.e. the track finding is executed in the $r-\phi$ plane. The hits in the stereo wires are added to the tracks as a last step to reconstruct the z information. The left figure shows the first step of the global track finder in the two dimensional plane so that the track can be seen as a circular trajectory. The hit positions are approximated by so-called drift circles around the positions of the wires, where the radius is derived from the timing information of the individual hits. In the next step a conformal transformation (Hough transform) is applied, which transforms the circular trajectory to a straight line while the drift circles remain circles. This significantly simplifies the task as now a common tangent to a set of circles has to be found. In the final step, Legendre Parameters are used to describe the position (x_0, y_0) and radius R_{dr} of the drift circles as

$$\rho = x_0 \cos \theta + y_0 \sin \theta + R_{\text{dr}}. \quad (1)$$

This equation corresponds to a sinusoidal curve for each of the drift circles as shown in right figure. Tracks are reconstructed by determining points of maximum density in this parameter space. This task is implemented very efficiently as a two dimensional binary search with a dedicated quadtree structure and a 'sliding bin' technique, which recenters the area of interest around the point of maximum density.

Figure 4: Main steps of the CDC Legendre track finding algorithm. The track (dashed line) is reconstructed using the information from the drift circles around the CDC wires (colored circles). The algorithm uses a conformal transformation (middle) and formulation in Legendre Parameters (right) to find tracks in this global approach.

Compared to the global track finder, which shows a high performance for tracks from the primary vertex, the local track finder focuses on short and displaced tracks. The three main steps of this algorithm are shown in Figure 5. In the first step, triplets of hits in neighboring layers are formed assuming a certain right-left-passage of the track. The second step connects triplets that share two hits and assigns a weight based on a common fit to these segments. Finally, overlapping segments are combined and a weight is assigned based on a common fit.

Figure 5: Main steps of the CDC cellular automaton track finding algorithm. This local approach is based on subsequent combinations of track segments.

Currently, the local track finder is not used as a standalone algorithm due to the non-negligible fake rate. Instead, reconstructed segments are added to tracks found by the global track finder using multivariate methods*. As the last step of the CDC track finding there are several further MVA-based filters to improve fake and clone rate, as well as purity and track parameter resolution. Furthermore, an additional quality indicator is currently being studied to reduce the fake rate of the local track finder so that it can be used as a standalone algorithm.

2.2 Extrapolation from CDC to SVD and SVD to PXD

The next step in the standard track reconstruction chain is to extrapolate the previously found CDC tracks inwards to the SVD. This is done via a CKF, which may skip detector layers to account for inefficiencies of the detector. The iterative procedure is as follows: all hits within a certain $\theta \times \phi$ window around the extrapolated track are considered and the best of these candidates are picked using MVA-based filters. Then, new paths are defined based on all selected candidates and the procedure is repeated for all of them. In the end, the best candidate is selected for each CDC track seed.

The implementation of the algorithm is highly configurable as it is completely template based. This has the advantage that filters for the selection of the best hit and path candidates can be modified and tuned

*The multivariate methods are typically based on FastBDT [2] throughout the Belle II software.

easily. Furthermore, basically the same code is used for the last step of the track reconstruction chain where all tracks are extrapolated to the PXD.

As a side note, material interactions are currently disabled during the CKF as many extrapolations have to be done to reduce computing time. This only has a minor influence on the reconstructed tracks as the CKF is only used to add hits to previously found tracks and the actual track fit considers material interactions. Nevertheless, studies are going on to replace the GENFIT2 tracking toolkit [4], which is used as the basis of many track definition and track reconstruction tasks throughout the software, with ACTS [5], which promises more efficient modeling of material interactions amongst other advantages.

2.3 SVD Track Finding

All SVD hits that have not been added to tracks extrapolated to the SVD in the previous step are subject to the SVD standalone track finding algorithm, which is commonly called VXDTF2. This algorithm is based on a 'sector map' that stores friendship relations between sectors. To that end, each of the SVD sensors is split to 3×3 sectors. The friendship relation between two sectors is stored in the map if consecutive hits of simulated tracks are found and if certain filter criteria are passed that are used to reject outliers. Accordingly, the sector map greatly reduces the complexity of the track finding problem by lowering the potential combinations of hits that have to be considered. Furthermore, the granularity of the sectors can be tuned to optimize the track finding for high efficiency or low fake rate.

To actually find the tracks a cellular automaton is employed that considers pairs of space points. In the next step, all combinations that do not pass certain filter requirements based on quantities like the angle between the hits or timing are rejected. In the final step, a MVA is used to reject fake and clone tracks.

This algorithm, which was developed in-house, shows a very high performance at the current background levels and is especially important to reconstruct low momentum and forward tracks, which both typically only have a low number of CDC hits and are thus hard to reconstruct by the CDC track finding algorithms.

2.4 Extrapolation from SVD to CDC

This second CKF step aims to add CDC hits to the tracks found by the standalone SVD track finder, which improves the momentum resolution of the tracks. This is illustrated in Figure 6. The left plot shows the fraction of reconstructed tracks that have CDC hits with and without this additional CKF, as a function of the forward angle of the tracks. This slope is denoted as $\tan \lambda$ with $\lambda = \pi/2 - \theta$, so that $\tan \lambda = 0$ means that the track is perpendicular to the direction of the beam. The right figure shows the invariant mass as calculated for two-track events, where both tracks are required to be in the forward detector regions as indicated by the blue dashed lines in Figure 6 (a).

Figure 6: (a) The fraction of tracks with CDC hits with and without the additional CKF, where $\tan \lambda$ denotes the slope (forward angle) of the tracks. (b) The improvement of the resolution of the invariant mass for events with forward tracks as indicated by the blue dashed lines in (a).

The implementation of this algorithm is very similar to the CKF described in Section 2.2 due to the template based nature but some modifications were necessary to take effects like drift time and left-right-passage into account.

2.5 Current developments

One of the novel tracking algorithms that are currently being developed is introduced to serve as an example. As part of the performance studies discussed in Section 3, it is observed that the electron track finding efficiency is about 5% lower due to material effects (Bremsstrahlung). One of the ideas to mitigate this effect is to use calorimeter showers as seed objects for an additional CKF, as the template-based nature of the CKF allows for easy code development.

The algorithm starts with a helix extrapolation for both charge assumptions from the position of the shower to the center of detector. The helix parameters are then used as a seed for the CKF. As only one of the charge assumptions is expected to be a valid track the candidate with the lower number of hits is rejected. The implementation of the CKF is done, so currently the parameters of CKF are being optimized and the validation on data is performed. Possible extensions of this algorithm include to add Bremsstrahlung photons along the track and to implement a procedure to find vertices from pair production.

3 Performance

This section provides a few benchmark points to illustrate the excellent performance of the Belle II track finding algorithms. Figure 7 shows the track finding efficiency as a function of the transverse momentum p_T and for different particle types for different background levels with respect to the expected beam background at nominal luminosity. These figures show that the track finding efficiency is quite robust against beam background and the performance is still acceptable at twice the expected background level. Furthermore, there is still room for improvements since no optimizations for higher than expected background have been done yet.

Figure 7: Track finding efficiency of particles from the primary interaction calculated for simulated $\Upsilon(4S)$ events with different levels of beam-induced background relative to the expected level as a function of the transverse momentum (a) and the particle type (b) [1].

Figure 8 illustrates the excellent track parameter resolution that is achieved with the combination of all tracking algorithms discussed in the previous section. As expected, the d_0 resolution is dominated by the PXD hits and thus basically independent of the background level. In contrast to that, the p_T resolution degrades slightly for low momentum particles at higher background levels.

Figure 8: Track parameter resolutions of (a) the transverse impact parameter d_0 and (b) the transverse momentum p_T for simulated $\Upsilon(4S)$ events with different levels of beam-induced background [1].

More generally, the tracking code runs very stable on the High Level Trigger (HLT). Due to the complexity, tracking is the most time-consuming process as illustrated in 9; all in all about 1 s per event is needed for the track reconstruction. The largest share of this goes to the CDC track finding, the track fitting and the vertexing. The current CPU consumption due to tracking is not critical at current conditions but is expected to rise at higher background levels. However, there is still room for improvement. As mentioned before, there are studies going on to replace GENFIT2 with ACTS, which provides faster fitting and modeling of material interactions, and, as mentioned before, the chain of track finding algorithms can be restructured thanks to its modularity.

Figure 9: Processing time of a standard online reconstruction performed on s HLT worker node in single-processing mode for different event types [1]. The abbreviation *ECL* refers to the electromagnetic calorimeter of the Belle II experiment.

4 Validation

The track finding efficiency is a key performance driver of Belle II physics. As mentioned before, many physics analyses make use of the Full Event Interpretation approach for which it is especially important to achieve a high tracking performance, know where its limitations are and validate it on data. The track finding efficiency is validated via several tag-and-probe studies focusing on a variety of final states to cover a

large track momentum spectrum. Three of these final states are introduced in Figure 10 for low momentum (left, $p_T \lesssim 200$ MeV), intermediate momentum (middle, $200 \text{ MeV} \lesssim p_T \lesssim 2$ GeV) and high momentum (right, $p_T \gtrsim 2$ GeV).

Figure 10: Examples of final states used for Tag-and-Probe studies to validate tracking efficiencies in data for low (left), intermediate (middle) and high (right) momentum tracks. The tracks used to tag the event are shown in red, while the blue track corresponds to the probe object.

The main principle of these tag-and-probe analyses can be explained quite easily focusing on the τ -pair events depicted in the middle figure. To tag the events it is required that they have three good quality tracks with a total charge of ± 1 (shown in red). The probe then consists of a fourth track (blue) that passes only loose selections and conserves the charge. The track finding efficiency ϵ can then be derived using the ratio of the number of events where the probe track is found N_4 and where it is not found N_3 as

$$\epsilon \cdot A = \frac{N_4}{N_3 + N_4} \quad (2)$$

where A corresponds to the geometric acceptance of the detector. These studies show high level of agreement between data and simulation - otherwise they can serve as direct input to improvements of the simulation.

5 Beam Spot Width and Alignment

As mentioned in the introduction, SuperKEKB strongly squeezes the beams at the interaction point. This leads to the fact that the vertical beam spot size σ_y is much smaller than the resolution of the transverse impact parameter d_0 with $\sigma_y < 2 \mu\text{m}$. The horizontal beam spot size is in the order of $\sigma_x \approx 15 \mu\text{m}$. In comparison, Figure 11 shows the impact parameter d_0 as measured on data, with (red) and without (blue) the inclusion of PXD hits during the track reconstruction. Only horizontal tracks were selected so that the size of the beam spot can be neglected. Furthermore, it should be noted that for this figure data from an early experiment was used, where only parts of the vertex detector were installed. As anticipated, the PXD significantly increases the resolution down to $\sigma = 12.1 \mu\text{m}$, which is in agreement with the expected value of $\sigma \approx 10 \mu\text{m}$. It should be mentioned here that this high performance is not possible without good detector alignment. In our case, the alignment is corrections are derived using the Millepede-II framework [9].

Furthermore, the d_0 distribution can be determined as a function of the polar angle ϕ_0 as shown in Figure 12 (a), which reveals a dual peak shape coming from the asymmetric beam profile ($\sigma_y \ll \sigma_x$). The simulation is observed to underestimate the resolution slightly. Moreover, this distribution can be unfolded using the d_0 resolution discussed previously to determine the beam profile, which is shown in Figure 12 (b). Here, a good simulation of the beam profile can be seen. All in all, this illustrates the excellent performance of the track reconstruction and alignment procedures once more.

Figure 11: Distribution of transverse impact parameter d_0 as determined from events with two horizontal tracks [7].

Figure 12: Distribution of transverse impact parameter d_0 as measured in dimuon events (a) and unfolding of the distribution using measured the d_0 resolution to show the beam profile (b) [6].

6 Measurement of D^0 lifetime

As a highlight, one of the first highly track-based analysis is described as it is an excellent exercise to test vertexing and alignment, apart from the obvious physics aspect. The analysis is based on pure samples of $D^{*+} \rightarrow D^0 \pi^+$ events, where the D^0 is reconstructed in three different final states. The largest systematic uncertainties are expected to stem from residual misalignment and beam spot measurements. As illustrated before, these effects are well understood and corrected for to best current knowledge.

One of the results of the analysis is shown in Figure 13, which shows the distribution of the lifetime of the D^0 meson in one of the channels. The clear exponential decay towards long lifetimes is especially reassuring as it confirms the excellent resolution of achieved with the Belle II tracking detectors and employed algorithms. The D^0 lifetime extracted from the fit of the very limited data is determined as 370 ± 40 fs, which is statistically compatible with the expectation.

Figure 13: Determination of the D^0 lifetime [8].

7 Conclusions

The Belle II tracking detectors and algorithms show excellent performance throughout all of the presented studies. The high flexibility of the modular approach proves to be advantageous to adjust tracking to background conditions and performance requirements, as well as future extensions of algorithms. Currently, many studies are going on trying to exploit MVA-based approaches for all kinds of use cases like background rejection, track quality and many others. The high performance of Belle II tracking is also reflected in the first tracking-focused studies and analyses like the determination of the D^0 lifetime.

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Data Reconstruction Using Deep Neural Networks for Particle Imaging Neutrino Detectors

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ABSTRACT

A Liquid Argon Time Projection Chamber (LArTPC) is a type of particle imaging detector that can record images of charged particle trajectories with high (\sim mm/pixel) spatial resolution and calorimetric information. At the intensity frontier of high energy physics, LArTPC is the detector technology of choice for a number of experiments including the Short Baseline Neutrino program and the Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment which require high precision neutrino oscillation measurements to answer some fundamental questions about the universe. However, the analysis of detailed particle images can be difficult and building a high quality data reconstruction chain for large scale (over 100 tonnes) LArTPC detectors remains challenging. The research team at SLAC leads the R&D of a full Machine Learning (ML) based data reconstruction chain for LArTPC detectors. Our chain is a multi-task network cascade that performs pixel feature extraction (semantic segmentation using Sparse U-Net with ResNet modules), particle start and end point prediction (Point Proposal Network), pixel clustering for particle instance identification (custom convolution and instance attention layers), and particle flow analysis using Graph Neural Networks (GNNs). The output of the chain is a fully reconstructed event that can be used by physicists to infer neutrino oscillation physics. This R&D takes a significant step forward from the current state of the art in experimental neutrino physics. In this talk, we present the development of our reconstruction chain using an open data set. Our software is made publicly available to improve the reproducibility and transparency of our research work.

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1 Introduction

In recent years, the accelerator-based neutrino physics community in the United States has moved to employ Liquid Argon Time Projection Chambers (LArTPCs) as a central neutrino detection technology [1]. Charged particles that traverse the detector ionize the noble liquid. The electrons so produced are drifted in a uniform electric field towards a readout plane. The location of electrons collected on the anode combined with their arrival time offers mm-scale resolution images of charged particle interactions, as illustrated in figure 1. Wire-based and pixel-based readout technologies produce either three 2D projections – which can be combined to form a 3D image using tomographic reconstruction – or natively record a single 3D image, respectively.

Figure 1: (a) Three 2D projections of a neutrino interaction recorded by the ICARUS detector in the CNGS beam [2]. (b) Single 3D image of an electromagnetic shower recorded by the LArPIX detector [3].

The Short Baseline Neutrino Program (SBN) aims to clarify an anomalous signal observed by the Mini-BOONE experiment by using three $\mathcal{O}(100)$ t scale LArTPCs placed at varying short distances from a neutrino source [4]. The DUNE experiment is a future project that will use the LArTPC technology to measure electron neutrino appearance at a long baseline with unprecedented accuracy [5]. It will consist of a small pixel-readout near detector (105 t) and an enormous wire-readout far detector (40 kt).

Both of these physics endeavors centrally depend upon the efficient identification and accurate reconstruction of neutrino interactions. Traditional pattern recognition techniques are heavily challenged by the extraordinary level of detail LArTPCs images exhibit. Machine Learning (ML) is at the forefront of computer vision and offers a way to cover the large phase space necessary for this task. This paper presents a novel end-to-end ML-based reconstruction chain for LArTPCs. The following sections detail the architectures of the network modules developed for the hierarchical extraction of physics features from an image. Each stage of the reconstruction is trained and tested independently on a data set of 125280/22439 (train/test) images of size 768^3 voxels capturing a realistic density of particle interactions in a 12 m^3 volume of LAr.

2 Semantic Segmentation and Point Proposal

2.1 Architecture

The first module in the reconstruction chain is designed to extract voxel-level information in 3D images: the particle type of each voxel [6] and the location of important points [7]. These two tasks share a common backbone architecture called “U-ResNet”, a hybrid of two popular architectures: U-Net [8] and ResNet [9]. U-ResNet is schematically represented on the top of figure 2; it is an autoencoder-type network which

Figure 2: U-ResNet+PPN architecture for semantic segmentation and point proposal. Turquoise boxes are convolutions with stride 2 that increase the number of filters. Dark blue boxes are transpose convolutions with stride 2 that decrease the number of filters. Purple boxes are convolutions with stride 1 that decrease the number of filters. The spatial size of feature maps is constant across the horizontal dimension.

consists of two components. The first part is the encoding path: the image resolution is downsampled using strided convolutions while increasing the features dimension, thus learning from the input data at different scales. The number of down-sampling operations is referred to as *depth*. The second part is called the decoding path: it takes the low-spatial size, highly compressed features and up-samples them back to the original image resolution while decreasing the number of features at each step back to the initial number of features. The output layer predicts a score for each of the target particle classes: heavy ionizing particle (HIP), minimum ionizing particle (MIP), electromagnetic shower, delta rays and Michel electrons. In this section, the results are shown for a U-ResNet of depth 6 with 16 features at the highest resolution and a linear increase in the number of features at each downsampling step.

In parallel to the U-shaped network, additional layers are introduced at three spatial resolutions to form the so-called Point Proposal Network (PPN), as shown at the bottom of figure 2. These layers (PPN1–3) are attached to the decoding path, as it contains all the information extracted at each resolution it is connected to. At each spatial resolution and starting at the deepest level, PPN layers attempt to predict a positive score for voxels that contain a ground-truth PPN point. Positive voxels form a mask that is then applied to the following PPN layers. At the training stage, true-positives in the attention masks are added to both the PPN1 and PPN2 layers to be able to back-propagate through them. For each voxel that has been selected through these successive attention masks, the final layer, PPN3, uses 3×3 convolutions which predict:

- a set of coordinates with respect to the voxel center;
- a proximity score representing the likelihood of being less than 5 voxels from a ground-truth point;
- a type score related to the probability of belonging to a certain particle class.

2.2 Loss definition

The semantic segmentation part of the loss, \mathcal{L}_{seg} , is a simple cross-entropy classification loss on the class scores predicted by the network. For the PPN component, at any spatial resolution strictly lower than the original image resolution, *positive* voxels are defined as voxels containing at least one true label point. *Negative* voxels do not contain any true label points. At the original image resolution, among all voxels $\{\mathbf{x}_i\}_{i=1}^n$, the subset of positive voxels, A , is defined as voxels within a certain distance threshold $d_{positive} = 5$ voxels from the true label points $\{\mathbf{q}_j\}_{j=1}^{n_t}$; other voxels are labeled as negative. The PPN loss consists of

- a classification loss at each PPN layer averaged over all voxels. With $y_{k,i} \in \{0; 1\}$ the classification label and $p_{k,i}$ the predicted probability for voxel i in layer k to be positive, the loss reads

$$\mathcal{L}_{class} = - \sum_{k=1,2,3} \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{i=1}^{n_k} y_{k,i} \log(p_{k,i}) + (1 - y_{k,i}) \log(1 - p_{k,i}); \quad (1)$$

- an L_1 distance loss on the predicted positions of true positive voxels at the last layer. The raw point predictions of the network, $\{\mathbf{r}_i\}_{i=1}^{n_3}$, representing shifts with respect to the center of the voxels, $\{(0.5 + \mathbf{x}_i)\}_{i=1}^{n_3}$, are compared with the closest ground truth points, $\{\mathbf{q}_j\}_{j=1}^{n_t}$, in a loss of the form:

$$\mathcal{L}_{dist} = \frac{1}{n_3} \sum_{i=1}^{n_3} \mathbb{1}_A \min_{1 \leq j \leq n_t} \|\mathbf{r}_i + 0.5 + \mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{q}_j\|_1; \quad (2)$$

- a type prediction cross-entropy loss at the last layer. The predicted point type is compared with the semantic type of the closest ground truth point. With n_c the number of semantic classes, $\{\mathbf{y}_i\}_{i=1}^{n_3}$ one-hot encoded n_c -vectors indicating to which class the point belongs, and $\{\mathbf{p}_i\}_{i=1}^{n_3}$ the n_c -vectors of predicted probabilities that the point belongs to each class, the loss is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}_{type} = - \frac{1}{n_3} \sum_{i=1}^{n_3} \mathbb{1}_A \sum_{c=1}^{n_c} y_{i,c} \log(p_{i,c}). \quad (3)$$

The loss used for optimization is the sum of all the aforementioned losses, i.e. $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{seg} + \mathcal{L}_{class} + \mathcal{L}_{type} + \mathcal{L}_{dist}$.

2.3 Performance

The first two panels of figure 3 show an example set of predictions made on an event in the test dataset. The semantic predictions are obtained by taking the argmax of the segmentation scores. Point proposals are reconstructed by applying the following post-processing to the set of predictions given by the network:

1. remove points with a ‘positive’ score below 0.5;
2. run DBSCAN [10] with a distance scale of $\epsilon = 1.999$ voxels on the remaining point predictions;
3. pool the points that belong to a common cluster by taking their mean position and max class;
4. remove points of class c that are further than 2 voxels away from any voxel of semantic class c .

The rightmost panel of figure 3 shows the semantic segmentation confusion matrix. All the classes are identified with a high level of precision, with HIPs, MIPs and Shower being classified with a voxel-wise accuracy above 98%. The most significant sources of confusion are delta rays and Michel voxels identified as MIP. This is understandable considering that delta rays and Michel always either overlap or touch MIPs.

The left panel of figure 4 shows the distribution of distance from a true label point to the closest predicted point; 97.8 % of the true label points are within 10 voxels of a predicted point. The right panel of figure 4 shows the distribution of distances from a predicted point to the closest true label point; 97.8 % of the predicted points are within 10 voxels of a true label point. For both of these figures, true label points of type delta rays and predicted label points of type delta rays – defined as having a delta class score ≥ 0.1 – are not included. The fraction of true points that are more than 5 voxels away from any predicted point is 2.6 %, 1.4 %, 5.6 % and 1.2 % for the HIP, MIP, Shower and Michel true point types, respectively.

Figure 3: (a) Energy deposits from charged particle trajectories, whose color corresponds to an energy scale. (b) Semantic segmentation of the image into five classes: HIP in purple, MIP in dark blue, showers in light blue, delta rays in green and Michel electrons in orange. The large points represent PPN predictions. (c) UResNet semantic segmentation confusion matrix. Each row sums to 100%.

Figure 4: (a) Distance from a ground-truth point to the closest predicted point. (b) Distance from a predicted point to the closest ground truth point. Points of type delta are excluded from (b) and (c).

3 Dense Particle Clustering

3.1 Architecture

The third task in the reconstruction chain involves clustering voxels into different dense particle instances using a CNN. The method described in this section follows the construction in [11] and uses a U-ResNet with two decoders as shown in figure 5. The input 3D image is passed through a shared encoder and then expanded into two output feature planes. The first feature plane is referred to as the *embedding* layer and the second as the *seediness* layer. The embedding layer learns a coordinate transformation of the input image voxel coordinates such that points that belong to the same particle are embedded close to one another. The seediness layer quantifies how likely a given voxel is to be close to the centroid of embedded points that share the same particle id. Once a reasonable transformation that groups each voxels into localized clusters in embedding space is obtained, information from the two feature maps are combined in a post-processing stage where cluster labels are assigned in a sequential manner, as detailed in the following subsections.

Figure 5: Architecture of the UResNet-based dense particle clustering network.

3.2 Loss Definition

The position of the voxels in the input image are first normalized to a range that spans -1 to 1 in each direction, $\{\mathbf{x}_i\}_{i=1}^n$. The embedding decoder of the network transforms the original coordinates by learning a perturbation with respect to each voxel, i.e. $\mathbf{e}_i = \mathbf{x}_i + f(\mathbf{x}_i)$. It also outputs a margin value for each voxel, σ_i , which estimates the spatial extent of the cluster the voxel belongs to in embedding space. The seediness decoder predicts a seediness score for each voxel, $\{s_i\}_{i=1}^n$. The clustering loss consists of:

- the embedding loss, which penalizes embedded voxel coordinates, $\{\mathbf{e}_i\}_{i=1}^n$, that are far away from their cluster centroid in embeddings space, $\{\boldsymbol{\mu}_k\}_{k=1}^K$, i.e

$$\mathcal{L}_{emb} = -\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{i=1}^{n_k} [y_{i,k} \log(p_{i,k}) + (1 - y_{i,k}) \log(1 - p_{i,k})], \quad (4)$$

with K the true number of clusters, n_k the number of voxels in cluster k , $y_{i,k} \in \{0, 1\}$ an indicator of whether or not voxel i belongs to cluster k , $p_{i,k} = \exp(-\|\mathbf{e}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_k\|^2 / \sigma_k^2)$ the distance between \mathbf{e}_i and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_k$ mapped to a value between 0 and 1 and σ_k the mean margin for cluster k ;

- the smoothing loss, which enforces all margins within a common cluster to be similar, i.e.

$$\mathcal{L}_{smooth} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{i=1}^{n_k} |\sigma_i - \sigma_k|; \quad (5)$$

- the seediness loss, which tends to maximize the seediness score of points close to the centroid, i.e

$$\mathcal{L}_{seed} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{i=1}^{n_k} (s_{i,k} - p_{i,k})^2; \quad (6)$$

- the intercluster loss, which encourages the network to separate clusters in embedding space, i.e.

$$\mathcal{L}_{inter} = \frac{1}{K(K-1)} \sum_{i < j} [2\delta_d - \|\mu_i - \mu_j\|]_+^2, \quad (7)$$

with δ_d an inter-cluster margin parameter and $[\cdot]_+ = \max(0, \cdot)$.

The full loss is a weighted sum of the different components: $\mathcal{L}_{clust} = \gamma_1 \mathcal{L}_{emb} + \gamma_2 \mathcal{L}_{seed} + \gamma_3 \mathcal{L}_{smooth} + \gamma_4 \mathcal{L}_{inter}$.

3.3 Results

Inference follows an iterative greedy search procedure for detecting instances, as described in [11], and treats the voxels belonging to different semantic classes separately. The post-processing function first picks the voxel with the highest seediness, s_k , queries the corresponding embedding vector, e_k , and the margin, σ_k . This defines a Gaussian Kernel of mean e_k and width σ_k , from which one can compute the probability values, $p_{i,k}$, for all the remaining points. The voxels with probability above some threshold p_0 are clustered together. This process is repeated with the next highest seediness voxel until either all the points are attributed to a cluster or the next highest seediness is below some threshold s_0 . The values of p_0 and s_0 are selected for each class by doing a grid search on a small validation set and optimizing clustering metrics.

In order to characterize the clustering performance, three metrics are used: efficiency, purity and Adjusted Rand Index (ARI). Efficiency is a measure of undersclustering defined as the average fraction of a ground-truth cluster that is mapped to a single predicted cluster. Conversely, purity is a measure of overclustering defined as the average fraction of a predicted cluster that belongs to a single ground-truth cluster. The ARI is a more stringent metric which measures the similarity between two partitions by looking at the fraction of pair of voxels that are correctly either combined or separated, while accounting for random chance [12].

Figure 6 shows summary statistics of the clustering metric distributions associated with each semantic class. This algorithm achieves high clustering accuracy across all classes; the lowest accuracy is associated with tracks, as they can extend over much longer distances and touch or overlap regularly.

4 Graph Neural Networks Clustering

4.1 Architecture

At this stage of the reconstruction, Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) are used to cluster distant objects together: shower fragments into shower instances and particles into interactions. The reconstruction chain is schematically illustrated for the shower clustering task in figure 7 and detailed in [13].

The shower fragments are each initially encoded into a set of 22 features: the fragment voxels centroid (3), their covariance matrix (9), its eigenvalues (3), the fragment size (1), the initial point (3) and direction (3). Nodes are connected together by a complete graph in which edges are each given 19 features: the two closest points of approach (6), their displacement vector (3), its outer product (9) and its norm (1).

The node and edge features are updated through message passing. At each step, the edge features are updated by a 3-layer perceptron which combines the edge features with the node features of the two nodes that it connects together. The node features are updated by two successive 3-layer perceptrons, one that builds messages by combining source node features with edge features and the other that folds target node features with aggregated messages. After three message passing steps, the number of edge and node features are reduced to two each and passed through the softmax function to produce a *primary* score for shower fragment nodes and an *adjacency* score matrix for edges. The ground-truth adjacency matrix is built such

Figure 6: Box plot of the clustering metrics obtained with the UResNet-based dense particle clustering network. The square markers represent the means, the boxes the interquartile range, the lines inside the boxes the medians and the whiskers span at most 150% of the IQR on either side of the box.

Figure 7: Schematics of the reconstruction chain for shower clustering and primary identification.

that if two nodes belong to the same group, the edge that connects them is given a label of 1. The edge scores are used to constrain the connectivity graph and the primary scores to identify shower primaries.

The interaction clustering task uses an identical architecture and a very similar feature extractor, with particle instances as an input instead of fragments and interaction groups as an output instead of shower instances. For the latter task, the node features are not explicitly used.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Shower clustering

The leftmost two panels of figure 8 show an example of shower clustering and primary identification produced by the GNN algorithm. The third panel shows the distribution of clustering metrics on the entire test set. The network achieves an average purity and efficiency of 99.6% and a mean ARI of 98.1%. The network identifies primaries by selecting the node with the highest primary score in each predicted group, which yields a 99.6% primary prediction accuracy for this dataset.

Figure 8: (a) Ground-truth shower group labels and particle edges, (b) predicted shower group labels and edges. The filled circle correspond to voxels that belong to the primary fragment. (c) Distribution of shower clustering metrics. In the top box plot, the blue diamonds represent the means, the orange lines the medians and the whiskers span from the 10th to the 90th percentile.

4.2.2 Interaction grouping

The leftmost two panels of figure 9 show an example of interaction clustering produced by the GNN algorithm. The third panel shows the distribution of clustering metrics of the entire test set for different number of interactions in the image. For a realistic density of 5–10 interactions per image, the network achieves an average purity of 99.8%, an average efficiency of 99.3% and a mean ARI of 99.1%.

Figure 9: (a) Ground-truth interaction labels, (b) predicted interaction labels and edges. (c) Box plot distribution of interaction clustering metrics as a function of the number of interactions per image. The diamonds represent the means, the lines the medians, the boxes the interquartile ranges and the whiskers extend from 10th to the 90th percentile.

5 Conclusions

Machine Learning (ML) algorithms are the state-of-the-art in Computer Vision and offer the most promising path forward in maximizing the physics output of highly detailed Liquid Argon Time Projection Chambers images. This paper demonstrates the success of a modular end-to-end ML-based reconstruction chain which takes 3D particle interaction images as an input and hierarchically extracts increasingly high-level information at each stage by building upon the previous steps. Convolutional Neural Networks are used to extract voxel-level features while Graph Neural Networks are employed to tackle the clustering of spatially detached objects. The algorithm provides a list of interactions per image, a list of particle instances per interaction, their particle types, start and end points. The performance of each module has been evaluated independently and shown to perform up to the highest standards.

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Track Seeding and Labelling with Embedded-space Graph Neural Networks

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ABSTRACT

To address the unprecedented scale of HL-LHC data, the Exa.TrkX project is investigating a variety of machine learning approaches to particle track reconstruction. The most promising of these solutions, graph neural networks (GNN), process the event as a graph that connects track measurements (detector hits corresponding to nodes) with candidate line segments between the hits (corresponding to edges). Detector information can be associated with nodes and edges, enabling a GNN to propagate the embedded parameters around the graph and predict node-, edge- and graph-level observables.

Previously, message-passing GNNs have shown success in predicting doublet likelihood, and we here report updates on the state-of-the-art architectures for this task. In addition, the Exa.TrkX project has investigated innovations in both graph construction, and embedded representations, in an effort to achieve fully learned end-to-end track finding.

Hence, we present a suite of extensions to the original model, with encouraging results for hitgraph classification. In addition, we explore increased performance by constructing graphs from learned representations which contain non-linear metric structure, allowing for efficient clustering and neighborhood queries of data points. We demonstrate how this framework fits in with both traditional clustering pipelines, and GNN approaches. The embedded graphs feed into high-accuracy doublet and triplet classifiers, or can be used as an end-to-end track classifier by clustering in an embedded space. A set of post-processing methods improve performance with knowledge of the detector physics. Finally, we present numerical results on the TrackML particle tracking challenge dataset, where our framework shows favorable results in both seeding and track finding.

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1 Introduction

High energy physics (HEP) experiments are designed to solve some of the most fundamental questions in the universe by probing the interactions of elementary particles in vast quantities of particle collision data. As the frontiers of known physics advance, experiments must increasingly search in regimes of higher energy, higher data volume, and higher data density. In experiments such as ATLAS [1] and CMS [2] at the High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) [3], giant particle detectors will collect measurements from 200 particle interactions per collision event on average. One critical component of the data analysis pipeline in HEP is the reconstruction of charged particle trajectories in high granularity tracking detectors (“particle tracking”). Tracking systems at the HL-LHC will have $\mathcal{O}(10^8)$ readout channels to record $\mathcal{O}(10^5)$ position measurements (referred to as “space-points” or “hits”) of $\mathcal{O}(10^4)$ charge particles per event. Tracking algorithms must be able to identify as many of these trajectories as possible while prioritizing the high-transverse momentum particles coming from the highest energy interactions.

Traditional tracking solutions in HEP are broken up into several steps. One of these is *seed finding*, in which small combinations of hits (e.g. three-hit “triplets”) are identified as likely track candidates through hand-crafted criteria. Another, *track building*, involves extrapolating the candidate seeds using Kalman Filters [4] and searching through likely hit candidates at each detector layer until reaching the end of the detector. The combinatorial nature of these algorithms means their computational cost will increase significantly with the expected increase in collision density in the HL-LHC.

Motivated by the high computational cost of existing tracking solutions in HEP, the HEP.TrkX pilot project [5] and now the Exa.TrkX [6] project have been investigating machine learning solutions. Applications using convolutional and recurrent neural networks have been explored but were deemed insufficient to address the challenges of realistic particle tracking [7, 8]. Graph neural network (GNN) [9, 10] models were then proposed and demonstrated to be effective at identifying tracks in realistic data [8, 11]. In these applications, graphs are constructed from the point cloud of hits in each event. Edges are drawn between hits that may come from the same particle track according to some loose heuristic criteria. The GNN model is then trained to classify the graph edges as real or fake, giving a pure and efficient sample of track segments which can be used to construct full track candidates.

This work builds off of the previous studies of GNNs applied to particle tracking, advancing in the areas of graph construction and formulation, model performance, and full track reconstruction. All methods are demonstrated on the TrackML dataset [12] using the same preprocessing procedure defined in [11], i.e. restricting to the barrel detector only and pre-filtering out the noise hits. Section 2 describes our new approaches for building graphs with learned hit embeddings. Section 3 represents the GNN edge classifier and its performance in correctly identifying edges in doublet graphs and triplet graphs, as well as a seeding algorithm transformed from the results of applying the GNN edge classifier on the triplet graphs. Section 4 shows the track labeling performance of our GNN model. Finally, the conclusion and future work is given in Section 5.

2 Graph Construction

We present a general graph construction approach where the objective is to place as many edges as possible between entities that belong together, and as few edges as possible between entities that do not. In doing so, we first find a good distance metric between pairs of 3D hit measurements, wherein pairs belonging to the same particle are nearby, and pairs belonging to different particles are further apart. Assuming the cost to compute the distance between a pair of points is $\mathcal{O}(1)$, we can then construct a sparse graph efficiently by performing neighbor or neighborhood queries.

2.1 Embedding Architecture

Rather than learn a distance metric directly, we instead embed our hit measurements $x_i \in \mathcal{X}$ into a new Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^d , where d is low enough that the embedded space is not too sparse. This formulation is an effort to leverage existing frameworks [13] which can perform efficient queries using common distance metrics, something we will need for graph construction.

We embed points using a learned model ψ , parameterized by θ , which maps points into the new Euclidean space

$$x \in \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \psi(\theta, x) \in \mathbb{R}^d. \quad (1)$$

In our experiments, x includes the 3D hit position in cylindrical coordinates and the shape of the energy deposited by charge particles, ψ is implemented as a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) and θ are the trainable parameters in MLP.

This stage is trained using a hinge embedding loss, pulling together points belonging to the same particle and pushing apart points which do not. So for a given sample $s_{ij} = [(x_i, x_j, y_{ij})]$, where

$$y_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (x_i, x_j) \text{ belong to the same track} \\ 0 & \text{else,} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

we compute the loss l as

$$l(s_{ij}) = \max\left(0, 1 - y_{ij} * \|\psi(\theta, x_i) - \psi(\theta, x_j)\|_p\right). \quad (3)$$

p here is ostensibly a hyperparameter. By convention, for our implementation, we use $p = 2$.

Upon completion of the learned embedding’s training, we now have a distance metric d where for points $x_i, x_j \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$d(x_i, x_j) = \|\psi(x_i) - \psi(x_j)\|_p. \quad (4)$$

With d , we can construct the input graph G_{in} by querying, for each point x_i , the set of points N_i which are nearby. Then, for every point $x_j \in N_i$, we add a directed edge $e_{i,j}$ which connects node i to node j .

For efficient querying, we construct a kd-tree from the embedded points, a binary tree data structure which is constructed in $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$ time and can be queried in $\mathcal{O}(\log n)$ time. Once built, each point is queried using one of the following two strategies:

- **k -nearest neighbors**, which finds for each point x_i a neighborhood

$$N_{knn}^i = knnQuery(x_i, k), |N_i| = k \quad (5)$$

- **ϵ -ball query**, which finds for each point x_i a neighborhood

$$N_{ball}^i = ballQuery(x_i, \epsilon), \quad (6)$$

where for each neighbor

$$x_j \in N_{ball}^i, d(x_i, x_j) < \epsilon. \quad (7)$$

Graphs produced with k -nearest neighbor queries are regular, thus they allow for grid-like data structures wherein there is no need for sparse matrix multiplication – something which allows for speedups on GPU. In practice, ϵ -ball queries typically exhibit superior graph construction performance, likely due to the non-uniform density of points in the embedded space.

Figure 1 shows the process by which neighboring hits are selected from a seeded hit’s query to the embedded space.

Figure 1: Subset of hits in one event shown in the xy plane with a single hit used to select its corresponding neighborhood (left). Selected hits which fall within the seed hit’s ϵ -ball radius are shown in a 2d projection of the embedded space (center). Selected hits are shown projected back into the original space, and the selected hits which belong to the same track as the seed are shown in yellow (right).

2.2 Edge Refinement

Although graphs produced using the learned embeddings are sparse, further refinement can yield still much sparser graphs. Within the embedding model, we are only able to consider features derived from each point individually. Since we have now produced a relatively small set of edges, represented as pairs of points, we can now consider models which take as input pairs of points, as well as pairwise features derived from domain expertise.

We thus construct an edge refinement model ψ' , parameterized by θ' , which operates on pairs of points x_i, x_j and their pairwise features z_{ij} , and outputs the probability p_{ij} that the pair belongs to the same cluster.

$$p_{ij} = \psi'(x_i, x_j, z_{ij}) \in [0, 1] \quad (8)$$

ψ' is likewise parameterized as a multi-layer perceptron.

With our trained model, we compute p_{ij} for each $e_{ij} \in E$ produced during the embedding stage. Then, choosing a threshold hyperparameter $t \in [0, 1]$, we are left with our final edge selection

$$E' = \{e_{ij} | p_{ij} > t\}. \quad (9)$$

2.3 Performance

To achieve competitive performance with traditional tracking algorithms, the graph construction stage must run in sub-second time per processing unit (in this case, a shared 20-core Intel Skylake CPU and Nvidia V100 GPU) while maintaining a sufficiently high portion of the graph’s true edges. This requirement may be relaxed if high scaling efficiency can be achieved by parallelising the graph construction and GNN inference across processors, with an event being distributed. This has not yet been shown to be the case, however.

Whereas the embedding model ψ must only consider N_i points, the edge refinement model ψ' must infer over $|E_i|$ pairs of points and as such acts as a bottleneck. To mediate this bottleneck, ψ' is a relatively small network containing just 3 hidden layers with 512 hidden units each. Additionally, ψ' uses half-precision parameters which is able to achieve a 2x speedup over full precision when run on Nvidia’s GPU architectures.

We also note the adaptability of our architecture to differing edge recovery and graph size requirements through the neighborhood and filtering hyperparameters, ϵ and t , respectively. In our tests, we required 96% of the true edges to be recovered by the graph construction pipeline to maintain a high TrackML score. Respecting the timing requirements for this stage, our architecture was thus capable of graph construction where 30.3% of all edges were true edges. This result has significant implications for downstream GNN training and inference, allowing for vastly reduced computation in graph convolution, and a smaller memory footprint during training which eliminates the need to divide the domain onto multiple GPUs.

Figure 2: Recurrent Attention Message Passing Architecture

3 GNN Edge Classification

3.1 GNN Architecture

We extend the prototypical message passing Graph Neural Network architecture as described in [14], with an attention mechanism [15] and a ResNet-style [16] addition operation between message passing layers to help reduce the vanishing gradient effect. Once hits are assembled into input graphs G_{in} in embedded space (section 2), the hit coordinates of the i^{th} node $x_i = (r_i, \phi_i, z_i)$ are passed through a $(n_{layers,in}, n_{dims,hidden})$ input MLP, where $n_{layers,in}$ are the number of fully connected layers between cylindrical coordinates and the latent node features h_i , and $n_{dims,in}$ is the width of these layers (generally, we take MLPs as having the same number of parameters in each layer).

We then include a recurrent set of $\{EdgeNetwork, NodeNetwork\}$, iterating n_{iter} times through (fig. 2). In its forward pass, the *EdgeNetwork* concatenates the $n_{dims,hidden}$ features of the nodes on either end of each edge and passes this through a $(n_{layers,edge}, n_{dims,hidden})$ edge MLP, with one fully connected layer outputting a scalar value for each edge. For an edge connecting nodes i and j , this value is called the *edge score* s_{ij} , defined for the l^{th} iteration as

$$s_{ij}^l = \text{MLP}(h_i^l \oplus h_j^l) \quad (10)$$

where \oplus is a concatenation of the hidden features, and MLP is a sequence of multiplications by weight matrices and operations of non-linear activations, in this case Tanh functions. This edge score is used in an attention mechanism. The *NodeNetwork* implements a message passing forward pass, such that for each node, the neighboring node features of all incoming edges are aggregated with a weighted sum. The same is done with outgoing edges, then these two pooled vectors are concatenated and passed through a $(n_{layers,node}, n_{dims,hidden})$ node MLP.

$$h_i^{l+1} = \text{MLP}\left(\sum_j s_{ij}^{in} \cdot h_j^l \oplus \sum_j s_{ij}^{out} \cdot h_j^l \oplus h_i^l\right) + h_i^l \quad (11)$$

As can be seen, the the output of the MLP is summed with the hidden features of the previous iteration (a "skip connection"). After n_{iter} iterations, the node features are passed through the Edge Network a final time, to determine the edge scores, which are interpreted as a truth likelihood and handled by a binary cross entropy loss function.

In order to determine the best set of model hyperparameters, we perform Bayesian optimisation over them, with the goal of optimising both edge classification efficiency (eff) and purity (pur), and thereby overall accuracy (acc). In practice, we aim to maximise the value $f_1 = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{eff} \times \text{pur}}{\text{eff} + \text{pur}} \in (0, 1)$ introduced in [17], where

$$\text{eff} = \frac{n_{\text{true,positive}}}{n_{\text{true}}}, \quad \text{pur} = \frac{n_{\text{true,positive}}}{n_{\text{positive}}}, \quad \text{acc} = \frac{n_{\text{true,positive}} + n_{\text{fake,negative}}}{n_{\text{true}} + n_{\text{fake}}}. \quad (12)$$

3.2 Doublet GNN Performance

Given the above architecture, we present the results of edge classification. Figure 3 gives the efficiency and purity at different choices of edge score threshold (ROC curve). The ROC area under curve (AUC) for the best doublet GNN hyperparameter configuration is 0.997. As a matter of memory management, the hit graphs must be split into subgraphs. We find that 8 subgraphs, segmented around the ϕ -direction. To preserve edges, each full graph is first constructed, hits in each ϕ slice are assigned to subgraphs, as are copies of hits connected by an edge to those hits.

3.3 Triplet GNN Performance

(a) Doublet GNN

(b) Triplet GNN

Figure 3: GNN performance metrics

To perform classification of triplets using the same approach as the doublet classification, we need to identify hitgraph doublets as nodes in a new "triplet graph", and combinations of triplets as edges in a triplet graph. To accelerate this transformation, we first convert the edge list (the standard Pytorch Geometric COO format [18]) to sparse row matrices (CSR format) on a GPU with CuPy [19]. These two matrices, one incoming, on outgoing, are multiplied to produce a square

CSR matrix that represents triplet edges. That is,

$$(e_{CSR}^{triplet})_{ij} = (e_{CSR,out}^T \times e_{CSR,in})_{ij} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } e_i^{out} \neq e_j^{in} \\ 1, & \text{if } e_i^{out} = e_j^{in} \end{cases}, \text{ where } (e_{CSR})_{ij} := \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } e_i^{out} \neq i \\ 1, & \text{if } e_i^{out} = i \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

This efficient transformation is able to decrease the time taken for each event, from the inbuilt methods of Pytorch Geometric of $\mathcal{O}(1s)$, to $\mathcal{O}(100ms)$, thereby making the prospect of sub-second triplet classification possible. Once the triplet graph is constructed, the same GNN architecture of the previous section is used in training and edge classification. Node features in the triplet graph are defined by concatenating the node features of each doublet, along with the classification score of the associated edge, such that for two nodes i and j connected by an edge e_{ij}

$$x_e^{triplet} = (r_i, \phi_i, z_i) \oplus (r_j, \phi_j, z_j) \oplus s_{ij}. \quad (14)$$

A cut is placed on the edges used in the triplet graph construction, so as to limit combinatorial growth. Cutting doublet edges below a score of $s_{ij} < 0.1$ boosts the graph purity from 30% to 60%, while retaining 99.12% efficiency. Training the triplet GNN on the hyperparameter configuration given above produces the performance given in table 1.

	Doublet GNN		Triplet GNN	
Threshold	0.5	0.8	0.5	0.8
Accuracy	0.9761	0.9784	0.9960	0.9957
Purity	0.9133	0.9694	0.9854	0.9923
Efficiency	0.9542	0.9052	0.9939	0.9850

Table 1: Performance of doublet and triplet GNNs at given thresholds.

Figure 4: Edge classification on example hitgraph. Black: True positive (transparent for clarity), blue: False negative, red: false positive.

Seeds, defined as a set of at least three hits recorded by consecutively different layers, are the crucial inputs for the existing tracking reconstruction algorithms [20]. The triplet GNN was

turned into a seeding algorithm in which the edges with a high GNN score are selected and the nodes connecting each edge form a seed candidate. The performance of the GNN-based seeding algorithm is evaluated in terms of seeding efficiency, defined as the ratio of the number of good tracks matched to at least one seed candidate over the total number of good tracks, and seeding purity, defined as the number of seed candidates matched to a good track over the total number of seed candidates. Good tracks are defined as the tracks that are resulted from particles leaving at least three hits in different layers and having at least five hits in the triplet graph. Evaluated on 100 testing events, the GNN-based seeding algorithm renders a seeding efficiency of $(88.6 \pm 0.2)\%$ and a seeding purity of $(99.08 \pm 0.07)\%$. Only statistical uncertainties are taken into account. The seeding efficiency is further evaluated as a function of the transverse momentum (p_T) and the pseudo-rapidity* (η) of the particle that the track is associated with, shown in Figure 5. The GNN-based seeding algorithm has an efficiency of 83% for particles of p_T in $[0.1, 0.3]$ GeV and increases to 92% for particles with p_T at or above 0.7 GeV.

Figure 5: Seeding efficiency of the triplet-GNN-based seeding algorithm, defined as the ratio of the number of good tracks matched to at least one seed candidate over the total number of good tracks, as a function of p_T (left) and η (right). Good tracks are defined as the tracks that are resulted from particles leaving at least three hits in different layers and having at least five hits in the triplet graph.

4 Track Labeling Performance

Given a graph of classified (doublet or triplet) edges, we would like to use these scores e_{ij} to assign unique track labels to each hit. The approach we use here is to apply DBSCAN (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) [13], with $min_samples = 1$. Recent releases of DBSCAN allow a sparse matrix as a precomputed metric input. In practice, we take the COO-format edge list, convert it to a CSR-format sparse matrix as described in section 3.3, and assign each entry a distance d_{ij} , defined as $d_{ij} = 1 - e_{ij}$. The *neighborhood distance* ϵ is left as a hyperparameter to be tuned for the best track labelling performance. This performance we measure according to the *TrackML Score* as defined in the TrackML Challenge Kaggle Competition ([cite](#)). The score $s \in (0, 1)$ is a weighted sum of each correctly labelled hit, giving more importance to straighter and longer tracks, and particularly hits at the beginning and end of these tracks that could be used as seeds. DBSCAN outputs integer cluster labels, which are used directly for

* $\eta = -\ln \tan(\theta/2)$, where θ is the polar angle.

calculating the TrackML Score against the truth labels. For a graph created from truth, with efficiency and purity artificially tuned, the TrackML score produced with the DBSCAN method scales as in fig. 6. We see that, provided purity is close to 100%, DBSCAN will generally deliver a faithful score. The score produced with this method drops exponentially with purity, but is robust (dropping linearly) against inefficiency. There are methods that will cluster more robustly for drops in efficiency and purity, and these should be explored in future works. In this work, we settle on DBSCAN for its simplicity and fast performance, being careful to note when a drop in score is merely an artifact of DBSCAN or some more intrinsic failure of the GNN classification or embedding construction.

Figure 6: The performance of DBSCAN against generic efficiency/purity scaling

Condition	TrackML Score	
	Truth	Prediction
Doublet GNN	0.935	0.805
Triplet GNN	0.846	0.815
and $\eta \in (-2.1, 2.1)$	0.912	0.876
and 5 hits adjacent	-	0.932

Table 2: TrackML score for each stage of pipeline and condition.

We calculate the TrackML score against various possible conditions on the dataset. Each condition and its corresponding maximum score is given in table 2. As we are only classifying hits in the barrel, we normalise against this condition. The table gives the maximum score attainable with the edges provided from the metric learning neighbourhood construction stage, and applying DBSCAN to truth-level classification. This stems from the 96% efficiency of the construction stage, leading to a 6.5% loss in TrackML score. This is consistent with the generic scaling seen in fig. 6. The actual performance of the doublet GNN is given as $s = 0.805$.

The maximum score attainable with the triplets constructed from the doublet classification stage (as a reminder, all hits connected in a graph are constrained to adjacent layers in the detector), again using truth-level classification is $s = 0.846$. This is another large reduction in possible score, this time from heavily-weighted doublets that are not included in the triplet construction as they are not joined by likely edges. These are predominantly at the edges of the barrel, where they are part of a track dominated by endcap layer hits. By narrowing the pseudo-rapidity range of possible hits to $\eta \in (-2.1, 2.1)$ and removing a small number of "fragments" (these tails of longer tracks

in the endcaps) we reclaim much of the maximum possible score lost in the triplet construction. Finally, given that we artificially restrict our study to adjacent layers, we restrict tracks with greater than five hits to contain at least five adjacent hits, giving the final adjusted score of $s = 0.932$.

5 Conclusion

The pipeline presented here represents a significant improvement in track labelling and seeding performance. To apply the stages of preprocessing, KNN clustering in learned embedded space, pair filtering, GNN classification of doublets and triplets, then either seed generation or track finding requires $\mathcal{O}(5s)$ per event. Restricting the pseudorapidity to focus on the barrel ($\eta \in (-2, 2)$), we have seed efficiency $> 93\%$ and purity $> 99\%$, while the track finding gives a TrackML score of 0.932 given reconstructability constraints. These metrics compare favourably with traditional methods of seeding and track finding, and moreover allow for fast performance and parallelizability – features often lacking due to the scaling problems inherent in many traditional algorithms.

We note that several artificial advantages were incorporated into the work, including ignoring noise hits and excluding data from the endcaps. Current work is focused on incorporating that data back into the classification pipeline and further advancing the computational and physics performance of the models, including testing our pipeline on data simulated by HL-LHC experiments. We will also study the robustness of our solution against various systematical effects such as detector noise and misalignment. To meet the requirements of HL-LHC tracking we need to improve the physics and computational performance of our models. To this end, we are exploring the utilization of more advanced GNN architectures, next-generation GP-GPUs and Google Cloud TPUs, and of distributed training and inference.

Software Availability

The software and the documentation needed to reproduce the results of this article are available at <https://github.com/exatrck/exatrck-ctd2020>

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Particle Clustering and Flow Reconstruction for Particle Imaging Neutrino Detectors Using Graph Neural Networks

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ABSTRACT

Machine learning (ML) techniques, in particular deep neural networks (DNNs) developed in the field of Computer Vision, have shown promising results to address the challenge of analyzing data from big, high resolution particle imaging detectors such as Liquid Argon Time Projection Chambers (LArTPCs), employed in accelerator-based neutrino experiments including the Short Baseline Neutrino (SBN) program and the Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE). Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been the de-facto choice for image feature extraction tasks, and they are particularly powerful for identifying locally dense features. On the other hand, Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) have been studied actively for analyzing correlation features between distant objects. Example applications for LArTPC detectors include identifying signal correlations between two independent detectors (optical detectors and TPCs), reconstructing particle hierarchies (e.g. a primary particle vs. secondary radiation), and clustering particles into interaction in a busy “neutrino pile-up” environment, expected at the DUNE near detector under high neutrino beam intensity. In this talk, we present our work on utilizing GNNs in the context of a full ML-based data reconstruction chain for LArTPC detectors.

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1 Introduction

In recent years, the accelerator-based neutrino physics community in the United States has moved to employ Liquid Argon Time Projection Chambers (LArTPCs) as a central neutrino detection technology [1]. Charged particles that traverse the detector ionize the noble liquid. The electrons so produced are drifted in a uniform electric field towards a readout plane. The location of electrons collected on the anode combined with their arrival time offers mm-scale resolution images of charged particle interactions.

The Short Baseline Neutrino (SBN) program aims at clarifying an anomalous signal observed by the MiniBOONE experiment [2]. The DUNE experiment is a project that will use the LArTPC technology to measure electron neutrino appearance with unprecedented accuracy [3]. It will consist of a near detector (105 t) and a far detector (40 kt). Both of these physics endeavors centrally depend upon the efficient identification and precise reconstruction of electromagnetic (EM) showers. They also rely on the successful clustering and identification of neutrino interactions, which can be piled up with other interactions.

EM showers exhibit an incoherent branching tree structure in LArTPCs. A single electron or photon creates a cascading chain of EM shower fragments that may be far removed from one another in the image. Similarly, a neutrino interaction may produce photons that are seemingly detached from the vertex while other particles originating from it may experience secondary interactions away from the vertex. The recent development of Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) is ideally suited to the clustering of electromagnetic showers and particle interactions in LArTPCs as they may each be represented by a collection of distinct particle objects (the graph nodes) that are correlated through potentially invisible particles (the graph edges). The task thus comes down to identifying the edges that connect fragments within a group.

2 Reconstruction chain

The reconstruction chain is schematically illustrated for the shower clustering task in figure 1 and detailed in [4]. The input set of voxels associated with electromagnetic showers is passed through a density based clustering algorithm that forms dense shower fragments [5]. Each fragment is encoded into a set of node features in a graph connected by arbitrary edges carrying edge features. Edge and node features are updated through a series of message passing composed of edge and node updaters. The updated edge features are used to constrain the connectivity graph and the updated node features to identify shower primaries. The interaction clustering task uses an identical architecture, with particle instances as an input instead of fragments and interaction groups as an output. For the latter task, the node features are not explicitly used.

Figure 1: Schematics of the reconstruction chain for shower clustering and primary identification.

2.1 Message passing

The shower fragments are each initially encoded into a set of 22 features: the fragment voxels centroid (3), their covariance matrix (9), its eigenvalues (3), the fragment size (1), the initial point (3) and direction (3). Nodes are connected together by a complete graph in which edges are each given 19 features: the two closest points of approach (6), their displacement vector (3), its outer product (9) and its norm (1).

The node and edge features are updated through message passing [6]. At each step, the edge features are updated by a 3-layer perceptron which combines the edge features with the node features of the two nodes that it connects together. The node features are updated by two successive 3-layer perceptrons, one that builds messages by combining source node features with edge features and the other that folds target node features with aggregated messages. After three message passing steps, the number of edge and node features are reduced to two each and passed through the softmax function to produce a *primary* score for shower fragment nodes and an *adjacency* score matrix for edges, S . The ground-truth adjacency matrix, A , is built such that, if two nodes belong to the same group, the edge that connects them is given a label of 1.

2.2 Inference

The network predicts an adjacency score matrix, which does not naturally translate into a node partition. The optimal partition, \hat{g} , is built in such a way that it minimizes the cross-entropy loss associated with it, i.e.

$$\hat{g} = \min_g L(S|g) = \min_g \sum_{i,j} [\delta_{g_i,g_j} \ln(S_{ij}) + (1 - \delta_{g_i,g_j}) \ln(1 - S_{ij})]. \quad (1)$$

The partition score defined in equation 1 is first calculated for an empty graph in which each node forms its own group. Edges are sequentially added in order of decreasing score, only if the new partition they form improves the partition score. In figure 2, the edge with score 0.6 is not added to the graph because it would put the nodes connected by the edge with 0.1 score in the same group and reduce the partition score.

Figure 2: Schematics of the edge selection mechanism at the inference stage.

3 Results

In order to characterize the clustering performance, three metrics are used: efficiency, purity and Adjusted Rand Index (ARI). Efficiency is a measure of undersclustering defined as the average fraction of a ground-truth cluster that is mapped to a single predicted cluster. Conversely, purity is a measure of overclustering defined as the average fraction of a predicted cluster that belongs to a single ground-truth cluster. The ARI is a more stringent metric which measures the similarity between two partitions by looking at the fraction of pair of voxels that are correctly either combined or separated, while accounting for random chance [7].

3.1 Shower clustering

Figure 3 shows an example of shower clustering and primary identification produced by the GNN algorithm. The left panel of figure 4 shows the distribution of clustering metrics of the entire test set. The network

achieves an average purity of 99.4%, an average efficiency of 99.6% and a mean ARI of 97.8%. The network identifies primaries by selecting the node with the highest primary score in each predicted group, which yields a 99.8% primary prediction accuracy on this dataset.

Figure 3: (a) Ground-truth shower group labels and particle edges, (b) predicted shower group labels and edges. The filled circle correspond to voxels that belong to the primary fragment.

Figure 4: (a) Distribution of shower clustering metrics. (b) Box plot distribution of interaction clustering metrics as a function of the number of interactions in the image. The diamonds represent the means, the lines the medians, the boxes the interquartile ranges and the whiskers extend from 10th to the 90th percentile.

3.2 Interaction grouping

Figure 5 shows an example of interaction clustering produced by the GNN algorithm on an image with seven interactions. The right panel of figure 4 shows the distribution of clustering metrics of the entire test set for different number of interactions in the image. For a realistic density of 5–10 interactions per image, the network achieves an average purity of 99.8%, an average efficiency of 99.5% and a mean ARI of 99.4%.

Figure 5: (a) Ground-truth interaction labels, (b) predicted interaction labels and edges.

4 Conclusions

Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) are an ideally suited method to tackle the clustering of spatially detached objects in Liquid Argon Time Projection Chambers (LArTPCs). A GNN-based reconstruction chain was developed to cluster electromagnetic showers and particle interactions. This paper studied its performance on a generic 3D sample of particle interactions in liquid argon and demonstrated a clustering efficiency and purity all above 99% for both tasks. This method will be part of an end-to-end machine learning reconstruction chain developed at SLAC for all LArTPCs.

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Allen: A High Level Trigger on GPUs for LHCb

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ABSTRACT

The upgraded LHCb detector will begin taking data in 2021 with a triggerless readout system. As a result the full 30 MHz inelastic event rate will be processed using a software-only High Level Trigger (HLT). This will allow for dramatic improvements in LHCb's ability to study beauty and charm hadron decays, but also presents an extraordinary technical challenge and has prompted the study of alternative hardware technologies. In this talk I will discuss the Allen project, a framework for implementing LHCb's first stage HLT (HLT1) on GPUs. I will focus on the development and performance of the full HLT1 reconstruction sequence executed on GPUs, including reconstruction algorithms developed and optimized specifically for many-core architectures.

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1 Introduction

After the ongoing long shutdown, the LHC will begin providing proton-proton collisions at an upgraded center of mass energy of 14 TeV, and LHCb will take data at a luminosity of $\mathcal{L} = 2 \times 10^{33} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Figure 1 shows production rates for some standard model particles at the upgraded LHC. ATLAS and CMS primarily study processes such as production of Higgs bosons, top quarks, and electroweak bosons. At the upgraded LHC's design energy and luminosity, these processes will occur at rates of a few kHz or less. These processes also produce high-energy particles. As a result, ATLAS and CMS can effectively trigger on these processes at rates of less than about 100 kHz using high-energy signatures in single detector systems, such as high- E_T calorimeter clusters.

Figure 1: Event rates for various interesting standard model processes at the upgraded LHC's design energy and expected instantaneous luminosities. Calculated using MADGRAPH5_AMC@NLO [1].

The LHCb experiment's primary goal is to study the decays of hadrons containing b or c quarks. The combined production rate of these heavy flavor hadrons will exceed 1 MHz in the LHCb detector's acceptance [2]. Furthermore, these hadrons will decay to final state particles with $p_T \lesssim 1$ GeV, which is comparable to other particles produced in the underlying pp event. Figure 2 shows the expected Run 3 performance of an algorithm similar to those used in the LHCb hardware trigger to select hadronic heavy flavor decays in Runs 1 and 2. This algorithm selects events based only on the highest energy 2x2 cell cluster in the hadronic calorimeter. In Runs 1 and 2, the LHCb hardware trigger operated at an output rate of 1 MHz, which would result in trigger efficiencies of around 10% in Run 3.

Figure 2: Efficiency versus trigger rate for various heavy flavor decays using a hardware trigger algorithm that selects events based on the highest E_T calorimeter cluster in the event. The dashed line shows the performance of randomly selecting events. From Ref. [4].

Instead of relying on high-energy signatures, LHCb triggers on heavy flavor decays using displaced tracks and secondary vertices. This strategy requires combining information from the entire tracking system. As a result, LHCb will operate without a hardware trigger in Run 3. The entire detector will be read out at the

LHC bunch crossing rate of 40 MHz and processed using software triggers [4]. This presents a significant computing challenge and has resulted in efforts to redesign LHCb’s high level trigger.

I will present the Allen project, a software trigger on GPUs for Run 3 at LHCb. I will summarize the Allen framework and the algorithms that make up LHCb’s first level software trigger (HLT1) sequence. I will also discuss Allen’s physics performance and throughput. Finally I will discuss ongoing work and the ways Allen could allow LHCb to expand its physics program in Run 3. Results shown here are based on Allen version 0.8 documented in Ref. [3]*.

2 The Allen Framework

The Allen project is named after Frances E. Allen and began as a GPU research and development project in February 2018. Allen is a standalone application requiring only CUDA v10.2 and a C++17 compatible compiler. Allen includes a framework for complex GPU workflows, as well as a sequence of algorithms performing LHCb’s entire HLT1 reconstruction and selection sequence. After an extensive review process, Allen was recently chosen as LHCb’s baseline HLT1 for Run 3.

Allen is based on a framework that effectively hides some difficult aspects of general purpose GPU programming and allows developers to focus on algorithm development. Figure 3 shows an overview of this framework. A custom memory manager and scheduler handle allocating and deallocating GPU memory based on each algorithm’s data dependencies. Allen can also be compiled for CPUs, so new developers can contribute without access to GPUs. This accessibility has allowed Allen to grow under a development team consisting primarily of students, including undergraduate and masters students. It is also necessary for allowing the Allen developer base to grow, as most LHCb collaboration members have little GPU programming experience.

Figure 3: An overview of the Allen framework. From Ref. [5].

Only the algorithms implemented in Allen are specific to the LHCb experiment. Allen could easily host non-LHCb algorithms. This would allow Allen to serve as a platform for other high-throughput GPU applications.

*Source code is available at <https://gitlab.cern.ch/lhcb/Allen/-/releases/v0.8>

Figure 4: The upgraded LHCb detector. A sketch of the relative magnetic field strength is overlaid in black. From Ref. [3].

3 The Allen HLT1 Sequence

The Allen HLT1 sequence performs a partial reconstruction of charged tracks. Figure 4 shows the upgraded LHCb detector. Allen reconstructs tracks using the VELO, UT, and SciFi subdetectors. The sequence also reconstructs primary vertices and performs muon identification. Charged tracks are fit using a Kalman filter and combined to form two-track secondary vertices. Finally events are selected based on the reconstructed tracks and secondary vertices.

3.1 VELO Tracking

The LHCb Vertex Locator (VELO) is made up of 26 layers of silicon pixel detectors. During stable beams the VELO closes around the beamline, resulting in a minimum distance of 5.1 mm between the beamline and the sensitive region of the detector. The VELO provides tracks used for reconstructing primary vertices and is crucial for determining the displacement of reconstructed tracks and secondary vertices.

VELO pixels are clustered in constant time using a bit mask clustering algorithm. Seed candidates consist of activated pixels surrounded by unactivated pixels to their north, northeast, east, and southeast. Activated pixels among the eight surrounding pixels are added to the cluster. This is then repeated with newly added pixels until no additional pixels can be added to the cluster.

The VELO track finding algorithm is described in Ref. [6]. Charged particles originating from the beamline will produce hits of constant azimuthal angle ϕ . To take advantage of this, clusters are sorted in ϕ , and three-hit triplets are created from clusters falling within a ϕ search window. Triplets are then forwarded to the next VELO layer where another hit can be added to the track. The triplet creation and forwarding is repeated until every layer has been processed. At every layer, each cluster is processed in parallel. Figure 5a shows the VELO tracking efficiency.

3.2 Primary Vertex Finding

Reconstructed VELO tracks are used to locate primary vertices. These tracks are extrapolated to their closest point to the beamline and a histogram is filled using a Gaussian kernel based on their z positions and uncertainties. This is performed in parallel for each track. Primary vertex seeds are created from peaks in this histogram and their positions are determined using a weighted minimum χ^2 fit. Figure 5b shows the PV finding efficiency.

Figure 5: VELO tracking efficiency (a) and PV finding efficiency (b). Generated distributions are shown in the shaded regions. From Ref. [3].

Figure 6: UT tracking efficiency as a function of p_T . The generated p_T distribution is shown in the shaded region. From Ref. [3].

3.3 UT Tracking

The Upstream Tracker (UT) is a silicon strip detector located upstream of the LHCb dipole magnet and consisting of four detector layers. The strips in the first and fourth layers are aligned parallel with the y -axis and are referred to as x layers. The second and third layers are rotated by $+5^\circ$ and -5° , respectively, and are referred to as u and v layers. The small magnetic field in the region allows the UT to provide an initial momentum estimate for charged tracks. VELO tracks are extrapolated to the UT and search windows are opened assuming $p > 3$ GeV, the minimum momentum required for muon identification with the LHCb detector. Track seeds are created using the first and third layers. If no seed is found, the fourth and second layers are used. Hits are added to the resulting seed to create three- or four-hit UT tracks. Figure 6 shows the UT tracking efficiency. The UT tracking algorithm is discussed in more detail in Ref. [7].

3.4 SciFi Tracking

The Scintillating Fiber (SciFi) tracker is located downstream of the LHCb dipole magnet and consists of twelve layers of scintillating fibers. The twelve layers are arranged into three tracking stations with four layers each. These layers have the same $x - u - v - x$ arrangement as the UT. Seed triplets are created

Figure 7: The SciFi momentum resolution (a) and tracking efficiency (b). In both cases the generated distribution is shown in the shaded region. From Ref. [3].

using the x layers. Using these seeds, the hit positions on the remaining layers can be estimated to within a few millimeters. The forward tracking algorithm provides an improved momentum estimate. While forward tracking in HLT1 in Runs 1 and 2 required a minimum p_T of 500 MeV in order to limit the search area for forward track hits, Allen is able to reconstruct all tracks with $p > 3$ GeV with no p_T requirement. Figure 7 shows the SciFi tracking efficiency and momentum resolution.

3.5 Muon Identification

SciFi tracks are matched to hits in the muon stations in order to identify charged particles as muons. Allen uses the same algorithm used in Runs 1 and 2 at LHCb. This is documented in Ref. [8]. The muon identification efficiency is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Muon identification efficiency for reconstructed SciFi tracks. From Ref. [3]

3.6 Kalman Filter

Allen uses a fast VELO-only Kalman filter to fit the reconstructed tracks. This fit uses a momentum-dependent parameterization to describe the noise from multiple scattering within the VELO, improving the track description at its point closest to the beamline. This provides an improved impact parameter

resolution and allows for better discrimination between prompt and displaced tracks. Figure 9 compares the performance of selections using this parameterized Kalman filter and a simplified Kalman filter using no momentum information. Fitting only the VELO segment of the track results in a fit that takes less than one percent of the total Allen execution time.

Figure 9: Selection efficiency for $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi\phi$ decays using a Kalman filter with a momentum-dependent noise parameterization and a simple Kalman filter with no momentum dependence. The rates of the hypothetical selections are varied by adjusting the impact parameter requirement. From Ref. [3].

3.7 Selections

Selections in HLT1 are performed on one- and two-track candidates. Allen includes prototype HLT1 selections that cover most LHCb physics. While only five selections are shown here, Allen can perform (100) selections with minimal impact on throughput. These selections are tuned to accept an output rate of 1 MHz. Table 1a lists the output rates of individual selections. Table 1b shows selection efficiencies for various signal channels. These prototype selections are based on simple rectangular cuts. Experience from Runs 1 and 2 has shown that selection based on machine learning algorithms can provide improved efficiencies at the same rates. These prototype selections, however, already demonstrate the power of LHCb’s software-only trigger strategy in Run 3. Allen provides trigger efficiencies of 30% to 50% for heavy flavor decays to fully hadronic final states, compared to the 5% to 10% percent shown in Figure 2.

Trigger	Rate [kHz]
1-Track	215 ± 18
2-Track	659 ± 31
High- p_T muon	5 ± 3
Displaced dimuon	74 ± 10
High-mass dimuon	134 ± 14
Total	999 ± 38

(a)

Signal	Efficiency
$B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} \mu^+ \mu^-$	79 ± 3
$B^0 \rightarrow K^{*0} e^+ e^-$	52 ± 4
$B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi\phi$	57 ± 3
$D_s^+ \rightarrow K^+ K^- \pi^+$	35 ± 4
$Z \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$	77 ± 1

(b)

Table 1: Trigger rates (a) and efficiencies (b) for the prototype selections implemented in Allen. The trigger candidate causing the positive decision must be matched to a generated signal decay product to contribute to the efficiency. The efficiencies include losses due to a Global Event Cut that removes the highest occupancy events in order to decrease processing time.

4 Throughput

Allen will run on GPUs in LHCb’s roughly 170 Event Builder nodes. Each node can host three GPUs, so Allen must be able to handle a 30 MHz event rate using fewer than 510 GPUs. Figure 10 shows Allen’s throughput on several GPUs. This demonstrates that Allen can process events at just over 70 kHz on a GeForce RTX 2080 Ti GPU, allowing Allen to process the full LHC event rate using about 430 cards. Figure 10 also shows that Allen’s performance scales well with theoretical GPU performance and improves with each new generation of GPUs. This indicates that Allen’s performance will continue to improve before the beginning of Run 3.

Figure 10: Throughput of the full Allen sequence for various GPUs as a function of each GPU’s theoretical maximum 32-bit TFLOPS. From Ref. [3].

5 Future Prospects

5.1 Multi-track Vertices

Allen can reconstruct forward tracks with no p_T requirement. This could allow Allen to efficiently reconstruct three- and four-track vertices. Experience with the LHCb HLT2 topological trigger [9, 10] in Runs 1 and 2 has shown that selections based on multi-track vertices become more powerful than those based on one- and two-track candidates as tracking momentum requirements decrease. This could allow HLT1 to trigger with similar efficiencies at a lower trigger rate.

5.2 Calorimeter Reconstruction in HLT1

LHCb’s HLT1 has only used information from the tracking systems in the past. Experience with VELO clustering algorithms in Allen indicates that calorimeter clustering could be efficiently implemented on GPUs. Implementing calorimeter clustering in Allen would allow for electron identification in HLT1. This would facilitate important measurements using electrons, such as tests of lepton universality and searches for dark photons decaying to electrons.

6 Conclusions

Allen is the first full software trigger stage implemented on GPUs for a high energy physics experiment. LHCb’s baseline HLT1 has been fully implemented in Allen, and optimizations and improvements continue.

Furthermore, Allen will allow LHCb to increase the scope of its physics program in Run 3. As Allen's throughput continues to improve, it will be able to handle additional tasks. As a result, incremental improvements to throughput could lead to overhauled trigger strategies. These possibilities will continue to expand as GPUs improve before the beginning of Run 3.

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An updated hybrid deep learning algorithm for identifying and locating primary vertices

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ABSTRACT

We present an improved hybrid algorithm for vertexing, that combines deep learning with conventional methods. Even though the algorithm is a generic approach to vertex finding, we focus here on it's application as an alternative

Primary Vertex (PV) finding tool for the LHCb experiment.

In the transition to Run 3 in 2021, LHCb will undergo a major luminosity upgrade, going from 1.1 to 5.6 expected visible PVs per event, and it will adopt a purely software trigger. We use a custom kernel to transform the sparse 3D space of hits and tracks into a dense 1D dataset, and then apply Deep Learning techniques to find PV locations using proxy distributions to encode the truth in training data. Last year we reported that training networks on our kernels using several Convolutional Neural Network layers yielded better than 90% efficiency with no more than 0.2 False Positives (FPs) per event. Modifying several elements of the algorithm, we now achieve better than 94% efficiency with a significantly lower FP rate. Where our studies to date have been made using toy Monte Carlo (MC), we began to study **kernel density histograms** produced from complete LHCb Run 3 MC data, including full tracking in the vertex locator rather than **standalone tracking**.

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1 Introduction

The LHCb experiment is currently being upgraded for the planned start of Run3 of the LHC in 2021 to facilitate recording proton-proton collision data at $\sqrt{s} = 14$ TeV with an instantaneous luminosity of $2 \times 10^{33} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ [1]. Building on the success of Run2 [2], the experiment will continue moving towards a real-time-analysis approach and consequently remove the Level 0 hardware trigger in favor of a pure software trigger system. In this process the the entire software stack is refactored, not only to reflect the new hardware components, but also to improve performance of reconstruction and selection. One of the algorithms that is largely affected by the increased instantaneous luminosity is Primary Vertex (PV) finding. The increased luminosity translates to an expected average number of PVs from 1.1 in Run2 to 5.6 in Run3, which will degrade the overall performance of PV reconstruction. A new fast PV finding algorithm has been brought forward and is currently proposed as the baseline solution [3].

As an alternative we propose a hybrid algorithm, established in Ref. [4], available on gitlab [5], and schematically shown in Fig. 1, that approaches this challenge with machine learning techniques in the cluster search of PV finding - the part of the algorithm that drives the PV reconstruction efficiency. In the context of PV finding at LHCb, the hybrid algorithm starts with tracks that have been reconstructed from hits in the Vertex locator (Velo). Their location, direction, and covariance matrix information is used to reduce the problem from three to one dimension, by calculating “kernels” in bins along z , *i.e.* the beam direction. The z positions of the primary vertices are closely related to peaks in this kernel histogram, and it is then used as input to a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to carry out the cluster search and predict the PV locations. The output probabilities from the CNN are converted to a list of PV candidate z -locations using a simple peak finding algorithm. A toy simulation of the LHCb detector is used to train, develop and test the algorithm. In parallel, the algorithm has been deployed into the LHCb software stack where it can be used for PV finding.

Figure 1: Schematic workflow of the hybrid deep learning algorithm for vertex finding.

2 Kernel generation

The kernel generation step converts sparse 3D data into a feature-rich 1D histogram. It consists of 4000 bins along the z -direction (beamline), each $100 \mu\text{m}$ wide, covering the active area of the Velo around the interaction point. Each z bin of the histogram is filled by the maximum kernel value in x and y , where the kernel - **growing larger the closer and the more track trajectories pass the beamline** - is defined by

$$\mathcal{K}(x, y, z) = \frac{\sum_{\text{tracks}} \mathcal{G}(\text{IP}(x, y)|z)^2}{\sum_{\text{tracks}} \mathcal{G}(\text{IP}(x, y)|z)} - \sum_{\text{tracks}} \mathcal{G}(\text{IP}(x, y)|z) . \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), $\mathcal{G}(\text{IP}(x, y)|z)$ is a Gaussian function, centered at $x = y = 0$ and evaluated at the impact parameter $\text{IP}(x, y)$: the distance of closest approach of a track projection to a hypothesized vertex at position x, y for a given z . The width/covariance of \mathcal{G} is given by the $\text{IP}(x, y)$ uncertainty/covariance matrix. Finding the maximum $\mathcal{K}(x, y, z)$ is a two step process, where kernel values are first computed in a coarse 8×8 grid in x, y ; then the parameters of that search are then taken as starting points for a MINUIT minimization process to find the maximum kernel value.

Equation (1) is computed from the location, direction, and covariance matrix of input tracks. This information can be provided by a standalone toy Monte Carlo proto-tracking [4] or from the proposed LHCb Run 3 production Velo tracking [6]. While the former uses a heuristic Gaussian width to estimate the $IP(x, y)$ uncertainty, the latter makes use of the measured covariance matrix of the track state closest to beam to compute the $IP(x, y)$ covariance. The difference between kernel histogram using the heuristic and measured $IP(x, y)$ uncertainty/covariance is exemplarily shown in Fig. 2. It can be seen that the kernels are more pronounced around PVs, which suggests that – once re-trained – the CNN performance should increase. Further improvement with LHCb simulation data is expected from centering \mathcal{G} at the actual beamline position at a given z position, and by using Kalman-fitted Velo tracks as input to the kernel generation.

Figure 2: Comparison of kernel histograms heuristic (blue) and measured (red) $IP(x, y)$ uncertainty/covariance. A random single event with 6 reconstructible primary vertices is shown, whose z positions are marked by black dots. Here, a simulated primary vertex is called reconstructible if more than four simulated tracks within the Velo acceptance emerge from that vertex. Note that there are 2 PVs at about +15 mm, illustrating the issue of PV proximity that the cluster search faces frequently.

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The cluster search in our algorithm is conducted by a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) consisting of several one dimensional convolution layers. We use `PyTorch` [7] for training and development, and `TorchScript` [8] as C++ inference engine in the LHCb software stack.

Before being able to train a CNN, we need to define what it should learn, *i.e.* give it a target. The CNN in our algorithm is designed to output a 4000 bin *target histogram*, just as the input kernel histogram **with** essentially all “noise” removed, **as sketched in Fig. 1**. A first approach to create such a target histogram is to define a Gaussian with unit area and a width of one bin ($100 \mu\text{m}$) centered around the simulated PV position. These simple target histograms have been updated to take the PV resolution as a function of track multiplicity into account, which affects width and area of the Gaussians. The resulting performance improvement is plotted in Fig. 3. Further, regions around PVs that do not pass the criterion of being reconstructible, *i.e.* have 5 or less detectable associated tracks, are “masked”. Masked regions are effectively hidden during training, so that discoveries in them are neither punished nor rewarded.

Our best performing network to date is composed of 6 convolutional layers with leaky ReLU activation functions in-between hidden layers and a softmax activation for the output layer. The widths and padding of each convolution kernel was chosen by visual inspection of the data; the number of channels were increased until benefits were no longer noticeable upon adding new channels. The training is carried out on GPUs using mini-batch gradient descent, the Adam optimizer and dropout regularization.

A custom cost function, similar to cross-entropy, has been defined and it was found that its initial symmetric form favored small false positive rates at the expense of efficiency. Therefore, a single parameter asymmetry term has been added to the cost function, serving as powerful control for selecting the false positive to efficiency tradeoff [4]. To stabilize the training process in early epochs, the last convolution layer is replaced by a Fully Connected (FC) layer. After several training epochs with this architecture, the weights of the convolutional layers are fixed, the FC layer is replaced by a convolutional layer, and the network is trained for a few more epochs. Then, all weights are floated and the CNN is trained in its final architecture.

Recently, we improved the CNN performance by adding x and y position information, found by maximizing the kernel (Eq. (1)), in a perturbative manner. Adding the information perturbatively is important because the CNN overestimates the importance of these variables compared to the z information. The perturbative addition works as follows: On the basis of the original network, another CNN with 3 convolutional layers that solely processes x and y position information is trained independently, but parallel to the original network. Such, that both CNN responses at the end of each training epoch are multiplied. The CNN with x and y information will contribute with values close to 1 in most cases, but can veto kernel peaks with high x, y gradients that have been observed in data and can lead to false positives. The performance improvement of the perturbation network, together with the addition of one convolutional layer is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Performance improvements with respect to Ref. [4] achieved by modifying target histograms, adding layers to the CNN and adding x, y position information perturbatively. Details are described in the text.

4 Results

The proof of principle, that the here proposed hybrid deep learning algorithm is an efficient vertex finding tool has been established in Ref. [4]. Since then, the algorithm’s performance has been improved further by changes described in Sec. 3 and are shown in Fig. 3. We want to highlight that for a fixed PV finding efficiency of 94%, the false positive rate per event could be reduced by a factor of 2. These numbers have been obtained on toy simulation using metrics that do not fully reflect standard LHCb definitions, and are thus not directly comparable to the ones given in Ref. [3]. However, first studies using official LHCb simulation in place of the toy simulation with our metrics agree with those from pure toy simulation. We are looking forward to re-train the CNNs with LHCb simulation data and expect further improvements of the PV finding performance.

5 Conclusions and Outlook

We have presented a hybrid deep learning vertexing algorithm and its application as PV finding algorithm in the LHCb Run 3 software trigger. The algorithm has been privately deployed in the LHCb CPU software stack and its performance has been further improved using toy data.

Future milestones of the project are well defined. We plan to deploy the algorithm in Allen, the High-Level Trigger application on GPUs for LHCb [9]. Further, it is of great importance to have a one to one comparison with the currently proposed LHCb Run 3 production PV finding algorithm [3]. This means that we need to refactor the current implementation of our algorithm in the LHCb software stack to be able to run the same performance benchmark tests. In parallel, we need to re-train our CNN with official LHCb simulation data in place of toy data. We expect further performance improvements from doing so, in particular from using the measured covariance matrix of (Kalman-fitted) Velo tracks in the generation of kernel histograms. Currently, the generation of these kernel histograms is the throughput bottleneck of our algorithm due to the usage of MINUIT. We are planning to replace the kernel generation by a fast machine learning algorithm, which could be merged with the cluster search CNN into a single algorithm that predicts PV positions from the output of the Velo track reconstruction in one step. We are also investigating pruning techniques to speed up the throughput of the inference. Moreover, we plan to associate Velo tracks with found PV candidates probabilistically to reduce the false positive rate. In an adjacent step, we plan to probabilistically identify secondary vertices and associated tracks.

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Before being able to train a CNN, we need to define what it should learn, *i.e.* give it a target. The CNN in our algorithm is designed to output a 4000 bin *target histogram*, just as the input kernel histogram with essentially all “noise”, as sketched in Fig. 1. A first approach to create such a target histogram is to define a Gaussian with unit area and a width of one bin ($100 \mu\text{m}$) centered around the simulated PV position. These simple target histograms have been updated to take the PV resolution as a function of track multiplicity into account, which affects width and area of the Gaussians. The resulting performance improvement is plotted in Fig. 3. Further, regions around PVs that do not pass the criterion of being reconstructible, *i.e.* have 5 or less detectable associated tracks, are “masked”. Masked regions are effectively hidden during training, so that discoveries in them are neither punished nor rewarded.

Our best performing network to date is composed of 6 convolutional layers with leaky ReLU activation functions in-between hidden layers and a softmax activation for the output layer. The widths and padding of each convolution kernel was chosen by visual inspection of the data; the number of channels were increased until benefits were no longer noticeable upon adding new channels. The training is carried out on GPUs using mini-batch gradient descent, the Adam optimizer and dropout regularization.

A custom cost function, similar to cross-entropy, has been defined and it was found that its initial symmetric form favored small false positive rates at the expense of efficiency. Therefore, a single parameter asymmetry term has been added to the cost function, serving as powerful control for selecting the false positive to efficiency tradeoff [4]. To stabilize the training process in early epochs, the last convolution layer is replaced by a Fully Connected (FC) layer. After several training epochs with this architecture, the weights of the convolutional layers are fixed, the FC layer is replaced by a convolutional layer, and the network is trained for a few more epochs. Then, all weights are floated and the CNN is trained in its final architecture.

Recently, we improved the CNN performance by adding x and y position information, found by maximizing the kernel (Eq. (1)), in a perturbative manner. Adding the information perturbatively is important because the CNN overestimates the importance of these variables compared to the z information. The perturbative addition works as follows: On the basis of the original network, another CNN with 3 convolutional layers that solely processes x and y position information is trained independently, but parallel to the original network. Such, that both CNN responses at the end of each training epoch are multiplied. The CNN with x and y information will contribute with values close to 1 in most cases, but can veto kernel peaks with high x, y gradients that have been observed in data and can lead to false positives. The performance improvement of the perturbation network, together with the addition of one convolutional layer is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Performance improvements with respect to Ref. [4] achieved by modifying target histograms, adding layers to the CNN and adding x, y position information perturbatively. Details are described in the text.

4 Results

The proof of principle, that the here proposed hybrid deep learning algorithm is an efficient vertex finding tool has been established in Ref. [4]. Since then, the algorithm’s performance has been improved further by changes described in Sec. 3 and are shown in Fig. 3. We want to highlight that for a fixed PV finding efficiency of 94%, the false positive rate per event could be reduced by a factor of 2. These numbers have been obtained on toy simulation using metrics that do not fully reflect standard LHCb definitions, and are thus not directly comparable to the ones given in Ref. [3]. However, first studies using official LHCb simulation in place of the toy simulation with our metrics agree with those from pure toy simulation. We are looking forward to re-train the CNNs with LHCb simulation data and expect further improvements of the PV finding performance.

5 Conclusions and Outlook

We have presented a hybrid deep learning vertexing algorithm and its application as PV finding algorithm in the LHCb Run 3 software trigger. The algorithm has been privately deployed in the LHCb CPU software stack and its performance has been further improved using toy data.

Future milestones of the project are well defined. We plan to deploy the algorithm in Allen, the High-Level Trigger application on GPUs for LHCb [9]. Further, it is of great importance to have a one to one comparison with the currently proposed LHCb Run 3 production PV finding algorithm [3]. This means that we need to refactor the current implementation of our algorithm in the LHCb software stack to be able to run the same performance benchmark tests. In parallel, we need to re-train our CNN with official LHCb simulation data in place of toy data. We expect further performance improvements from doing so, in particular from using the measured covariance matrix of (Kalman-fitted) Velo tracks in the generation of kernel histograms. Currently, the generation of these kernel histograms is the throughput bottleneck of our algorithm due to the usage of MINUIT. We are planning to replace the kernel generation by a fast machine learning algorithm, which could be merged with the cluster search CNN into a single algorithm that predicts PV positions from the output of the Velo track reconstruction in one step. We are also investigating pruning techniques to speed up the throughput of the inference. Moreover, we plan to associate Velo tracks with found PV candidates probabilistically to reduce the false positive rate. In an adjacent step, we plan to probabilistically identify secondary vertices and associated tracks.

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Tracking with A Common Tracking Software

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ABSTRACT

In high energy physics (HEP) experiments, the reconstruction of charged particle trajectories is one of the most fundamental yet computationally expensive parts of event processing. At future hadron colliders such as the High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC), there can be up to ten thousand particles per event. The CPU resources required by the event processing at the HL-LHC estimated using the LHC Run-2 computing model exceeds the available resources by a factor of 4 [1]. Efficient and fast tracking software is necessary to maintain and improve the tracking performance. This can benefit from both fast tracking algorithms and modern computing architectures with many cores and accelerators.

The *Acts* (A Common Tracking Software) project encapsulates the current ATLAS tracking software into an experiment-independent software designed for modern computing architectures. It provides a set of high-level track reconstruction tools agnostic to the details of the detector and magnetic field configuration. Particular emphasis is placed on thread-safety of the code in order to support concurrent event processing with context-dependent detector conditions, such as detector alignments or calibrations. *Acts* aims in addition to be a research and development platform for studying innovative tracking techniques and exploiting modern hardware architectures.

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1 Introduction

The Large Hadron Collider (LHC), operated at CERN, Geneva (Switzerland) will go through an ambitious series of upgrades that will ultimately result in an instantaneous luminosity up to $L = 7.5 \times 10^{34} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ at the HL-LHC [4]. This corresponds to approximately 200 inelastic proton-proton collisions per beam crossing (pileup, μ) and will present an extremely challenging tracking environment to the existing ATLAS [5] tracking software [6], which was initially designed without much consideration of thread-safety. In order to facilitate this evolution, a redesigning as a new project rather than in situ changes of the ATLAS tracking software has been chosen.

The **Acts** (A Common Tracking Software) project [2, 3] aims to prepare a tracking toolkit for future detectors based on the ATLAS tracking software, and in addition open the software stack to inclusion of alternative ideas or concepts. In order to take advantage of modern CPU architectures with many parallel threads, the software is designed to be thread-safe by adhering to strict discipline of **const-correctness** and utilizing stateless tools. The code is written in compliance with the C++ 17 standard. To support fully parallel event execution, the context-dependent data, i.e. detector alignment, calibration data, detector or magnetic field status, are handled by context or payload objects which guarantee access to the correct conditions in memory in a concurrent environment. More importantly, **Acts** handles these context objects through the call chain, i.e. **Acts** doesn't really implement them (the experiments do), but **Acts** makes sure the context objects arrive where they should. In **Acts**, virtual interfaces are minimized by using compiler templating, which provides fast code execution and maximum customizability. **Acts** is designed with minimal dependency on external libraries with the **Eigen** library [7] as the only requirement. This vastly facilitates the integration of **Acts** into various experiment software frameworks. Benefitting from its highly modular and user-friendly design, **Acts** is also used as a research and development (R&D) platform for investigating various innovative tracking techniques and modern hardware architectures.

The current release of **Acts** is v0.26.00. The main component of the repository [8] is a set of fundamental tracking tools, e.g. geometry and navigation, tracking Event Data Model (EDM) *, track parameter propagation engine and tracking algorithms. It also includes a **Gaudi** [9]-inspired test framework which can be used to run event processing with prototype detectors to test the performance of the core components. In addition, a fast simulation engine used to simulate the trajectories of particles in the detector is provided in the repository.

This paper will present a brief overview of the **Acts** project. Section 2 will discuss selected components of the repository focusing on the tracking infrastructures and algorithms for track fitting and track finding. Section 3 will demonstrate the performance of implemented algorithms for track fitting and track finding with an example detector. The ongoing R&D activities in **Acts** will be introduced in Section 4. The conclusions will be provided in Section 5.

2 Acts tracking components

2.1 Geometry and navigation

The detector geometry is the fundamental component for track parameter propagation and integration of material effects during track reconstruction. Since track reconstruction with a realistic detector description as used in full detector simulation requires large CPU, a simplified detector geometry, i.e. tracking geometry, is used in track reconstruction in **Acts** for efficient navigation and fast extrapolation of tracks.

The key geometric component of the **Acts** tracking geometry is the **Acts::Surface** class, which builds up into further geometrical objects such as the **Acts::Layer** and **Acts::TrackingVolume**. The **Acts::Surface** class plays the key role for defining the local reference frame for track representation. It is fundamental to the tracking EDM and used together with track parameter propagation. In order to support various detector layouts, the abstract **Acts::Surface** base class is inherited by various concrete surface types with different definitions of local reference frame: the **Acts::PlaneSurface** with a local Cartesian coordinate

*The collection of classes used to describe track parameterisation, measurement expression, track objects and vertices

system, the `Acts::DiscSurface` with a local polar coordinate system, the line-like surfaces for describing straw detectors (`Acts::StrawSurface`) and perigee representation (`Acts::PerigeeSurface`) as well as the `Acts::CylinderSurface` and the `Acts::ConeSurface` with appropriate cylindrical coordinates. The shapes of the surfaces are described by the inherited concrete classes of the `Acts::SurfaceBounds`. The `Acts::TrackingVolume` contains `Acts::BoundarySurface` objects inherited from the `Acts::Surface` class with additional information about the attached `Acts::TrackingVolume`. Its oriented normal vector is used as an indicator of the track propagation direction, which turns the `Acts::BoundarySurface` into the key component for navigation across the `Acts::TrackingVolume`.

Each concrete surface type can be approximated by an `Acts::Polyhedron` object which contains a list of Cartesian vertices in the global frame as well as a list of indices indicating the vertices to form a face. This polyhedron approximation of the surface allows for a common representation of the various geometrical objects contained in the `Acts::TrackingGeometry`. As a consequence, the intersection of a track with all geometrical objects can be investigated simultaneously harnessing the massive parallelism of modern hardwares.

The detector material approximated from the full detector geometry description is mapped into the tracking geometry, i.e. the `Acts::Surface` or the `Acts::Volume`, by a dedicated material mapping algorithm. When the material is mapped into the `Acts::Surface`, the material effects are considered when the surfaces are traversed by the track. When the material is mapped into the binned grids of the `Acts::Volume`, the material effects from each grid are considered when the track propagation reaches that grid.

The full detector geometry description is based on the abstract `Acts::DetectorElementBase` class with a pure virtual method to return the `Acts::Surface` representation, which helps build the connection between the full detector geometry and the `Acts` tracking geometry. `Acts` has dedicated geometry plugins to build full detector geometries and the simplified `Acts` tracking geometry from various detector geometry description, e.g. the TGeo within the `ROOT Geometry Package` [12] and the common DD4Hep modelling [13]. To date, example HEP detector of the following types have been described using the `Acts` tracking geometry: the Silicon tracker, the Time Projection Chamber (TPC), the Calorimeter and the Muon Chambers.

2.2 Event Data Model

In `Acts`, the EDM used for track reconstruction is based on the `Eigen` library. A track can contain one or more sets of track parameters along the track and the measurements from which the track parameters are derived. The available tracking information on a surface is grouped together into a track state object. Thus, the track state EDM and track EDM are usually defined based on the track parameter EDM and measurement EDM.

The trajectory of a particle in a magnetic field can be described by a set of track parameters describing the space coordinates and momentum of the particle at that space point. In `Acts`, an additional time parameter is also included to support inherent timing measurement. The global or free track parameters are represented by the following set of variables [†]:

$$G = (\vec{X}, t, \hat{T}, \frac{q}{p}), \quad (1)$$

where (\vec{X}, t) represents the coordinate in space-time, \hat{T} an unit vector representing the direction of global momentum, q the charge and p the momenta of the track. The local representation of the track parameters is:

$$L = (l_0, l_1, \phi, \theta, \frac{q}{p}, t), \quad (2)$$

where the (l_0, l_1) denotes two coordinates to describe the position in the local frame, $(\phi, \theta, \frac{q}{p})$ a representation of the momentum in the three-dimensional polar frame and t the timing component of the space-time coordinate. Two types of local track parameter EDM are implemented and used in different scenarios: the `Acts::SingleBoundTrackParameters` class when the reference surface is an explicit geometry object and the `Acts::SingleCurvilinearTrackParameters` class when the reference surface is implicitly built

[†]A helical representation has deliberately not been chosen, as this would bind the parameterization to a solenoid field

as an `Acts::PlaneSurface` with its center defined at the current track position and its normal vector pointing along the momentum direction. The (l_0, l_1) of an `Acts::SingleCurvilinearTrackParameters` object is fixed to be $(0, 0)$. For the `Acts::SingleBoundTrackParameters` class, the (l_0, l_1) can represent local coordinates with different parameterization depending on the type of its reference surface. For example, the (l_0, l_1) represents the local position in the Cartesian coordinate when the reference surface is an `Acts::PlaneSurface` object and represents the two dimensional polar coordinates when the reference surface is an `Acts::DiscSurface`. An appropriate local coordinate system is chosen to allow an ideal mapping between measurement representation and track parameterization and to minimize coordinate transformations.

The `Acts::Measurement` class is a templated class that receives the original raw data as a template parameter. It contains a variable set of measurement parameters from the full track parameterisation determined at compile time. This is to achieve maximum performance. The design of the `Acts::Measurement` class allows for user-defined measurement definition which is usually detector-specific as well as an additional calibration correction to the original measurement during the track reconstruction.

The `Acts::TrackState` class is designed based on the concept of the Kalman Filtering [14] algorithm, i.e. it contains three optional sets of track parameters representing the predicted, filtered and smoothed track parameters from the fitting, the optional uncalibrated measurement, i.e. a link to the raw detector measurement, and the optional calibrated measurement with user-defined calibration correction, at the reference surface. The `Acts::TrackState` also contains additional information for the transport Jacobian from the previous track state, the Kalman filtering quality and a bit-set type flags for fast distinction between different types of track state, e.g. whether the measurement contained in the track state is an outlier (measurement which is incompatible with the track hypothesis).

The combinatorial Kalman Filtering usually requires a tree-like structure for the track states, therefore, a dedicated track EDM, the `Acts::MultiTrajectory` class, is designed as a container of a collection of track states. For an `Acts::MultiTrajectory` object, the different types of information contained in the `Acts::TrackState` are stored separately. Bookkeeping of the storage indices uses a dedicated index data type. In particular, the index of the previous track state is stored in the index data of the current track state. This allows for multiple branches with a common previous track state, which is inherently consistent with the concept of the combinatorial Kalman Filtering. A track state proxy helps read from and write to the storage for a track state with a specific index.

2.3 Track parameter propagation

The extrapolation of the track parameterization and associated covariances is an integral part of track reconstruction. In general, this involves the (mostly) numerical integration of the equation of motion. In `Acts`, this is done with the `Acts::Propagator` class, which can use different numerical integrators. The adaptive Runge-Kutta-Nyström method [15] is used as the primary integration method. An extension of the standard Runge-Kutta-Nyström numerical integrator [10]: a concept that has been pioneered by ATLAS prior to the LHC Run-1 [11], has been adapted in `Acts` as an appropriate propagator extension for propagation in dense material environment (e.g. Calorimeters). This extension is needed for aforementioned volume based material integration. The `Acts::Propagator` class also supports navigation through different tracking geometries. The `propagate` call requires a set of starting track parameters, the propagation options with a compile-time extendable list of `Actor` and `Aborter` to support execution of custom code and usage of custom abort conditions at each integration step and an optional target surface which can be used to construct an `Aborter` to stop the propagation and extract the track parameters.

2.4 Tracking algorithms

Using the measurements as input, track reconstruction includes both the process of track finding, which uses either local or global pattern recognition methods to identify measurements originating from the same charged particle, and track fitting, which aims to estimate the track parameters from a set of measurements. Using the fitted tracks, the task of vertex reconstruction includes the identification of sets of tracks originating from the same vertex and the estimation of the parameters of the vertex, e.g. position and covariance of the vertex.

In `Acts`, various primary vertex reconstruction tools are available, e.g. the `Acts::IterativeVertexFinder` and the `Acts::MultiAdaptiveVertexFinder` [16].

2.4.1 Tracking fitting

The Kalman Filtering technique is implemented as the `Acts::KalmanFitter` in `Acts`. It is designed to be agnostic to the representation of the track parameters and measurements, the magnetic field, the detector geometry, the Kalman filtering and smoothing technique, the outlier finder and the calibrator for calibration of uncalibrated measurement using predicted track parameters during the fitting. It contains a properly configured `Acts::Propagator` which is served with a dedicated Kalman `Actor`. The core component of the `fit` method includes a `propagate` call. The `Actor` includes a method to create a track state if the propagation reaches a surface with either material or measurement on the surface. The found measurement is investigated by the outlier finder. Unless the measurement is tagged as an outlier by the outlier finder, it is used to update the track parameters by running the Kalman filtering. A hole track state is created on a traversed sensitive surface without measurement on it. The material effects can be included either before or after the Kalman filtering, which allows for splitted material effects.

When all the measurements have been processed or the navigation reaches the boundary of the tracking geometry, the Kalman smoothing is triggered to get the smoothed track parameters by either using the Rauch-Tung-Striebel smoother [17] formalism starting from the last filtered track state or proceeding with the propagation but with the navigation direction reversed.

The `fit` method of the `Acts::KalmanFitter` returns an `Acts::MultiTrajectory` object containing only one fitted track and the fitted track parameters at a target surface specified via the `Acts::KalmanFitterOptions`.

2.4.2 Tracking finding

The track finding algorithms in `Acts` includes a track seeding algorithm, the `Acts::Seedfinder`, and a track following algorithm, the `Acts::CombinatorialKalmanFilter`, using the combinatorial Kalman Filtering technique.

After transforming the measurements into space points (these are created from either a single two dimensional measurement, or a combination of two one dimensional measurements), the space points are grouped into two dimensional grids binned by the azimuthal angle and the global z coordinate of the space point. For each space point, the `Acts::Seedfinder` searches for all compatible space points from the neighbor grids by comparing the azimuthal angle to form the space point doublets, and then compare two doublets to search for a triplet by comparing the radius of the three space points in the transverse plane and the polar angle between the doublet. Since the search for triplets for different space points is independent on the search order, the `Acts::Seedfinder` is highly parallelizable. The `Acts::Seedfinder` is also designed to be highly configurable allowing for flexible seed finding criteria driven by e.g. potential minimum transverse momentum of the tracks, measurement errors and region of interest for seed finding.

As an extension of the `Acts::KalmanFitter`, the `Acts::CombinatorialKalmanFilter` can perform the measurement search during the fitting. If there are multiple compatible measurements found on a surface, the track propagation is repeated with multiple sets of track parameters updated with each measurement. The search of compatible measurements is handled by a measurement selector which supports custom implementation of the selection criteria. The `findTracks` method of the `Acts::CombinatorialKalmanFilter` returns an `Acts::MultiTrajectory` object with one or multiple tracks stored inside and multiple sets of fitted track parameters at the user-defined target surface.

3 Tracking performance

The performance of the `Acts::KalmanFitter` and the `Acts::CombinatorialKalmanFilter` algorithms are investigated using both a single muon sample with the transverse momentum p_T uniformly distributed between 100 MeV and 1 GeV and pseudorapidity η uniformly distributed between -2.5 and 2.5, and a $t\bar{t}$ sample with pileup, $\langle \mu \rangle = 200$, with a simplified detector implemented for the TrackML [18] challenge and at the ATLAS magnetic field.

3.1 The Acts::KalmanFitter performance

The fitting resolution is studied by calculating the pull of each track parameter:

$$pull = \frac{v_{fit} - v_{truth}}{\sigma_v}, \quad (3)$$

where v_{fit} and σ_v are the value and error of the fitted track parameter, respectively. The v_{truth} is the corresponding truth particle parameter. If the track parameter and its error are estimated correctly, the distribution of pull values should have mean 0 and R.M.S. equal to 1. This assumes that the measurement mapping function can be approximated by the first-order linearization model or the Gaussian noise from the material effects is large enough to underweight the non-linearization effect of the measurement model.

The pull distributions of the set of fitted track parameters at a perigee surface defined with respect to the beam line (in this case, the component (l_0, l_1) of the track parameters represents the impact parameters in the transverse and longitudinal plane, i.e. (d_0, z_0)) using Acts::KalmanFitter for the single muon sample are shown in Figure 1. Since the TrackML detector is modelled with very little material, the non-linearization of the measurement model becomes significant, which results in some deviation of the R.M.S. of the pull distributions from the expected value 1.

Figure 1: The distributions of pull values of the fitted perigee track parameters, $(d_0, z_0, \phi, \theta, \frac{q}{p}, t)$, for a sample of 1M single muons. The R.M.S. of the pull distributions for the longitudinal impact parameter z_0 and the momentum direction ϕ and θ are deviated from value 1 since the non-linearization effect of the measurement model becomes significant with the TrackML detector which is modelled with little material.

The fitting efficiency defined as the fraction of truth tracks that has fitted track parameters at the perigee surface versus η and p_T for both single muon and $t\bar{t}$ samples are shown in Figure 2. A technical fitting efficiency of 100% is attained for the single muon sample. The slight efficiency loss for the $t\bar{t}$ sample is coming from those truth particles significantly displaced from the active detector region.

Figure 2: The fitting efficiency versus (a) η and (b) p_T of the `Acts::KalmanFitter` for a sample of 1M single muons and 1k $t\bar{t}$ sample with $\langle \mu \rangle = 200$.

Figure 3 shows the average fitting time per track versus p_T with the two different smoothing approaches tested with single muons at the Intel's i7-8559U processor with a maximum single core frequency at 4.5 GHz. With the Rauch-Tung-Striebel smoother used for the smoothing, an average fitting time, 0.2 ms per track, is achieved. This shows very good timing performance of the `Acts::KalmanFitter`.

Figure 3: The average fitting time per track versus p_T using the `Acts::KalmanFitter` tested with single muons at the Intel's i7-8559U processor.

3.2 The `Acts::CombinatorialKalmanFilter` performance

Among the most important performance criteria for a track finding algorithm is the tracking efficiency and the rate at which fake tracks are reconstructed. The efficiency is usually defined as the fraction of particles

which are associated with tracks passing a set of track quality requirements. The matching probability of a reconstructed track is defined as the fraction of measurements originating from the particle with the majority number of hits. The efficiency of the `Acts::CombinatorialKalmanFilter` is defined as the number of selected reconstructed tracks matched to a selected truth particle with a matching probability above 0.5, divided by the number of selected truth particles. The truth particles are required to have at least 9 hits on the detector and the reconstructed tracks are required to have at least 9 measurements. The fake rate is defined as the fraction of reconstructed tracks that don't match to any truth particle, i.e. have a match probability below 50%.

Figure 4 shows the efficiency and fake rate versus η for the $t\bar{t}$ sample. The efficiency is about 99% with central pseudorapidity and a low fake rate of 10^{-4} is attained.

Figure 4: The (a) efficiency and (b) fake rate of the `Acts::CombinatorialKalmanFilter` for 1k $t\bar{t}$ sample with $\langle \mu \rangle = 200$. Only truth particles with $p_T > 1$ GeV are considered here.

4 R&D with Acts

There are currently a number of projects exploring Machine Learning (ML) techniques with the goal of developing fast tracking algorithms, e.g. the Kaggle TrackML challenge which has a range of solutions, the HEP.TrkX project using Graph Neural Networks [19] and the similarity hashing technique [20]. The TrackML detector implemented in `Acts` and the simulation data sets provided by the `Acts` fast simulation are widely used within those projects and many more.

HEP will need to exploit modern hardware technologies with large number of cores and GPUs to speed up track reconstruction. Event level parallelization across many cores of the processor is key to gain speed. Using the `Acts::KalmanFitter`, intra-event level parallelization, e.g. parallel fitting at the track level, with many cores has been investigated. Benefitting from the highly parallelizable structure of the `Acts::Seedfinder`, a factor of about 14 speed-up with identical physics output using GPUs compared to CPU at a tracking environment with up to 100k hits can be achieved as shown in Figure 5 which shows the seeding time versus number of space points. The parallelization of track parameter propagation at the track level using GPUs has also been investigated. Figure 6 shows the propagation time using the `Acts::Propagator` at the ATLAS magnetic field versus number of tracks. The speed increase compared to CPU execution without any parallelization is observed.

Figure 5: The gained speed-up which is defined as the ratio of seeding time on CPU (Intel’s i7-5820K) and GPUs (NVIDIA GTX1070) versus number of space points for the `Acts::Seedfinder`. The orange line and blue line represent the speed-up with and without preprocessing time for the space points, respectively.

Figure 6: The propagation time with 1000 propagation steps using the `Acts::Propagator` at the ATLAS magnetic field versus number of tracks on CPU (Intel’s Xeon Gold 6148) with (blue line) and without (red line) OpenMP parallelization, and on GPUs (NVIDIA V100) (yellow line).

5 Conclusions

The anticipated large increase in track multiplicity at future colliders needs high performance tracking software and ability to exploit parallel architectures. The `Acts` project aims to provide a framework-independent and detector-independent tracking toolkit tested for strict thread-safety to support multi-threaded event processing.

The `Acts` package is designed to be highly applicable and customizable to meet the requirement of different experiments. It includes a state-of-the-art implementation of the tracking infrastructures, e.g. tracking geometry, EDM and track parameter propagation engine and various tracking tools. In the past year, the tracking infrastructures are much optimized. In addition, new tools for track finding, tracking

fitting and vertex reconstruction have been implemented. The **Acts** project is currently undergoing very active development. In particular, there is rapidly growing interest in applying **Acts** as a tracking toolkit for various experiments over the past year, e.g. the CEPC experiment [21], the Belle-II experiment [22], the sPHENIX experiment [23] and the EIC experiment [24] and a number of detector geometries have been implemented.

Ongoing projects within the community include simplifying the navigator structure, implementing the concept of tracking fitting with free track parameters and measurement representation and implementing of Kalman Filtering based alignment approach. In the future, we anticipate focus on optimizing and improving the tracking toolkit by vast application of **Acts** to detectors from a variety of experiments.

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Requirements, Status, and Plans for Track Reconstruction at the sPHENIX Experiment

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ABSTRACT

sPHENIX is a new experiment that is being constructed at the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider at Brookhaven National Laboratory. The primary physics goals of sPHENIX are to measure jets, their substructure, and the upsilon resonances in $p+p$, $p+Au$ and $Au+Au$ collisions. To realize these goals, a tracking system composed of a time projection chamber and several silicon detectors will be used to identify tracks that correspond to jets and upsilon decays. However, the sPHENIX experiment will collect approximately 200 PB of data utilizing a finite-sized computing center; thus, performing track reconstruction in a timely manner is a challenge due to the large occupancy of heavy-ion collisions. The sPHENIX experiment, its track reconstruction, and the need for implementing faster track -fitting algorithms, such as that provided by the A Common Tracking Software package, into the sPHENIX software stack are discussed.

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1 Introduction

The sPHENIX experiment is a next-generation jet and heavy flavor detector being constructed for operation at the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC) at Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL) [1]. The primary physics goal for sPHENIX is to study strong force interactions by probing the inner workings of the quark-gluon-plasma (QGP) created in heavy nucleus-nucleus collisions, as outlined in the 2015 Nuclear Physics Long-Range Plan [2]. sPHENIX will also probe the structure of protons and nuclei in proton-proton and proton-nucleus collisions [3]. To achieve these goals, the detector is designed as a precision jet and heavy-flavor spectrometer. Jets, and their structure, can resolve strong force interactions at different scales when parton flavor is selected due to the difference in mass between heavy and light quarks. Similarly, the measurement of $\Upsilon(1S)$ and its first two excited states allow different screening temperatures of the QGP to be accessed. To achieve these physics goals, precise tracking capabilities are required.

However, accomplishing the precision tracking that is required for these measurements in the environment that RHIC will provide to sPHENIX will be a significant challenge. The accelerator will deliver Au+Au nucleus collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV at a rate of up to ~ 200 kHz, which means that sPHENIX will experience between three to eight pileup events per bunch crossing. Central heavy ion collisions can produce approximately 1,000 particles per event; therefore, the occupancy in the detector will be extremely high. Over a 3 year running period, while sPHENIX collects data at a rate of 15 kHz, these conditions will lead to an accumulation of nearly 250 PB of data. The data processing will also be performed on a finite-sized computing center at BNL. Therefore, sPHENIX requires high-speed, efficient, and precise tracking in an environment in which $\mathcal{O}(100,000)$ hits are expected within the tracking detector volume. To process and analyze the data in a timely fashion given these constraints, the track reconstruction software must be able to track an entire event within a 5 second budget on the 450,000 HS06 unit processing farm available at BNL. To reach this goal, A Common Tracking Software (ACTS) [4, 5] is being implemented into the sPHENIX software stack.

2 sPHENIX Detector and Physics Requirements

The sPHENIX spectrometer is a midrapidity barrel detector with full azimuthal and pseudorapidity $|\eta| < 1.1$ acceptance, and includes tracking and electromagnetic and hadronic calorimeters. An engineering drawing of the detector is shown in Fig. 1. The primary tracking detectors are a monolithic active pixel sensor (MAPS) based vertex detector (MVTX), the Intermediate Tracker (INTT), and a time projection chamber (TPC). The MVTX has three layers of silicon staves that cover a radial distance of approximately $2 < r < 4$ cm from the beam pipe. The INTT has two layers of silicon strips and covers approximately $7 < r < 10$ cm. The TPC is the primary tracking detector within sPHENIX and is a compact, continuous readout gas electron multiplier (GEM)-based TPC. These detectors are described in greater detail in the sPHENIX Technical Design Report [6].

The physics requirements for tracking are largely driven by the goals to reconstruct the $\Upsilon(1S)$, $(2S)$, and $(3S)$ states, measuring large transverse momentum jets, and jet substructure. To measure the three upsilon states, e^+e^- pairs from upsilon decays must be resolved with a mass resolution of less than 100 MeV. Therefore, tracks with a momentum of 4-8 GeV must have a resolution of approximately 1.2%. To resolve high momentum tracks for jet substructure measurements, the tracking must have a resolution at

Figure 1: An engineering diagram of the sPHENIX detector design. The MVTX and INTT are two subdetectors that are composed of silicon staves, shown in orange and grey, respectively. The TPC is a continuous readout GEM-based detector, and the TPC cage is shown in yellow.

high p_T of approximately $\Delta p/p \simeq 0.2\% \cdot p$. Figure 2 shows an example mass spectrum of the three upsilon states as reconstructed in $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV $p+p$ collisions. In addition to these requirements, the tracking must be robust against large combinatoric background environments, particularly within the TPC. Since the drift time is longer than the nominal bunch spacing provided by RHIC, there is potential for significant out-of-time pileup sampled in the TPC.

Figure 2: An example invariant mass spectrum for upsilon mesons reconstructed in sPHENIX simulations. The upsilon spectroscopy physics program largely drives the resolution requirements of the tracking.

Currently, sPHENIX uses Hough track seeding and the GenFit2 [7] package to perform track propagation and track fitting. In particular, the Hough seeding takes $\mathcal{O}(100)$ seconds per event, which is too slow for sPHENIX's computing needs. The collaboration is actively exploring Cellular Automaton seeding using RTrees, which is a geometric indexing that provides seeds based on nearest neighbors. The left panel in Fig. 3 shows the seeding CPU time per minimum bias plus 100 kHz pileup event when using RTrees only; this improves the seeding time by several orders of magnitude compared to the Hough seeding. Current efforts to implement Cellular Automaton indicate further improvements. The right panel of Fig. 3 shows the

total time to perform track fitting in GenFit with the RTree seeding implementation. The current tracking algorithm gives approximately 9 seconds per event to perform the full track fit. Therefore, to meet the desired goal of 5 seconds per event given the challenging experimental conditions in which sPHENIX will operate, sPHENIX is exploring the ACTS software package.

Figure 3: The CPU time for RTree seeding (left). The total CPU time for the track fitting procedure in the current sPHENIX tracking framework (right). Note the different scales of the x axes in the figures.

3 ACTS Implementation in sPHENIX

ACTS is a software package that is being developed by members of several different particle physics collaborations. ACTS is intended to be an experiment-independent set of track reconstruction tools written in modern C++ that is performant yet customizable. The toolkit development was largely motivated by the High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) that will begin data taking in 2027. At the HL-LHC, ATLAS and CMS expect environments in which roughly 200 $p+p$ collisions per bunch crossing occur [8]. Therefore, the speed at which data are processed must be dramatically improved to accommodate the significantly larger data rates. This, in addition to modernizing certain tracking code, prompted the development of ACTS. sPHENIX expects roughly comparable hit occupancies with three to eight heavy ion collisions per bunch crossing as what is expected at the HL-LHC; thus, ACTS is a natural candidate for tracking in the types of environments expected at sPHENIX.

The first step for implementing ACTS into the sPHENIX software stack is to properly translate the tracking detector geometry into the expected ACTS geometry. The main detector element used for track fitting is the `Acts::Surface`. ACTS has an available ROOT `TGeometry` plugin that can take the relevant active `TGeo` objects and convert them into `Acts::Surfaces`. Since sPHENIX already has a detailed and well-tested GEANT4 geometry description that uses the ROOT `TGeoManager`, this plugin was a natural choice. Figure 4 shows the MVTX and INTT active silicon surfaces as implemented within ACTS. The geometry is imported directly from the `TGeoManager`, so any changes in the sPHENIX GEANT4 description will be automatically propagated to the `Acts::Surface` description.

The TPC implementation is not as straightforward because, at the time of writing, ACTS does not support continuous volume geometries for tracking. This is because track fitting is performed measurement-by-measurement on the local surfaces; this is not possible for a TPC since clusters can be formed anywhere within the continuous TPC volume. The implementation of global track fitting is an ongoing effort within ACTS to allow the use of drift chamber and TPC geometries. In the meantime, the sPHENIX TPC is modeled as a set of layered surfaces that correspond to the TPC readout layers. This models the TPC as a set of concentric cylindrical layers in which each cylinder is divided into surfaces that span half the TPC length in z and 10° in azimuthal angle. Figure 5 shows this current TPC implementation within ACTS.

To provide ACTS with the information necessary for performing the track fitting, the sPHENIX software maps the relevant sPHENIX tracking objects to the analogous ACTS tracking objects. These maps are

Figure 4: The sPHENIX MVTX and INTT silicon detectors as implemented within ACTS.

Figure 5: The sPHENIX TPC as currently implemented within ACTS. The TPC surfaces are shown in red, and the MVTX and INTT surfaces are shown in yellow and blue, respectively.

maintained so that the sPHENIX objects can be passed to ACTS, and then the returned ACTS objects can be mapped back to their corresponding sPHENIX counterparts. For example, the primary class responsible for cluster or hit information is the `Acts::SourceLink`. Therefore, a map is created that links a sPHENIX cluster, or `TrkrCluster`, to the corresponding `Acts::SourceLink` with the same hit and surface information. The software is written in a modular way so that each step of data preparation for ACTS is contained within its own sPHENIX module. This allows for flexibility in the track fitting process so that any of the various seeding, propagating, or fitting algorithms can be swapped in and out to test the functionality of various combinations.

4 Conclusions

The sPHENIX experiment is a dedicated jet and heavy-flavor experiment that is being constructed at RHIC. sPHENIX will measure a variety of strong force interaction physics in proton-proton, proton-nucleus, and nucleus-nucleus collisions. To achieve the physics goals, precise tracking must be implemented that can withstand large backgrounds from out-of-time pileup collisions in all three collision systems. Additionally,

the data must be reconstructed in a timely manner on a fixed computational center available at BNL. To reach the current tracking budget of 5 seconds per event in minimum bias heavy ion collisions with 100 kHz pileup, sPHENIX is implementing the ACTS tracking reconstruction toolkit. The sPHENIX geometry has been appropriately implemented, and the track fitter performance is being studied. Future results will identify whether ACTS will meet the computational goals and physics requirements for sPHENIX.

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